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1 Summary

This report was created as part of the WP2 'New IMTA value chains and production methods' of the H2020 All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project.

The objective of this deliverable was to gather, in a single document, valuable information for planning the development of integrated multitrophic marine aquaculture (IMTA) in Argentina.

Throughout the document, data are gathered on different aspects of importance for planning the development of IMTA in Argentina, such as the history of marine aquaculture development in Argentina, the potential of native species of the Beagle Channel, and their current market value and opportunities. For this, valuable opinions and experiences were collected from different stakeholders, including scientific researchers, producers, policymakers, technical staff, and consumers, who contributed small details that are unknown or often overlooked when planning aquaculture development.

In addition to analysing the species' potential, a study of the environmental conditions of the Beagle Channel was carried out, recording valuable data such as seasonal variations in water temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and light at different depths.

Furthermore, a geographic information system (GIS) was created as a tool to save, order, update, and manipulate valuable data for aquaculture site selection. This GIS contains information on environmental conditions, available infrastructure, marine traffic, protected natural areas, and coastal uses, among others.

For each topic that was addressed, the existing gaps were described, and recommendations were proposed to address future work aimed at achieving the development of profitable and sustainable IMTA in Argentina.

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3 Introduction

It is widely known that fisheries and aquaculture are two essential activities contributing to food security worldwide, providing 90 and 88 million tonnes of aquatic food in 2020, respectively (FAO 2022). While fisheries have shown constant catches during the last three decades, aquaculture production continues to increase exponentially, with an average annual growth rate of 6.7% between 1990 and 2020. In this scenario, aquaculture is commonly considered an activity with global growth. Nevertheless, the production is highly concentrated in a few countries. From the worldwide production in 2018, 92% was achieved by only 20 countries; meanwhile, 95 out of 170 countries with aquaculture activity produced less than 10,000 tons per year (Cai *et al.* 2022). This last scenario is the current aquaculture situation in Argentina, where the maximum annual production recorded so far was only 4,000 tons in 2014, mostly from freshwater species (Figure 1). Although Argentine aquaculture production has not yet been consolidated, it has a long history of development on an experimental scale through countless scientific research projects around the cultivation of native species.

Figure 1: Global aquaculture production in Argentina between 1961-2021. Data source: FishStatj FAO 2022.

According to the report made by the Argentina Mariculture Network Report (RMCP 2013), until 2012, a total of 68 marine aquaculture attempts had been distributed along the Patagonia coast (Figure 2). Most of these (91%) were on the production of bivalve molluscs (91%), mainly *Mytilus chilensis* and *M. edulis*, and there were only four initiatives (6%) on fin fish farms focused on salmonids (*O. mykiss*

and *O. kisutch*). In addition, two attempts (3%) were made to produce shrimp (*Pleoticus muelleri*) at an experimental scale.

Figure 2: Production sites at the experimental, pilot, and commercial in Argentina until 2012 (left), and currently until 2021 (right). Data source: RMCP 2013.

Thus, under this scenario of low historical production volume but a long history of development attempts, the objective of the work carried out for this deliverable was to gather, in a single document, valuable information for the development of integrated multitrophic marine aquaculture in Argentina. This information was collected from scientific publications, technical reports, doctoral theses, and even non-digitalized reports. All existing information was accompanied by new data generated during the ASTRAL project. In addition, different stakeholders were consulted, covering biological, technical, economic, political, environmental, and social issues related to aquaculture. The information was organized into five main sections: 1) Historical SWOT Analysis of Aquaculture in Tierra del Fuego; 2) Environmental Data for Aquaculture; 3) Aquaculture GIS Development; 4) Species Selection for IMTA in Argentina; 5) Proposed IMTA Configurations. In each section, existing gaps were detected, and recommendations were proposed to guide the development of future work on the topic.

4 The Astral Project

ASTRAL developed new, sustainable, profitable, and resilient value chains for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) production within the framework of existing, emerging, and potential Atlantic markets¹. The proposal gathered four IMTA labs including open-water (Ireland, Scotland), flow-through land-based (South Africa) and recirculation land-based (Brazil) systems and one prospective IMTA lab (Argentina), focusing on a regional challenge-based perspective, including fish, mollusc, echinoderm, crustacean and algae species. ASTRAL proposed to increase circularity by 50-60% compared to monoculture aquaculture and provided a circular business model, boosting revenue diversification for aquaculture producers increasing profitability by at least 30%. New and improved innovative technologies were developed, including biosensors, sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) and an Artificial Intelligence (AI) data analytics platform to be validated at IMTA labs at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 5. Potential environmental and climatic risks for Northern and Southern Atlantic regions were addressed, delivering a monitoring programme and recommendations for Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), pathogens and microplastics. ASTRAL provided an ambitious and gender-sensitive Human Capital Development Plan (HUCAP), improving professional skills and creating a highly trained workforce. A collaborative ecosystem was provided within the project framework bringing together and connecting industrial partners, SMEs, scientists, policy makers, social representatives, and other relevant stakeholders, promoting data exchange, knowledge sharing and business opportunities.

IMTA is defined as the farming of aquaculture species from different trophic levels, and with complementary ecosystem functions in the same area or at the same site. This type of integrated culturing allows one species' uneaten feed, waste, and nutrients to be recaptured and converted into fertilizer and feed for the other aquaculture species. This approach takes advantage of synergistic interactions between species. The combination of fed aquaculture species (e.g., finfish or shrimp) with extractive aquaculture species, which utilizes the inorganic nutrients (e.g. seaweeds) and organic nutrients (e.g. suspension and deposit-feeders) allows growth in this type of system. IMTA aims to aid ecological balanced systems to improve environmental sustainability, enhance ecosystem services, boost economic stability by increasing biomass, lowering costs, providing product

¹ More details about the functional groups that can make up IMTA systems can be found on ASTRAL web page <https://www.astral-project.eu/>.

diversification, reducing risk, and creating jobs in rural communities while advancing societal acceptability².

The IMTA labs were the heart of the ASTRAL project, providing the context for developing cost-effective, profitable, and sustainable IMTA production (Figure 3). The term ‘IMTA labs’ refers to the locations of the IMTA production and is not to be confused with a typical laboratory set up. The ASTRAL IMTA labs consisted of recirculation, flow-through, open-water and land-based production systems. This work was carried out in Work Package 2 (WP2) of the project “New IMTA value chains and production methods”. WP2 coordinated work in and between IMTA labs, delivers samples, data and information to all ASTRAL sustainability work packages and provides the environment for testing and validating new sensor and IoT technologies.

Figure 3: ASTRAL project work package interactions and objectives.

4.1 ASTRAL IMTA Laboratories

The ASTRAL proposal gathered four IMTA labs located along the north-south coast of the Atlantic Ocean (Figure 4). The IMTA labs include open offshore (Ireland and Scotland), flow-through inshore (South Africa) and recirculation inshore (Brazil) systems and one prospective IMTA lab (Argentina),

² Chopin, T. (2013). Aquaculture, Integrated Multi-trophic (IMTA) . In: Christou, P., Savin, R., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Misztal, I., Whitelaw, C.B.A. (eds) Sustainable Food Production. Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5797-8_173

focusing on a regional challenge-based perspective, including fish, mollusc, echinoderm, crustacean, and algae species.

Figure 4: Locations of IMTA labs around the Atlantic Ocean and the countries involved in ASTRAL project.

The results achieved in the IMTA Labs were used for Task 2.6 proposed in ASTRAL: “*Identify best practices to implement IMTA*”. This task tested the feasibility of new IMTA processes in relation to fish husbandry, welfare, health management and biosecurity and developed best practices for IMTA, including Operation Welfare Indices for selected species through ongoing assessments. ASTRAL validated the IMTA production methods, show the benefits of co-locating aquaculture species through continuous monitoring of each site and provide data on growth, survival, welfare, health,

and stocking densities. With the knowledge gathered from the IMTA Labs practices, ASTRAL delivered a “*Species for the future*” catalogue, gathering the best species to be cultivated within Partner countries’ regions. This catalogue delivered long-term production estimation per species. These species were identified based on their resilience, profitability, sustainability, and nutritious value.

4.1.1 Ireland IMTA Lab

The Ireland IMTA Lab was designed to develop and validate a cost-effective IMTA process in open water systems. Through this task, the feasibility of the cultivation of Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*), European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*), native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*), queen scallop (*Aequipecten opercularis*), seaweed spp. and spiny sea urchins (*Paracentrotus lividus*), was explored. Production technologies for these species were assessed and optimised in the IMTA system. Ireland IMTA lab operates in line with organic standards to enhance potential profitability and mitigate environmental impact. New methods of culturing native oysters, lobsters, queen scallops and sea urchins were assessed for suitability for integration into the culture system.

4.1.2 Brazil IMTA Lab

The Brazil IMTA Lab developed and validated a cost-effective IMTA in Biofloc systems to enhance the marine shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*). An assessment to establish the ideal biomass ratios between the marine white shrimp, tilapia, halophytes, and molluscs was carried out. This task studied the role of seaweeds (*Ulva linza*), mollusc (*Crassostrea brasiliana*), halophytes (*Salicornia neei*) and fish (*Oreochromis niloticus*) on the control of nutrients and organic material in a Biofloc system. Water with Biofloc recirculated between the tanks to maintain the biosecurity, increase biomass production, diversify products, and reduce the fish and shrimp feed conversion rate. Additionally, microbial communities from the tanks and the different species included in the IMTA systems were monitored. Correlations among microbial diversity, species welfare, Biofloc systems productivity, environmental conditions and water quality were assessed.

4.1.3 South Africa IMTA Lab

The South Africa IMTA Lab developed and validated a cost-effective IMTA in land-based pump ashore systems. In this task, the physical and chemical parameters of the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA systems were

monitored, including the microbial community, to provide critical information on biosecurity, species health and system health. Microbiome data were used to assess correlations among environmental conditions, microbial diversity, species welfare and abalone-Ulva IMTA system productivity. The growth of *Ulva* in recirculation and flow-through systems in aquaculture facilities was characterised, and fertility control in *Ulva* was investigated. Development and optimization of culture technology in IMTA systems to produce new high-value specie, the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*, was also carried out. The potential for using faecal matter from the sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as a feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone was investigated. The South African IMTA lab generated information on the bacterial and fungal microbiome associated with the water and cultured species in integrated systems with different recirculation rates and under different physiochemical conditions. Information and models on *Ulva*'s bioremediation capacity and the factors necessary for controlling the reproduction of the seaweed to maintain the vegetative state for commercial production were investigated. The potential to produce additional value-added products from the integrated systems was also investigated, particularly the use of effluent-grown *Ulva* as a supplementary feed or feed additive to enhance the growth, health, product quality and sustainability of cultured abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*).

4.1.4 Scotland IMTA Lab

The Scotland IMTA Lab developed and validated a cost-effective IMTA in open water systems. IMTA lab in Scotland collaborated with industrial partners to expand its seaweed farm and consolidate its IMTA site by cultivating five species of seaweed (*Alaria esculenta*, *Saccharina latissima*, *Palmaria palmata*, *Laminaria sp.*, and *Ulva sp.*) and shellfish (native oysters *Ostrea edulis* and king scallops *Pecten maximus*). Sea urchins and lumpsuckers were used for cleaning the structures and mussel spat was collected. Optimal stocking density for seaweed cultivation was quantified, and synergies of co-cultivation with other species groups were explored. IMTA Lab Scotland collaborated with a neighbouring oyster farmer and prawn fishers to compare cultivation insights. IMTA lab Scotland developed best practice procedures for native species to promote sustainable and productive IMTA businesses, including developing Operation Welfare Indices for selected species.

4.1.5 Argentina Prospective IMTA Lab

The prospective IMTA lab Argentina explored the potential of native species from the Southwest Atlantic Ocean focused on the promotion and development of IMTA at the Beagle Channel and along

the Patagonian Region. The prospective IMTA lab Argentina task was planned as a replication case building on knowledge from other IMTA labs and following the overarching approach of ASTRAL. The feasibility of employing local species from the Beagle Channel in Argentina and identifying the appropriate sites within the Beagle Channel to facilitate IMTA was assessed. Several species of fish, crustacean, mollusc, echinoderm, algae, and halophytes native to the Beagle Channel were evaluated to determine their potential for IMTA.

The prospective IMTA lab in Argentina was led by the Austral Centre for Scientific Research (CADIC) based in Ushuaia City, Tierra del Fuego Province, Argentina (Figure 5). CADIC is an interdisciplinary research centre belonging to the National Council for Scientific and Technical Research (CONICET). It has the infrastructure to develop experimental activities with marine aquatic organisms at a laboratory scale. It has carried out several research programs evaluating physiological and ecological issues of native species of the Beagle Channel.

Figure 5: Aerial view of the Austral Centre for Scientific Research (CADIC-CONICET) at Ushuaia City (54°48'41" S; 68°19'43" W) with the Beagle Channel at the bottom.

5 Historical SWOT Analysis of Aquaculture in Tierra del Fuego

The history of aquaculture development in the Province of Tierra del Fuego dates back to 1931 when salmonids were introduced from the Northern Hemisphere, supported by private and governmental projects to develop recreational fishing (Bruno Videla 1978). Since then, several studies have been conducted to develop salmon farming, evaluate the carrying capacities of different freshwater and marine environments, and test different farming systems (Quiros *et al.* 1993; Luchini and Wicki 2002). Rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) has been the only species reaching commercial production in the past, and it is the only fish species currently farmed at an artisanal scale by the enterprise Australmar, on an open land-based system.

In the 2010s, the possibility of establishing aquaculture projects with Atlantic salmon in the Beagle Channel has arisen. These projects could be an opportunity to take advantage of the potential of a natural resource and generate employment and income. However, the potential benefits may not be such if the analysis includes environmental issues, the degradation of natural spaces and the potential adverse effects on other productive activities, highlighting tensions between several actors (García *et al.* 2020). Thus, despite the potential that the marine environment of Tierra del Fuego has to produce salmonids, the last modifications in the provincial law related to aquaculture ban any production activity of salmonid species, except for rainbow trout, brown trout (*Salmo trutta*) and brook trout (*Salvelinus fontinalis*) on land-based systems (Law 1,355; 2021), although it is not yet regulated³. This law was based on the environmental impact that this activity generated in Chile (see Quiñones *et al.* 2019) as well as the possible negative impact it could have on the tourism industry (Salgado *et al.* 2015) in Tierra del Fuego. The strong rejection by society expressed in different acts demonstrated the crucial importance of having a social license to carry out this activity in natural environments.

The first organised attempts to develop aquaculture of native species started in 1995 when the Directorate of Fisheries and Aquaculture began planning a project to cultivate blue mussels (*Mytilus chilensis*) in the waters of the Beagle Channel. This initiative started with financial assistance from the European Union, installing cage raft in Harberton Bay and a longline in front of Ushuaia City on the Bridges Islands. At the same time, a salmon farming project began on Redonda Island, consisting of three 10m² cage rafts designed for the marine growth phase of rainbow trout. The success of

³ Background information on Argentine, Brazil, South Africa, Ireland and Scotland aquaculture policy and legislation can be found in ASTRAL Deliverable 4.4 "ASTRAL IMTA systems' compliancy to eco value chains standards and recommendations" available in Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/records/10777250>.

these initiatives led to a private salmon farming project in 1999 with assistance and advice from the provincial state. To support the mussel aquaculture activities, technical and financial assistance and advice were requested through the Federal Investment Council through the creation of the Project called “Support for the Implementation, Development and Promotion of the Mussel (*Mytilus chilensis*) culture in the Beagle Channel” (see Zampatti 2002). These projects took place in Bahía Brown, near Almanza Port ($54^{\circ}52'15''$ S; $67^{\circ}33'50''$ W); a small artisanal fishing village and gastronomic centre located 70 km from Ushuaia City (Figure 6). This area is currently recognised as a class “A” zone for bivalve molluscs’ production by The National Service of Food Health and Quality (SENASA) by Resolution No. 433/10, which is the highest category granted to the quality of the environment for mussel production.

Figure 6: Top panel: Location of Brown Bay ($54^{\circ}52'15''$ S; $67^{\circ}33'50''$ W), near Port Almanza, on the north coast of the Beagle Channel, Argentina. Bottom panel: Typical mussel raft used during the first attempts of aquaculture production in Bahía Brown.

A qualitative SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis was carried out to understand the aquaculture needs in the Province of Tierra del Fuego. For this, 16 previous reports that characterised aquaculture activity in Tierra del Fuego between 1997 and 2021 were gathered and combined into a single historical SWOT (Table 1 and Figure 7).

Table 1: Documents analysed for marine aquaculture SWOT evaluation in Argentina.

Year	Authors	Title (Translated to English)	Institutions and Species
1997	Sesar <i>et al.</i>	Bases for the development of aquaculture in Tierra del Fuego.	Federal Investment Council. Mussels and salmon.
2002	Luchini and Wicki	Evaluation of the potential for aquaculture in the province of Tierra del Fuego. Basic information.	Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food. Salmonids in freshwater and sea.
2002	Wicki and Luchini	Evaluation of the potential for aquaculture in the Comahue region. (Province of Neuquén and Río Negro). Basic information.	Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food. Rainbow trout.
2002	Zampatti	Support for the implementation, development, and promotion of mussel farming in the Province of Tierra del Fuego.	Federal Investment Council. Mussels, Rainbow trout.
2005	Hualde	Evaluation of the feasibility of food production for rainbow trout in Tierra del Fuego and Santa Cruz	Federal Investment Council. Rainbow trout, Feed.
2011	Bertolotti <i>et al.</i>	Mussel cultivation in Puerto Almanza, Tierra del Fuego, innovation, and sustainability.	Analysis of Innovation in Aquaculture in Ibero-America (ACUINNOVA), Knowledge Network belonging to CYTED (Science and Technology for Development in Ibero-America). Mussel.
2011	Errazti <i>et al.</i>	SWOT analysis of the artisanal oyster farming sector of the province of Buenos Aires.	Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences of the National University of Mar del Plata in collaboration with the National Institute of Fisheries Research and Development. Oysters.
2011	Fosati	Situation of aquaculture in Tierra del Fuego.	Department of Aquaculture. Global aspects.
2012	Pagani <i>et al.</i>	Current situation of the mussel farm in Puerto Almanza. Tierra del Fuego. Argentina.	Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences of the National University of Mar del Plata; National Institute of Fisheries Research and Development; Secretariat of Sustainable Development and Environment of Tierra del Fuego. Blue mussel.
2014	Bertolotti <i>et al.</i>	Production chain of mussel cultivation in 2011 in the province of Tierra del Fuego, Antarctica and South Atlantic Islands, Argentina.	National Institute of Fisheries Research and Development; National University of Mar de la Plata; Government of Tierra del Fuego, A.I.A.S. Blue mussel.

Table 1: Continued

2016	Burguener and Barón	Technological prospective in mariculture: Argentina in a global context.	National Technological University (Chubut). Global aspects.
2018	Baruj and Drucaroff	Estimates of the economic potential of the ocean in Argentina.	Interdisciplinary Center for Studies in Science, Technology and Innovation (Argentina). Global aspects.
2020	Ruiz Díaz <i>et al.</i>	The challenges in the transformation of the territory: An analysis of the case of the multi-trophic farm in Puerto Almanza (Tierra del Fuego, Argentina) as a territorial development strategy.	25 th Annual Meeting of the Mercosur. SME Network. IMTA.
2021	Carciofi and Rossi	Aquaculture in Argentina: network of actors, production processes and spaces for value addition. In search of an export boost for aquaculture products.	Council for Structural Change Ministry of Productive Development of the Nation. Global aspects.

Figure 7: Summary of SWOT analysis of marine aquaculture in the Province of Tierra del Fuego.

Strengths

- Production cost of aquaculture products is relatively low.
- Local producers have decades of experience and the necessary infrastructure for low-scale production.
- Availability of local workforce with technical knowledge and experience.
- Artisan fishers, fish farmers and shellfish farmers had formed an association coordinating the industry's activity.
- Possibility of obtaining seeds from nearby banks.
- Availability of local R&D institutions.

Weaknesses

- Aquaculture is a marginal activity, and its production, in most cases, is artisanal and/or experimental.
- The low level of business management of aquaculture companies has a significant impact on the competition and development of the industry.
- Compared to other countries, direct labour costs are higher in Argentina, negatively affecting the industry's competitiveness.
- The lack of a specialised workforce hinders the development of the industry.
- Low production volume does not allow manufacturers to enter long-term and reliable customer contracts.
- The high cost of the initial investment required to start a business discourages the creation of new companies.
- The high riskiness of the industry hinders the attraction of new investments, which affects aquaculture development.
- High seed prices have a strong impact on the competitiveness of the industry.
- Difficulties with the export of products from the province are holding back aquaculture development.

Opportunities

- The water quality on the Beagle Channel represents environmental conditions for the sustainable development of aquaculture.

- The continued growth of seafood consumption abroad stimulates the development of the industry and the growth of export volumes.
- The constant growth of seafood consumption in the domestic market has a positive effect on the development of the industry.
- The existence of national and provincial legislation regulating aquaculture creates the prerequisites for the industry's sustainable development.
- Availability of public grants for R&D stimulates the development of new projects and innovations.

Threats

- The inefficiency of public policy at the municipal, provincial, and national levels does not contribute to the industry's sustainable development.
- The poor condition or lack of infrastructure (roads, gas, waste management, electricity, effluent treatment plant, dock, etc.) hinders the increase of production volumes, the attraction of new investments, and increases the product cost.
- Decades of financial and economic crisis and political instability are taking a toll on the industry.
- Generalized climate change phenomena (fundamentally global warming) can affect multiple fisheries due to changes in the abiotic and biotic conditions of the sea.
- High interest rates on loans provided by the banking system obstruct the creation of new companies and the expansion of existing ones.
- Aquaculture in Patagonia is challenging due to its harsh climate condition.
- High transportation costs due to the province's geographic location increase production costs.
- The remoteness of producers from large urban centres increases the cost of production.
- Red tides can stop production for an extended period.
- Imported aquaculture products from other countries create strong competition with local producers.
- The population of Argentina consumes more meat products than seafood, which has historical and cultural roots.

Of all the documents analysed, the one by Ruiz Díaz *et al.* (2020) stands out regarding the SWOT analysis of an IMTA project designed for the integrated cultivation of rainbow trout, blue mussels and macroalgae in the Beagle Channel. This project was part of the INNOVACUA 2020 program “Sustainable Aquaculture in Multitrophic Marine Farm” launched by the Ministry of Science and Technology of Argentina (see INNOVACUA 2020), which was ultimately not carried out due to some technical inconsistencies and lack of financing. Table 2 transcribes the SWOT analysis carried out by Ruiz Díaz *et al.* (2020).

Table 2: SWOT analysis of the INNOVACUA project (IMTA in the Beagle Channel) carried out by Ruiz Díaz *et al.* (2020).

Strengths	Weakness
<p>S1: Aquaculture systems are positively recognised globally for their sustainable imprint.</p> <p>S2: Capacity of natural resources of the Beagle Channel.</p> <p>S3: Local scientific capacity for continuous analysis of the project.</p> <p>S4: Consolidated reputation of the final products for their quality.</p> <p>S5: Competitive activity to traditional aquaculture models.</p> <p>S6: Strong strategic project in Research and Development.</p> <p>S7: Productive innovation in the aquaculture sector at the local and national level.</p>	<p>W1: Limits in local-national technological capacity.</p> <p>W2: Regarding management capacity, a complex articulation of activities, such as difficult communication between actors and institutions, is considered.</p> <p>W3: The system to be built for the project exceeds the local scientific and engineering capacity.</p> <p>W4: Lacking infrastructure to implement a large-scale IMTA project.</p> <p>W5: Implementation costs.</p> <p>W6: Optimal scale of implementation.</p>
Opportunities	Threats
<p>O1: Opportunity to develop valuable products linked to the original production of the proposed species, such as processed products or with an additional production process.</p> <p>O2: Possible opening of new productive activities, such as new labour markets, due to the IMTA project incentive.</p> <p>O3: Due to the strong recognition of sustainability, together with commercial development, multitrophic aquaculture can be developed at the local and national level, whether in water or land.</p>	<p>T1: The project is exposed to the international nature of technology and technological capacity.</p> <p>T2: There is a risk linked to economic volatility. As Argentina is an economically unstable country, exponential variations in costs are considered, as well as the need to reduce project activities.</p> <p>T3: The aquaculture market is strongly competitive, and the increase in scale is an important risk for the sustainability of the proposal.</p> <p>T4: A difficulty regarding social acceptability is exposed due to the bad reputation of traditional aquaculture.</p>

Furthermore, within the framework of the training course “Bases and Concepts for Aquaculture Development” held by the ASTRAL project in Argentina on May 15-19, 2023, a survey was carried out among 28 participants asking what is missing in Argentina to increase aquaculture production⁴. The majority response indicates that political decisions are the key factor that must be developed in Argentina to achieve aquaculture development, accompanied by private investments and inter-institutional actions (Figure 8). It is interesting to note that those interviewed do not consider that scientific and technical research is currently a factor that impedes the development of this activity.

What is missing in Argentina to increase aquaculture production?

Figure 8: Opinions collected on what things are missing in Argentina for aquaculture to develop. Data source: ASTRAL Training course “Bases and Concepts for Aquaculture Development”, May 15-19, 2023. Ushuaia, Argentina.

From the analysis carried out of the documents from the years 1997-2021, it is observed that some SWOTs are continuously repeated, which indicates structural characteristics of the development potential of aquaculture in Tierra del Fuego and Argentina in general. Most of the weaknesses and threats are economical, and it is striking that in no case are aspects mentioned about the state of knowledge on production management, except for the lack of specialized workforce.

On the contrary, the lack of investment from both the private and public sectors, together with the lack of political decisions, were identified as the main factors limiting the aquaculture development in Argentina. At the same time, it is interesting to note that the limited (or non-existent in many

⁴ The slides presented during the training course are available in <https://zenodo.org/records/10599341>.

cases) inter-institutional action was detected as the third important factor that must be improved to achieve the development of this activity.

Regarding the training of future (and already trained) professionals interested in the development of IMTA, it was detected that Argentina has young people involved in the cultivation of species of different trophic levels. Although fish represent the group of greatest interest, crustaceans, mollusks, echinoderms, and microalgae also stand out (Figure 9). This represents great potential for IMTA development, but it must be oriented to encourage interaction between professionals and promote multitrophic cultures. In this sense, Ruiz Díaz *et al.* (2020) stated that the problematic communication between actors and institutions is a primary weakness for IMTA development.

What species is your activity related to?

Figure 9: Opinions collected on what species for aquaculture are the people work related. Data source: ASTRAL Training course "Bases and Concepts for Aquaculture Development", May 15-19, 2023. Ushuaia, Argentina.

6 Environmental Data for Aquaculture

Having data on environmental conditions is essential not only to plan cultivation strategies to optimize harvest volumes but also to foresee possible effects related to the global climate change in which we are immersed. In this scenario, a description of the general environmental conditions of the Beagle Channel was made. In addition, four of the main environmental variables were recorded in the Beagle Channel related to water quality for the cultivation of any species. These were temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and light penetration.

6.1 Beagle Channel

The Beagle Channel (54° 53' S, between 66° 30' and 70° W) is an ancient glacial valley originated by a marine ingression approximately 8000 years ago (Rabassa *et al.* 1986; Isla *et al.* 1999; Bujalesky 2007; 2011), which is part of the Fuegian channel system of the southern end of South America and represents one of the main connections between the Pacific and Atlantic oceans. Its approximate length is 240 km (Balestrini *et al.* 1998). Its maximum width, at Bahía Ushuaia, is 14.4 km, while the minimum width (1.2 km) is at the Macklay Pass (Daus 1978). Its depth is highly variable, reaching a maximum of 644 m at the western end (Balestrini *et al.* 1998). At its eastern end, the bottom is fine sand; to the west, it has coarse sand and mud, as well as clays and sandy mud in the deeper channels. Even further west, the bottoms are made up of alluvial sediments and silts (Brambati *et al.* 1991; Colizza 1991; Balestrini *et al.* 1998). Sediments contributed to these systems are almost exclusively of terrestrial origin (Isla *et al.* 1999). The rocky outcrops in shallow waters are covered by forests of the phaeophycean algae *Macrocystis pyrifera*, which generate niches and refuges that increase the diversity of the system.

The Beagle Channel responds to a fjord-estuarine dynamic controlled by seasonal and significant inflows of freshwater sources, which add up along the channel generating a west-east gradient from lower to higher salinity (Schmidt and Brandt 2001). Its sub-Antarctic waters are the result of intense mixing processes originating at the northern end of the Drake Passage, with inputs from the Antarctic Circumpolar Current and dilution due to high precipitation in the Southeast Pacific (Balestrini *et al.* 1998). The longitudinal axis of the channel is mostly governed by the influence of Pacific waters. Part of the incoming water flow is known as the Cape Horn Current, which circulates through the Fuegian channels favored by westerly and southwesterly winds and the height differences between both oceans (Balestrini *et al.* op. cit.; Giesecke *et al.* 2021; Cucco *et al.* 2022; Martín *et al.* 2023). It has a micromareal and semidiurnal tidal regime with diurnal inequalities. The average tidal amplitude is

1.2 m, with a maximum tide height difference of 2.4 m during summer (Figure 10), and the wave moves from west to east (Balestrini *et al.* 1998).

Figure 10: Tidal height estimated for Ushuaia Bay ($54^{\circ} 48' S - 68^{\circ} 17' W$) throughout a year. Data source: Naval Hydrographical Service of Argentina www.hidro.gov.ar.

In the Argentine sector of the Beagle Channel, Gable Island represents a point of separation in bathymetric and oceanographic characteristics. To the west the depth is greater and the water column, below the pycnocline, presents stratification almost all year round (Martín *et al.* 2023). To the east of the island, the basin is shallower and receives a greater influence of Atlantic waters. The shallow depths and presence of paleomoraines in Mackinlay Pass (and Murray Channel) and the presence of Gable Island limit the inflow of Atlantic Ocean waters to the inner channel (Gordillo *et al.* 2005; Giesecke *et al.* 2021; Cucco *et al.* 2022). Its waters are subsidized by nutrients of terrigenous origin (Amin *et al.* 2010; Cardona Garzón *et al.* 2016) and, although certain coastal areas are characterized by a high concentration of nutrients, it is considered to have a low concentration of chlorophyll. It has been suggested that light may be the limiting factor for phytoplankton production (Pizarro *et al.* 2005; Amin *et al.* 2010). In coastal areas, elevated nutrient values seem to indicate an allochthonous input of organic matter, either by drainage from surrounding forests, soils, and peatlands, or even of anthropogenic origin (i.e. sewage, garbage, waste; Biancalana *et al.* 2014). However, in Channel waters, it has been shown that silicate concentration is limiting the proliferation of diatoms and other silica-dependent organisms (Iachetti *et al.* 2021).

The Beagle Channel is known for its biodiversity and its importance to local communities. The demand for ecosystem services supported by the Beagle Channel from different local and foreign actors is growing. Examples of this are the productive private sector (e.g., salmon farming, tourism, the commercial exploitation of common resources such as king crab and sardine) and the needs of the regional government-sectors to define uses and regulations of the coastal areas of the region. It is a marine ecosystem potentially vulnerable to human impacts. The main urban settlements on the Beagle Channel, Ushuaia (on the Argentine side) and Puerto Williams (on the Chilean side) are growing, and the Beagle Channel has become a logistic corridor to supply these cities, and is experiencing a growing flow of marine traffic, due to the activity of tourist cruise ships (more than 500 port arrivals in 2022-23). This demand is shaped by a series of outstanding benefits for the development of the province and by a set of emerging ones that may result in negative impacts, if not properly monitored and incorporated into management guidelines. In 2019, a collaborative scientific cruise in the shared, bi-national (Chile and Argentina) sector of the Beagle Channel was performed and, recently (2023), the results of this and previous relevant surveys have been published (special issue) hoping to provide key scientific results as well as inputs for decision-makers and public policies of the two countries (Ferreyra and González 2023).

For the Argentine sector of the Beagle Channel, zooplankton is relatively well-known from a taxonomic and ecological point of view, including seasonal fluctuation studies (Lovrich 1999; Fernandez-Severini and Hoffmeyer 2005; Biancalana *et al.* 2007; 2011; 2014; Aguirre *et al.* 2012; Presta *et al.* 2015; 2023a; 2023b; Diez *et al.* 2016). On the other hand, studies on unicellular plankton are scarcer. They are mainly focused on phytoplankton although with an emphasis on toxic algae and red tide phenomena as a threat to the mussel aquaculture industry (Vinuesa 1993; Benavides *et al.* 1995; Hernando *et al.* 2007; Almandoz *et al.* 2008; 2014; Cadaillon *et al.* 2022; Schloss *et al.* 2023) or on the effects of UV-B radiation attributed to the thinning of the ozone layer (Hernando and San Roman 1999; Moreau *et al.* 2014). There are also specific studies carried out in Bahía de Ushuaia Bahía Golondrina and surrounding areas focusing on pollutants (Duarte 2011; Gil *et al.* 2011), eutrophication and terrigenous influence (Torres *et al.* 2009 Amin *et al.* 2010).

The Beagle Channel has a water flow in a west-east direction connecting the Pacific Ocean with the Atlantic Ocean. It is a semi-estuarine environment with a seasonal dynamic tightly related to freshwater input from precipitation and glacial melt (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Typical landscape of the Beagle Channel with the Chilean mountain at the bottom.

Water enters the Beagle Channel from its western entrance, predominantly along the Northwest branch (see Figure 12A) and flows eastwards. In the central sector of the Beagle Channel (see Figure 12B), the residual circulation is characterized by a more complex pattern due to the presence of morphological features such as Ushuaia Bay, several islands, and the Murray Channel. An intensification of the residual flow is evident approaching the Mackinlay Strait where the highest residual currents are found (see Figure 12C).

Figure 12: Vertically averaged residual circulation computed for the eastern sector of the Beagle Channel. Asterisk in Figure C indicates Brown Bay location. Taken from Cucco *et al.* (2022).

Brown Bay is the area with the highest water residence time (WRT) of the Beagle Channel, with higher values in winter (~80-85 days) and lower values in summer (~40-45 days) and intermediate values in the other seasons (Cucco *et al.* 2022; Figure 13).

Figure 13: Vertically averaged water residence times computed for summer (A), autumn (B), winter (C) and spring (D). Asterisk indicates Brown Bay location. Taken from Cucco et al. (2022).

6.2 Atmospheric Data

Atmospheric data were obtained from the meteorological station at Williams Port, Chile (-54.9333 S, -67.6333 W) located 7.7 km from Almanza River, available at Meteostat service <https://meteostat.net/es/>.

The atmospheric mean temperature fluctuates between 0.5 in winter and 10.7°C in summer, with only four days reaching an absolute maximum over 20°C (Figure 14A). The pressure was almost constant throughout the year, with value around 1,000 hPa, and lower peaks around 965 hPa or lower (Figure 14B). These values are low compared to other latitudes in Argentina, for example,

Puerto Madryn located at 42.7°S has values between 1008.2 and 1014.7 hPa (Data from 2023; <https://meteostat.net/es/>). This condition is important because atmospheric pressure directly affects the concentration of oxygen in water, which makes it necessary to pay special attention to monitoring these parameters, which may not be an important factor at other latitudes.

The annual mean wind speed was around 10 km/h, while the monthly maximum speed was between 75 and 90 km/h, with a southwest predominant direction (Figure 14C). All months showed at least one day with maximum wind speed between 44 and 85 km/h.

The total annual precipitations were between 753.0 mm in 2022 and 681.3 mm in 2023, with no seasonal fluctuations (Figure 14D).

Figure 14: Daily atmospheric data of Puerto Williams (gray lines) and monthly means (green lines) recorded from September 2021 to September 2023. Data source: Meteostat service <https://meteostat.net/es/>.

Only the maximum winds were analyzed for wind direction since they are the most important when designing mooring structures. A predominant southwesterly direction was observed throughout the year, while in winter (July, August, and September), an increase in the frequency of north and west winds was also observed (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Monthly wind direction and speed (Km/h) recorded in Puerto Williams. Data source Meteostat service <https://meteostat.net/es/>.

6.3 Water quality

6.3.1 Brown Bay

Two lines with sensors for recording temperature (data logger HOBO MX2201), conductivity (data logger HOBO U24-002) and light (data logger HOBO MX2202) were deployed inside and outside of Brown Bay (Figure 16). These sensor lines were continuously watched by fishermen of Port Almanza

from the coast and by personnel of the Secretary of Fisheries of the Province of Tierra del Fuego, who were meant to clean the sensors periodically and check the conditions of the moors, ropes, and fouling. This maintenance was only sometimes on time, and in many cases, sensors were found to be fouling when downloading data, most probably interfering with the measurements.

Figure 16: Sites where the sensors were anchored in the Brown Bay, and localization of Almanza River where sensors of temperature and water level were deployed.

The line anchored inside the Brown Bay ($54^{\circ}51'47.06''S$; $67^{\circ}30'29.76''W$) consisted of two sensors measuring conductivity and temperature and two measuring only temperature (Figure 17). This line was deployed at 20 m depth, pending from a mussel raft, thanks to the authorization that Fabián Valdes, a local fisher, and aquaculture producer, granted us.

Figure 17: Line of sensors attached to a mussel raft inside Brown Bay ($54^{\circ}51'47.06''S$; $67^{\circ}30'29.76''W$).

The second line deployed outside the Brown Bay ($54^{\circ}52'23.60''S$ $67^{\circ}32'36.71''W$) consisted of a fixed line moored at 27 m depth with a weight of 140 kg and a rectangular styrofoam buoy (80x40x40 cm). A plastic pipe of 2 m connects this buoy to two circular hard plastic buoys from where the sensor line was fixed (Figure 18). The line rises and falls following the tide behaviour, recording the data at the same depth from the surface. This line was fitted with two sensors measuring conductivity and temperature and four measuring light and temperature. The light sensor was fixed to ensure it remained parallel to the surface of the water (Figure 19). The tow hitch on top of the conductivity sensor's protective housing and the threaded tube where the light sensor attaches allow for easy retrieval and work freely with the sensors.

In addition to continuous records using automatic dataloggers, monthly measurements of temperature, conductivity and oxygen in the water column were carried out with a CTD (Rinko-Profiler, ASTD-102, JFE Advantech Co., Ltd., Japan) between June 2022 and May 2023. For this, the

Shenu scientific vessel belonging to the Austral Center for Scientific Research was used, and the operations were carried out in collaboration with the Argentine Marine Observation Network (ROMA). The sampling site was located close to the site where the sensor line was located outside Brown Bay (Figure 20).

Figure 20: BIC Shenu used to record temperature, conductivity, and water temperature monthly with CTD in the water column outside of Brown Bay (Beagle Channel).

The monthly mean temperature at 1 and 17 m depths for the whole time series can be seen in Figure 21, whereas Figure 22 shows all four surveyed depths. The average temperature in 2023 was lower than in 2022, and the difference was more evident in deeper waters. Water temperature showed a clear seasonal pattern with lower values in winter and higher in summer. For the Outside site, the average temperature was 7.29 °C and maximum and minimum values recorded for temperature were 12.45 °C and 4.24 °C at 1m, 11.05 °C and 4.20 °C at 17m, respectively. For the Inside sites, the average temperature value was 7.11 °C. Minimum values were lower, and maximum values were higher than those of the Outside site, with maximum and minimum values of 12.92 °C and 3.42 °C on the surface and 11.76 and 3.41 °C above the seabed.

The water column was fully mixed throughout the autumn and winter of both surveyed years except for the summer months when atmospheric heating and water inflow induced stratification of the water column, which was more evident in summer 2023 than in summer 2022 (Figure 22).

Figure 21: Maximum (red lines), minimum (blue lines) and mean (green lines) monthly water temperature recorded in Brown Bay (Beagle Channel) during two consecutive years.

Figure 22: Water temperature recorded inside (upper pannel) and outside (bottom pannel) the Brown Bay (Beagle Channel) every 15 minutes at four depths.

Average and maximum salinity values in 2022 were higher than in 2023 and generally higher in deeper waters, except when the water column was well mixed. For the outside site, the average salinity was 27.47, and maximum and minimum values recorded for salinity were 33.19 and 20.68 at 1m, 32.19 and 12.15 at 17m, respectively. For the Inside sites, the average salinity value was 28.42, and changes in salinity showed less amplitude (probably more stable) than those of the Outside site, with maximum and minimum values of 31.49 and 21.99 in surface and 13.84 and 32.03 above the seabed.

Salinity records in the Beagle Channel are typically higher in winter and lower in spring and summer, as described in Section 6.1, and shown in Figure 23 and Figure 24. Salinity could be influenced by freshwater input. from the Almanza River located 1.5 km. from the “outside” sampling site at Brown Bay (Figure 16 and Section 6.3.2). Additionally, surface water currents in Brown Bay appear to be causing water to circulate counterclockwise within the bay, which would encourage an accumulation of fresh water. In addition to the Almanza River, there is a small freshwater inlet at the inner side of

the bay, just 1 km from the “Inside” sampling site. Therefore, both moorings could be registering drops in salinity caused by the freshwater inflow. Nevertheless, only for the Outside site surface, a low and negative correlation (Spearman $r=-0.13$, $p<0.001$) was found between salinity values and the freshwater inlet from the Almanza River. The flow of the Almanza River did not follow a seasonal pattern, showing several flow peaks, potentially explained by rains and events of snow melting (see Section 6.3.2), which may explain the low peak in salinity records in the outside mooring and the drops in salinity recorded at certain moments of the sampling period.

On November 7th, 2022, more oxygenated, warmer, and low salinity waters were registered in surface waters (Figure 24), and for December 8th, 2022, and January 6th, 2023, high Brunt Vaisala frequency values were registered in superficial waters. Towards February, wind-driven mixing deepens the mixed layer almost to the bottom.

Figure 23: Maximum (red lines), minimum (blue lines) and mean (green lines) monthly water salinity recorded in Brown Bay (Beagle Channel) during two consecutive years.

Figure 24: Vertical profiles of salinity (top panel), temperature (mid panel), and dissolved oxygen (bottom panel) recorded outside Brown Bay throughout one year with CTD.

PAR (Photosynthetic Active Radiation) was measured as Lux on the surface and at two consecutive depths, 6 and 11 m, was also measured in the outside bay mooring (Figure 25). The 6m and the 11m PAR sensors stopped working and were replaced over time, but this took more than eight months; therefore, the data record was not continuous throughout the two years. The PAR intensity was higher in spring and summer and lower in autumn-winter months when light hours are less due to the latitude (6:18, light: dark). Nevertheless, the cloud cover is high year-round; therefore, PAR measurement varies permanently throughout the day.

Figure 25: PAR measured in Lux for 1; 6; and 11 meters in the Outside mooring at Brown Bay (Beagle Channel) every 15 minutes, for two years.

At this point, it is important to highlight that for most automatic sensors monitoring water parameters, biofouling is the most critical factor affecting operation, maintenance, and data quality (Delgado *et al.* 2021). Of all the sensors used in this report to monitor the environmental conditions of the Beagle Channel, the one used to record PAR was the one that had the most significant biofouling issues (Figure 26). To avoid this drawback, the only possible strategy is to routinely clean the sensors, which is a cost that must be added when estimating the performance and actual cost of the sensors.

Figure 26: Fouling in the lines of sensors. Right panel: Fouled container of conductivity sensor and Left panel: Fouled PAR sensor causing problems in accurately measuring light penetration.

6.3.2 Almanza River

In addition to recording environmental parameters in the Brown Bay, a sensor was placed to record temperature and water level (pressure; data logger HOBO U20L-04) in the Almanza River, which is the nearest freshwater stream outflowing to the Bay (Figure 27). Almanza River is the nearest freshwater inlet to the Brown Bay and there is no previous data recorded about its flow dynamic and temperature. Almanza River basin has no anthropic use along its entire length; it is fully forested and is not lake-fed. The sensor was fixed at the bottom of the river and manual measurements of the flow were made with a flow probe (FP111, Global Water Solutions Ltd., China) to later transform the pressure data obtained by the sensor into flow.

Figure 27: View of the Almanza River flowing to the Beagle Channel, near Brown Bay, where water level datalogger was deployed.

The water temperature showed a typical seasonal pattern, with minimum values in July-August and maximum values in January-February (Figure 28). The maximum temperature recorded rose up to 11-13°C between December and February, while the minimum mean daily temperature was 0°C during several days between June and August. Ice at the bank river was registered during the cold season, but the river surface was never fully ice covered.

Figure 28: Temperature at Almanza River recorded between September 2021 and October 2023.

The discharge of the Almanza River showed an erratic pattern throughout the year (Figure 29). In this sense, you will notice a basal flow rate of approximately 0.99 m³/sec, with sporadic peaks that can

exceed 8 m³/sec. These spikes could be due not only to precipitation, but also to sudden increases in temperatures, which would cause snow melt.

Figure 29: Discharge at Almanza River recorded between September 2021 and October 2023.

6.4 Gaps and Recommendation

Having timeline records of environmental variables, such as temperature, conductivity, and oxygen, is crucial to designing management strategies for aquaculture production to achieve profitability. To accurately understand the variation of these parameters and their relationship with production variables (e.g. growth and stocking densities), it is necessary to carry out continuous monitoring programs sustained over time, demanding the appropriate equipment and trained personnel⁵. Carrying out this task is expensive and time-consuming for producers, so an alternative could be for public or private research centres to carry out this task by providing specialized services. Another strategy could be for provincial technical personnel to supervise monitoring through technical advisory agreements with the private sector. This agreement would allow long-term programs to be deployed in an orderly and systematic way. However, this must be accompanied by data collection from producers themselves since this would allow not only the expansion of the geographical scope of the records but also the acquisition of information on specific parameters that are of interest for particular activities and escape the framework of a general monitoring program.

⁵ ASTRAL developed a «Technology User Guide for Training Courses and Apprenticeship» that can be found in <https://zenodo.org/records/7521394>.

These monitoring programs take on even greater relevance in current climate change and global warming. One of the main effects of global warming on aquaculture production is caused through ocean acidification (Narita *et al.* 2012). In this sense, it is known that acidification drastically affects the production of bivalves since it decreases the calcification of their valves (Tan *et al.* 2020). For fish, the potential effect of predicted temperature increases and $p\text{CO}_2$ in the Beagle Channel has been studied, demonstrating that these conditions could reduce the thermal tolerance range and aerobic range (Lattuca *et al.* 2022).

Another area for improvement in monitoring the environment is the necessity to reduce the cost of sensors. For this reason, ASTRAL developed low-cost technological solutions for aquaculture to make these types of equipment affordable for producers⁶.

⁶ More information about technological solutions developed by ASTRAL can be found in <https://www.astral-project.eu/astral-solutions>.

7 Aquaculture GIS Development

Planning the use of marine areas for aquaculture through the development of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has taken on great importance recently (Nath *et al.* 2000; Falconer *et al.* 2020). This is because GIS allows decision-making through the analysis and integration of a large amount of data of various kinds gathered in a single database. This system allows the incorporation of information on optimal environmental conditions for farm species and relevant data to develop strategies throughout the entire production chain, from service providers and inputs to the final marketing of the product. The recommended actions of the strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture in 2021–2030 (EC 2021) stated explicitly the need to “Develop a more detailed guidance document on the planning for space and access to water for marine, freshwater and land-based aquaculture”, highlighting the importance of the GIS.

Argentina is the eighth country in the world regarding surface area, with a large stretch of coastline reaching 4,500 km. This makes it an attractive country for developing a blue economy. In this sense, the FAO indicates that Argentina has the largest surface area suitable for developing marine aquaculture in terms of sea surface temperature and chlorophyll-a suitable for Atlantic salmon-blue mussel IMTA production (Kapetsky *et al.* 2013). However, several analyses have yet to be carried out to comprehensively evaluate the surface area available for this activity in Argentina. The only known report about an attempt to develop a GIS for marine aquaculture in the Province of Chubut, carried out in 2013 by personnel from the Coastal Development Institute of the National University of Patagonia San Juan Bosco, of which its degree of advance is unknown.

The availability of good-quality water is only one of the many requirements that must be evaluated to determine if a specific area is suitable for developing sustainable aquaculture. In this sense, a particular area may be suitable from the point of view of its climatic conditions and the physical and chemical parameters of the water. Nevertheless, it may not be available because there is no access to it or it is being used for another activity. Thus, some of the parameters that are used to define the availability of an area may be structural factors such as the existence of roads, prohibitive factors such as navigation exclusion zones, natural protected areas, and even cultural aspects related to social acceptability. This makes adequate territorial planning necessary to select suitable and available sites for the sustainable development of aquaculture. In this framework, the objective of ASTRAL was to kick off a GIS for aquaculture planning in both land-based and open-water systems on the southern coast of Argentina. This task does not intend to provide a fully developed GIS but rather to perform a first step that will serve as a basis for future developments.

7.1 Getting Data for GIS

A series of georeferenced spatial data are needed to develop a GIS, which must be organised in layers. Each layer contains information related to a set of reality elements with common characteristics and is classified into two types:

Vectorial layers: Store the location of geographic elements and associated attributes but cannot store topological relationships. These geographic elements can be represented as points, lines, or polygons (area).

Raster layers: Consists of regular-sized grids of pixels. Raster data is suitable for displaying information that varies continuously in the space.

Once the different layers with information are created, it is possible to integrate them into a unique geographic model with the sum of each layer's attributes (Figure 30). This geographical integration allows us to design spatial models with much information, facilitating decision-making. Furthermore, GIS is a "living" tool since it will enable existing data to be updated or new data to be incorporated as it is obtained, thus developing an increasingly robust tool.

Figure 30: Example of a GIS development integrating vectors and raster layers in a geographic model. © CADIC-CONICET.

For aquaculture GIS development in Tierra del Fuego, 21 layers were created (**Error! Reference source not found.**). All layers were gathered in one “geopackage” file (.gpkg) so they could be shared and edited in a simple way. GeoPackage is an open-source file format for geospatial information, which is very versatile and compatible with all GIS software. It allows you to store both different vector geometries (points, lines, and polygons) and raster layers in a single file (.gpkg) and store a large amount of information (up to 140 TB). GeoPackage was implemented for the first time in early 2014, but it has spread widely in recent years, facilitating the distribution and cooperation of geographic data.

Summary of layers created for aquaculture GIS development in Tierra del Fuego, Argentina, and some examples of the developed layers are shown in the Figure 31-Figure 34.

Table 3: Summary of layers created for aquaculture GIS development in Tierra del Fuego, Argentina.

Information	Layer type	Sources
Coastline (Argentina)	Vectorial (Line)	Digitised from images 1:10000, Google Earth Pro V services. 7.3.6.9345 (CNES/Airbus 2023. TerraMetrics 2023. Maxar Technologies 2023) and Bing Maps (Maxar 2023), through the QuickMapServices extension of QGIS V 3.22.8.
Coastline (Chile)	Vectorial (Line)	Map Library of the Library of the National Congress of Chile
Freshwater; water bodies (Argentina)	Vectorial (Line)	Digitised from images 1:10000, Google Earth Pro V services. 7.3.6.9345 (CNES/Airbus 2023. TerraMetrics 2023. Maxar Technologies 2023) and Bing Maps (Maxar 2023), through the QuickMapServices extension of QGIS V 3.22.8.
Freshwater; water bodies (Chile)	Vectorial (Line)	Map Library of the Library of the National Congress of Chile
Isobaths	Vectorial (Lineal)	Digitised from nautical charts of the Naval Hydrography Service (Área Marina Protegida Namuncurá – Banco Burdwood, H-5, H-50, H-60, H-80, H-416, H-477 A, H-477 B, H-477 C y H-5011).
Intertidal zone	Vectorial (Polygon)	Digitised from images 1:10000, Google Earth Pro V services. 7.3.6.9345 (CNES/Airbus 2023. TerraMetrics 2023. Maxar Technologies 2023) and Bing Maps (Maxar 2023), through the QuickMapServices extension of QGIS V 3.22.8.
Marshes	Vectorial (Polygon)	Digitised from Bianciotto (2006)
Kelp forests	Vectorial (Polygon)	Digitised from images 1:10000, Google Earth Pro V services. 7.3.6.9345 (CNES/Airbus 2023. TerraMetrics 2023. Maxar Technologies 2023) and Bing Maps (Maxar 2023), through the QuickMapServices extension of QGIS V 3.22.8.
Maritime traffic	Raster	MarineTraffic application at a scale of 1:100000.
Oil pipelines	Vectorial (Line)	Digitised from nautical charts of the Naval Hydrography Service (H-416 y H-477B).
Submarine cables and terminals	Vectorial (Line)	Digitised from nautical charts of the Naval Hydrography Service (H-416 y H-477B).

Table 3: Continued.

Areas prohibited for navigation	Vectorial (Polygon)	Digitised from nautical charts of the Naval Hydrography Service (Área Marina Protegida Namuncurá – Banco Burdwood, H-5, H-50, H-60, H-80, H-416, H-477 A, H-477 B, H-477 C y H-5011).
ARTF Classification zones	Vectorial (Polygon)	SENASA Resolution No. 433/10
South American sea lion <i>O. flavescens</i> colonies	Vectorial (Point)	Digitised from data available in Milano <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Seabird breeding colonies	Vectorial (Point)	Digitised from data available in Schiavini and Yorio (1995)
Road network	Vectorial (Line)	Digitised from images 1:10000, Google Earth Pro V services. 7.3.6.9345 (CNESA/Airbus 2023. TerraMetrics 2023. Maxar Technologies 2023) and Bing Maps (Maxar 2023), though the QuickMapServices extension of QGIS V 3.22.8.
Urban settlements	Vectorial (Polygon)	Tierra del Fuego Cadastre website of the Fuegian Collection Agency (AREF). http://catastro.aref.gob.ar/Web_TDF_catastro_ush/
Protected areas	Vectorial (Polygon)	National Geographic Institute (https://www.ign.gob.ar/NuestrasActividades/InformacionGeoespacial/CapasSIG)
Coastal tourism sites	Vectorial (Polygon)	Digitised from images 1:10000, Google Earth Pro V services. 7.3.6.9345 (CNESA/Airbus 2023. TerraMetrics 2023. Maxar Technologies 2023) and Bing Maps (Maxar 2023), through the QuickMapServices extension of QGIS V 3.22.8.
Maritime Traffic Surveillance and Control Posts	Vectorial (Point)	Personal communication
Argentine Naval Prefecture Posts	Vectorial (Point)	Personal communication

Figure 31: Layer with information on urban ejidos and public road network.

Figure 32: Layer with information about underwater pipelines.

Figure 33: Layer with information about intertidal zone, macroalga forests and marshes.

Figure 34: Layer with information about sea birds' reproductive colonies (red dots), sea lions' colonies (green dots) and protective areas (green areas).

7.2 Modelling GIS

The models were performed using a multi-criterion weighted overlay using QGIS 3.22.8 software (QGIS Development Team 2023). The vector and raster layers of interest are selected. In the case of vector layers, they will be transformed into raster layers using the rasterize function, assigning numerical values according to the relative importance of each attribute (See Table 4). Once assigning the importance values to each attribute, a raster calculator function was run to create two models: one for land-based aquaculture mainly focuses on the infrastructure available, and one for open-water aquaculture focuses mainly on environmental data.

At this point, it is necessary to emphasize that the values assigned to each attribute are entirely arbitrary and depend exclusively on the type of activity that is planned to be carried out. For example, if the objective is to design facilities for mussel farming in rafts, higher values will be assigned to depths of up to 25m. In contrast, if the objective is to install fish cages, the highest values will be assigned to depths greater than 25 meters.

Table 4: Values assigned to each attribute of each layer for the preparation of the multi-criteria weighted overlay models.

Layer	Atributte	Assigned Value
Depth	5 m	1
	10 m	2
	20 m	6
	50 m	5
	100 m	4
	200 m	3
	1000 m	2
	2000 m	1
Intertidal Area	Tidal influenced area	0
	Zone without tidal influence	1
Areas prohibited for navigation	Prohibited areas	0
	Permitted areas	1
Kelp forests	Areas with macroalgae	0
	40 m buffer zone	1
	Areas without macroalgae	2

Table 4: Continued.

Layer	Atributte	Assigned Value
Marine Traffic	Very intense	1
	Intense	2
	Intermediate	3
	Light	4
	Very light	5
	Without traffic	6
Road Network	Paved road	6
	Consolidated path	
	City road	5
	Camino consolidado	4
Proximity to cities	High influence (up to 5000 m)	5
	Average influence (from 5000 m to 10000 m)	3
	Low influence (from 10,000 m to 15,000 m)	1
GSM coverage	With coverage	1
	Without signal	0
Electricity	Mains electricity	4
	Generator electricity	2

7.2.1 Land-based Aquaculture Model

Four vector layers were used to model facilities available on land (GSM coverage, road network, proximity to cities, and electrical availability). For the road network, buffer areas of influence of 1000 m were created, and assessment levels were assigned depending on the type of road (paved road, city road or consolidated road). Values were assigned to the electrical availability layer depending on the kind of service, network, or generator. For the layer of proximity to cities, three buffer areas of high, medium, and low influence were created (at 5000, 10000 and 15000 m; respectively). The model was calculated as follows:

$$Model_{facilities} = Road\ Network + Proximity\ to\ cities + Electricity + GSM\ coverage$$

The facilities model resulted in a raster layer of 10,000 × 10,000 pixels, with an area of 123,802 km², with a spatial resolution of approximately 35 m and 16 rating levels of ease of access on land for the siting of aquaculture facilities (Figure 35). Finally, a layer indicating the seabird colonies (Schiavini and Yorio 1995) and the sea lion *Otaria flavescens* colonies (Milano *et al.* 2020) was added to the model, adding a buffer area of 1000 m in each of them, a vector layer indicating the protected areas and one showing the main tourist sites on the coast.

Figure 35: Example of a GIS model created for spatial planning of land-based aquaculture in Tierra del Fuego.

7.2.2 Open-Water Environmental Model

To create this model, information from four vector layers (depth, intertidal zone, areas prohibited for navigation and areas with the presence of macroalgae forests) and a raster layer (maritime traffic) were included (Figure 36). After rasterizing the vector layers and assigning relative importance values, the model was calculated as follows:

$$Model_{aptitude} = Areas\ with\ macroalgae \times Prohibited\ areas \times (Intertidal\ zone + Depth + Maritime\ traffic)$$

The model consisted of a raster layer of $10,000 \times 10,000$ pixels, covering an area of $123,802 \text{ km}^2$, with a spatial resolution of approximately 35 m and 32 levels of suitability assessment for the installation of longlines for cultivation of mussels in the sea. A vector layer was added to the model indicating the seabird colonies (Schiavini and Yorio 1995) and the sea lion colonies *Otaria flavescens* (Milano *et al.* 2020), adding a buffer area of 1000 m. A layer indicating the protected areas and one showing the main tourist sites on the coast were also included. Figure 37 shows a detail of this model developed for the Brown Bay area.

Figure 36: Example of a GIS model created for spatial planning of open-water aquaculture in Tierra del Fuego.

Figure 37: Example of a GIS model created for aquaculture spatial planning for blue mussel in Tierra del Fuego.

7.3 Gaps and Recommendation

Although the ASTRAL project focuses on integrated multi-trophic aquaculture, the development of GIS provides an approachable and informative tool with a much broader scope, even helpful beyond the aquaculture sector. In this sense, the development of this GIS allows planning the IMTA at a landscape scale, evaluating potentialities and interactions over the entire territory and not at the scale of each productive entrepreneurship. For example, the selection of sites suitable for cultivating a particular species could be conditioned by the suitability of a nearby site for producing another species, and both undertakings form an IMTA. In particular, if data from nearby sites suitable for finfish culture in cages that require deeper areas are added to the model developed for mussel farming (Figure 37), both undertakings could be managed separately but still constitute a large-scale IMTA at the landscape level.

Another usefulness of GIS models for IMTA development planning is the possibility of including information about the distribution of natural macroalgae forests. This would allow, for example, the selection of sites for mussel monoculture that have macroalgae (with or without commercial value) downstream of the longlines, thus achieving a de facto IMTA system.

Developing a GIS system must be a continuous task, with constant updates since the use and availability of spaces are dynamic. For this, it is recommended that this task be coordinated by government institutions and complemented with data from the scientific sector. In many countries, the development of GIS for aquaculture has emerged as a necessity to organise existing activities to avoid overlap and conflicts between them and new ones. On the contrary, Argentina can develop this tool to plan the expansion of aquaculture from the beginning, which is a unique opportunity that only some countries have had. Thus, creating an adequate GIS makes it possible to continuously incorporate new data as new regulations appear (e.g. new protected areas).

There are several areas for improvement in important information for aquaculture GIS development aimed at organising the activity. For example, aquaculture facility installations could affect coastal artisanal fishing activities; nevertheless, there is no officially published data on the distribution of these fisheries. On the other hand, in Tierra del Fuego, a coastal use regulation is being discussed through several projects (e.g. “Protected Coasts – Zoning Code for the Sustainable Use of the Provincial Coast Space”; 2020), which must consider all the potential limitations imposed for productive activity and include them in a GIS.

Regarding access and available services, it must be considered that according to the 2022 census, TDF is a province with only 0.19 inhabitants per km² grouped in 3 cities, which means that most of its territory is rural. Under these conditions, having data on access and availability of services is crucial to projecting the development of aquaculture activities and selecting optimal sites from the point of view of the costs associated with the transfer and the availability of services and inputs.

8 Species Selection for IMTA in Argentina

The choice of suitable species for aquaculture should be an integration between biological knowledge and economic value, but also external factors such as specific regulations, availability of suppliers (feed, seeds, equipment, etc.), and social acceptability of the production practices (i.e., for a particular species, the social acceptability could be different if an open system or a RAS is used). Thus, before selecting a species for culture or a (business) project, it is essential to consider the species' biological requirements, economics, and market potential. The following are some of the general factors that should be considered when selecting a species for a successful aquaculture venture from the beginning:

- Knowledge of biology, ecology, and life history.
- Knowledge of reproduction manipulation methods.
- Possibility of captive breeding and closing the life cycle under controlled farming conditions.
- Ability to culture at high densities in reared facilities.
- Ability to consume and efficiently grow on formulated diets.
- Ability to perform the complete life cycle in a controlled environment.
- Attainability of market size within the economically feasible period.
- Low vulnerability to pathogens.

The ideal aquaculture species must fulfill all the above characteristics and others. However, only some, if any, species are ideal. Under this frame, four consecutive steps were carried out to choose native species to the Beagle Channel (Southwest Atlantic Ocean) that could make up an IMTA system in Argentina:

Personal expertise: Meetings and discussion sessions with Argentinean experts (both scientific researchers and producers) on which species from the Beagle Channel have the potential (even if it's minimal) to be used in IMTA and monoculture were held. A first comprehensive list was compiled from these meetings, including all the species that, according to previous experiences and personal knowledge, have or may have the potential for aquaculture production (Table 5). In this case, no particular criteria were followed, just the knowledge about each species' biology, physiology, reared experiences and personal perceptions, trying to include as many species as possible.

Aquaculture know-how: Analysis of the aquaculture know-how of these species at provincial, national, and international levels was discussed. A broad review of more than 600 scientific papers, technical reports, and projects with biological and technical data (i.e., facility design, feed composition, growth curve, survival estimation, reproductive management, etc.) was done. A summary of the overall available literature is included in Annex I of this document.

Market value: To determine the economic potential of these species, a market study focused on seafood restaurants was carried out in Ushuaia City.

Selected species: The species were chosen according to their aquaculture know-how and the local market previously assigned. The species were grouped into four groups according to their potential function in an IMTA system. Group 1: Fed Aquaculture; Group 2: Organic Extractive Aquaculture (sedimented POM feeders); Group 3: Organic Extractive Aquaculture (detritivores POM feeders); Group 4: Inorganic Extractive Aquaculture (DIN feeders).

Table 5: List of native species analysed for IMTA production.

Latin name	Common name	
	English	Spanish
Fish		
<i>Eleginops maclovinus</i>	Patagonian blenny	Róbalo
<i>Galaxias maculatus</i>	Whitebait	Puyen, Puye
<i>Genypterus blacodes</i>	Ling	Abadejo
<i>Odontesthes nigricans</i>	Silverside	Pejerrey
<i>Odontesthes smitti</i>	Silverside	Pejerrey manila o corno
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Rainbow trout	Trucha arcoíris
<i>Sprattus fuegensis</i>	Patagonian sprat	Sardina fueguina
Crustacean		
<i>Lithodes santolla</i>	Southern king crab	Centolla
<i>Munida gregaria</i>	Squat lobster	Langostilla
<i>Paralomis granulosa</i>	Southern false king crab	Centollón
Mollusc		
<i>Aulacomya atra</i>	Ribbed mussel	Cholga
<i>Chlamys patagonica</i>	Patagonian clam	Ostión patagónico
<i>Enteroctopus megalocyathus</i>	Patagonian red octopus	Pulpo rojo
<i>Mulinia edulis</i>	Clam	Almeja fina chilena
<i>Mytilus chilensis</i>	Blue mussel	Mejillón
<i>Octopus tehuelchus</i>	Patagonian octopus	Pulpo Tehuelche
<i>Robsonella fontaniana</i>	Octopus	Pulpo
<i>Venus antiqua</i>	Clam	Almeja rayada
<i>Zygochlamys patagonica</i>	Patagonian scallop	Vieira Patagónica
Others		
<i>Loxechinus albus</i>	Red sea urchin	Erizo rojo
<i>Arbacia dufresnii</i>	Green sea urchin	Erizo verde
<i>Hemioedema spectabilis</i>	Sea cucumber	Pepino de mar
Phylum Polycheta	Polychaeta	Poliqueto
Algae and Halophytes		
<i>Macrocystis pyrifera</i>	Giant kelp	Cachiyuyo
<i>Porphyra sp.</i>	Seaweed	Alga roja
<i>Sarcocornia magellanica</i>	Glasswort	Salicornia
<i>Spartina sp.</i>	Spartina	Spartina
<i>Ulva sp.</i>	Sea lettuce	Lechuga de mar

8.1 Ranking of Species by Know-How

Table 6; 7; 8 and 9 show the ranking of the species developed according to the level of knowledge on the aquaculture techniques at international, national and province levels. For each spatial scale, a qualitative value was assigned as “High”, “Medium”, “Low”, and “Zero”, and the total score for each species is the sum of the three scores for each level according to the following values: High=3; Medium=2; Low=1; Zero=0.

Table 6: Ranking of native species by know-how at international, national and province levels. Group 1: Fed aquaculture. Total score red = 0; yellow = 1-3; orange = 4-6; green = 7-9.

Subgroup	Species	Know-how			
		International	National	Province	Total Score
Fish	Whitebait (<i>Galaxias maculatus</i>)	High	Zero	Low	4
Fish	Patagonian blenny (<i>Eleginops maclovinus</i>)	Medium	Zero	Low	3
Mollusc	Patagonian red octopus (<i>Enteroctopus megalocyathus</i>)	Low	Low	Zero	2
Fish	Silverside (<i>Odontesthes nigricans</i>)	Zero	Low	Zero	1
Fish	Silverside (<i>Odontesthes smitti</i>)	Zero	Low	Zero	1
Fish	Ling (<i>Genypterus blacodes</i>)	Low	Zero	Zero	1
Fish	Patagonian sprat (<i>Sprattus fuegensis</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0
Crustacean	Southern king crab adult (<i>Lithodes santolla</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0
Crustacean	Southern false king crab adult (<i>Paralomis granulosa</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0

Table 7: Ranking of local species by know-how. Group 2 - Organic Extractive Aquaculture (sedimented POM feeders). Total score red = 0; yellow = 1-3; orange = 4-6; green = 7-9.

Subgroup	Species	Know-how			
		International	National	Province	Total Score
Echinoderm	Green sea urchin (<i>Arbacia dufresnii</i>)	Medium	High	Zero	5
Echinoderm	Red sea urchin (<i>Loxechinus albus</i>)	High	Zero	Low	4
Crustacean	Southern king crab juvenile (<i>Lithodes santolla</i>)	Low	Low	Low	3
Mollusc	Octopus (<i>Robsonella fontaniana</i>)	Low	Low	Zero	2
Mollusc	Snail (<i>Adelomelon ancilla</i>)	Zero	Low	Zero	1
Mollusc	Key-hole limpet (<i>Fissurella sp.</i>)	Low	Zero	Zero	1
Mollusc	Snail (<i>Odontocymbiola magellanica</i>)	Zero	Low	Zero	1
Crustacean	Southern king crab adult (<i>Lithodes santolla</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0
Crustacean	Southern false king crab juvenile (<i>Paralomis granulosa</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0
Crustacean	Southern false king crab adult (<i>P. granulosa</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0
Crustacean	Squat lobster (<i>Munida gregaria</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0
Mollusc	Limpet (<i>Nacella magellanica</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0
Holothuria	Sea cucumber (<i>Hemioedema spectabilis</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0

Table 8: Ranking of local species by know-how. Group 3 - Organic Extractive Aquaculture (suspended POM feeders). Total score red = 0; yellow = 1-3; orange = 4-6; green = 7-9.

Subgroup	Species	Know-how			
		International	National	Province	Total Score
Mollusc	Blue mussel (<i>Mytilus chilensis</i>)	High	High	High	9
Mollusc	Ribbed mussel (<i>Aulacomya ater</i>)	High	Low	Low	5
Mollusc	Clam (<i>Mulinia edulis</i>)	Medium	Zero	Zero	2
Mollusc	Clam (<i>Ameghinomya antiqua</i>)	Low	Zero	Zero	1
Mollusc	Patagonian scallop (<i>Zygochlamys patagonica</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0
Mollusc	Patagonian clam (<i>Chlamys patagonica</i>)	Zero	Zero	Zero	0

Table 9: Ranking of species by know-how. Group 4 - Organic Extractive Aquaculture (DIN feeders). Total score red = 0; yellow = 1-3; orange = 4-6; green = 7-9.

Subgroup	Species	Know-how			
		International	National	Province	Total Score
Halophyte	Glasswort (<i>Sarcocornia spp.</i>)	Low	High	High	7
Algae	Sea lettuce (<i>Ulva spp.</i>)	High	Low	Zero	4
Alga	Giant Kelp (<i>Macrocystis pyrifera</i>)	Medium	Low	Zero	3
Alga	Purple laver (<i>Porphyra sp.</i>)	Medium	Low	Zero	3
Halophyte	Spartina (<i>Spartina sp.</i>)	Low	Zero	Zero	1

8.2 Ranking of Species by Market Value

To evaluate the current and potential local market for the native species to the Beagle Channel, a series of interviews were conducted with seafood restaurants in the city of Ushuaia in 2022. Face-to-face interviews with owners or managers of 45 seafood restaurants were held to learn about supply, demand, and personal interest and knowledge of native species. The following five specific questions were asked:

- What species and how often do they offer them?
- What importance do they assign to each species in their restaurant?
- Do they cover the demand?
- Would they be interested in including any of these species more frequently?
- Where do they get the product?

There was a good reception from the restaurant owners attending the survey, and it was possible to explain in detail the main objectives of ASTRAL and the IMTA concept. One of the most exciting aspects detected is that all the seafood restaurants interviewed offer native species, and the most offered and important were the southern king crab, blue mussel, and Patagonian blenny (Figure 38-Figure 40). On the other hand, the interviewees stated an unsatisfied demand for all species.

Figure 38: Percentage of restaurants offering each species and frequency with which they offer them.

Figure 39: Degree of priority of each species for restaurants.

Figure 40: Species by percentage of meeting the demand.

Respondents face difficulties when purchasing species for their restaurants. The main problems detected are an insufficient and unpredictable species supply, so restaurants cannot have guaranteed supplies, which is crucial for their business. Besides, there is a lack of visibility of some native species in the local market.

They mentioned that the prices of local suppliers are sometimes higher than in continental Argentina, so they are forced to buy species from other regions or countries.

Some restaurant owners are fishers and fish the species for their own. They highlighted some difficulties with fishing, like lack of infrastructure in the port of Almanza, lack of knowledge, weather conditions, regulations, etc.

A quantitative score was assigned for each species according to the proportion of restaurants offering each species and the proportion of restaurants that don't cover the demand of each species: $\text{Market Score} = \text{Offer (\%)} * \text{Uncovered Demand (\%)}$. The final score for each species was relativised to the maximum score obtained. Figure 41 shows the offer and cover demand of 20 marine species, 17 native and 3 exotics to the Beagle Channel and Table 10-Table 13 show the market ranking assigned to each species. The Southern king crab (*L. Santolla*) scored higher, followed by the blue mussel (*Mytilus spp.*), both native to the Beagle Channel. The next species with the highest market value were the exotic salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch* and *O. tshawytscha*) and rainbow trout (*O. mykiss*) that have invaded the Beagle Channel. At this point, it is important to note that most of the surveyed people differentiated the value of wild salmon captured in the Beagle Channel from those from farms, assigning greater importance to the former. Despite the importance of salmonids in the local market, they were not considered to analyse the potential for the development of IMTA because only native species were evaluated in this report.

Figure 41: % of restaurants offering each species (X-axis) and degree of demand coverage satisfaction (Y-axis) in seafood restaurants of Ushuaia City. Data obtained from interviews conducted with seafood restaurants in Ushuaia, 2023.

Table 10: Ranking of local species by market. Group 1 - Fed Aquaculture. Total score red = 0-0.1; yellow = >0.1-0.25; orange = >0.25-0.5; green = >0.5-1.0.

Subgroup	Species	Score
Crustacean	Southern king crab (<i>Lithodes santolla</i>)	1.000
Fish	Salmon (<i>Oncorhynchus spp.</i>)	0.778
Fish	Trout (<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>)	0.687
Crustacean	Southern false king crab (<i>Paralomis granulosa</i>)	0.589
Fish	Patagonian blenny (<i>Eleginops maclovinus</i>)	0.492
Fish	Silverside (<i>Odontesthes spp.</i>)	0.393
Fish	Ling (<i>Genypterus blacodes</i>)	0.383
Mollusc	Octopus (<i>Non-specified spp.</i>)	0.245
Fish	Sprat (<i>Sprattus fuegensis</i>)	0.007
Fish	Whitebait (<i>Galaxias maculatus</i>)	0.000

Table 11: Ranking of local species by market. Group 2 - Organic Extractive Aquaculture (sedimented POM feeders). Total score yellow = >0.1-0.25.

Subgroup	Species	Score
Echinoderm	Sea urchin (<i>Non-specified spp.</i>)	0.209
Mollusc	Snail (<i>Non-specified spp.</i>)	0.059

Table 12: Ranking of local species by market. Group 3 - Organic Extractive Aquaculture (suspended POM feeders). Total score red = 0-0.1; yellow = >0.1-0.25; green = >0.5-1.0.

Subgroup	Species	Score
Mollusc	Blue mussel (<i>Mytilus spp.</i>)	0.834
Mollusc	Scallop (<i>Non-specified spp.</i>)	0.226
Mollusc	Clam (<i>Non-specified spp.</i>)	0.207
Mollusc	Ribbed mussel (<i>Aulacomya ater</i>)	0.000
Mollusc	Limpet (<i>Non-specified spp.</i>)	0.000
Mollusc	Razor shell (<i>Non-specified spp.</i>)	0.000

Table 13: Ranking of local species by market. Organic Extractive Aquaculture (DIN feeders). Total score red = 0-0.1; yellow = >0.1-0.25. *For sarcocornia, a specific interview was one, see section 6.1 Sarcocornia.

Subgroup	Species	Score
Algae	Algae (Non specified spp.)	0.130
Halophyte*	Sarcocornia (<i>Sarcocornia magellanica</i>)	0.006

8.3 Selected Species and Description

The selected species were described in terms of their distribution, biology, state of fisheries, market value and aquaculture experiences. The description of the species was carried out, focusing almost exclusively on data obtained from Tierra del Fuego, the Austral Coast of Argentina and southern Chile.

A description about the state of knowledge of the non-selected species and the available literature are included in Annex II of this document.

8.3.1 Whitebait (*Galaxias maculatus*)

Distribution

Whitebait, locally known as small puyen, is one of the world’s most widespread freshwater fish found in Argentina, Chile, Australia, New Zealand, and Tasmania (Waters and Burrige 1999) (Figure 42). Its distribution range in Argentina comprises the Patagonian Region, from 32°S to the Beagle Channel at 55°S as its southernmost sites (McDowall 1971).

Figure 42: Worldwide distribution of *G. maculatus*. Taken from Berra et al. (1996).

Biology

This species develops both landlocked and diadromous populations in Tierra del Fuego (Rojo *et al.* 2020). The diadromous phenotype spawns in estuary environments (Figure 43), in salinity <20, and the juveniles return to freshwater after 5-6 months (Hicks *et al.* 2010). McDowall *et al.* (1994) stated that the populations of New Zealand are semelparous, but studies made in Tierra del Fuego suggested the presence of repetitive spawning, with a protracted spawning period from October to February (Boy *et al.* 2007; 2009a). Experimental trials in captivity showed that *G. maculatus* could spawn 4-11 times for 10-60 days (Valdebenito and Vega 2003; Boy *et al.* 2009a). Most individuals become sexually mature in their first year of life, although some reach maturity at 2 or 3 years (Rojo *et al.* 2018).

The maximum size of this species in the Beagle Channel has been estimated at 123.8 mm (Rojo *et al.* 2018), with extraordinary records of 155 mm in length in the estuary of the Olivia River (Chalde comm. pers.).

Figure 43: Typical life cycle of the whitebait in the Beagle Channel. © CADIC-CONICET.

Fisheries and Wild Stocks

The artisanal fishery of whitebait was a significant activity in Chile in the '60s-70s, whose populations collapsed due to overexploitation (Mardones *et al.* 2008; Vega *et al.* 2013). Current fishing catches

are at most 2 tons/year (5,000,000 specimens), which is unsatisfactory for domestic supply (SERNAPESCA 2020). In New Zealand, the whitebait fishery is still an important activity, where the impact generated on the wild stock has led to stronger regulations⁷. In Argentina, there is no report about fisheries on any Galaxiid species.

Aquaculture State

Chile and New Zealand have had several aquaculture programs to develop whitebait farms (see Mitchell 1989; McDowall 1995; Vega 1999; Barile *et al.* 2003a; Mardones *et al.* 2008; Vega *et al.* 2013), and the Manāki Company is already producing whitebait at commercial scale in New Zealand (<https://whitebait.co.nz/>). This species supports high manipulation and low water quality in captivity, facilitating the productive cycle (Mitchell 1989). So far, only land-based systems (open and RAS) have been used. The complete life cycle in captivity has been achieved in 390 days (Barile *et al.* 2003). However, capture-based aquaculture is still carried out since production still depends on eggs obtained by extracting wild broodstock for breeding (Mardones *et al.* 2008). The growth cycle may begin with the purchase/capture of crystalline fry, which grows until it reaches sexual maturity (Figure 44). The gametes are obtained by stripping and incubated for 25-30 days in an automatic humidity incubation system (SAIH for Spanish) (Mardones *et al.* 2008). In this system, a monolayer of eggs is disposed of in trays with a damp cloth (100% humidity) at 6.4 eggs / mm² and incubated on dark conditions or 12L-12D (Barile 2003; Mardones *et al.* 2008; O'Malley 2023). The larvae take around 140 days to reach the juvenile stage, at which time a part of the stock can be harvested, and the rest continue growing until reaching sexual maturity and used for the next productive cycle. This first productive cycle, starting from the capture of wild fry to obtaining eggs, takes approximately 480 days. In comparison, a productive cycle with an already established breeding stock takes 150 - 180 days from the fertilisation of the eggs to the harvest of juveniles (Dantagnan *et al.* 2002; Barile *et al.* 2003; Barile 2003; Vega *et al.* 2013).

The eggs are incubated in damp cloth (100% humidity) at dark conditions until they achieve 280 - 320 ATUs (30 days at 10°C) and then passed to tanks where the larvae hatched at 4-6 mm in length (Mitchell 1989) and maintained at an initial density of 38 larvae/L (Dantagnan *et al.* 2002; Barile 2003). The juveniles are usually reared in tanks of 2 m³ and the density could be settled at 0.5 - 1 kg/m³ in semi-intensive culture or 8-11 kg/m³ in intensive culture (Valdebenito and Vega 2003;

⁷ New Zealand Whitebait Fishing Regulations 2021 are available at <https://www.legislation.govt.nz/regulation/public/2021/0180/latest/LMS513906.html?src=qs>

Mardones *et al.* 2008; Encina Montoya *et al.* 2011). The broodstock is maintained in circular tanks of 8 m³ and 3 m in diameter (Mardones *et al.* 2008).

Figure 44: Productive cycle of whitebait. © CADIC-CONICET.

Market

Whitebait is one of five Galaxiid species commercialised in New Zealand (McDowall 1995) and is highly valued internationally since it is considered a commercial simile of eel alevin (Mardones *et al.* 1999; 2008). The most common commercialised product is the whole frozen crystalline larvae of 0.3-0.5 g with a length of 4-6 mm (Dantagnan *et al.* 2002; Vega *et al.* 2013). It is the costliest fish on the market in New Zealand, reaching values up to U\$S 154/kg of frozen entire fish. Chile also has a high market demand, commercialised at U\$S 56/kg, with a range price of about U\$S25-100/kg.

Summary of Main Characteristics

Table 14-Table 17 show biological parameters relevant to aquaculture, water quality needs, parameters related to the performance of the whitebait in captivity and feeding tests in aquaculture.

Table 14: Main biological parameters of whitebait relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristic	Description	References
Environment type	Two life strategies: amphidromous, where its larval stage develops in the sea; and landlocked, where its entire life cycle develops in lakes, lagoons, or rivers.	Alò <i>et al.</i> 2019
Depth	Shallow waters.	Rojo <i>et al.</i> 2020
Max. length males	123.8 mm.	Chapman <i>et al.</i> 2006; Rojo <i>et al.</i> 2018
Max. length females	123.8 mm.	Chapman <i>et al.</i> 2006; Rojo <i>et al.</i> 2018
Max. weight males	5 g.	Boy <i>et al.</i> 2007
Max. weight females	7 - 9 g.	Boy <i>et al.</i> 2007
Max. age males	3+ years.	Rojo <i>et al.</i> 2018
Max. age females	3+ years.	Rojo <i>et al.</i> 2018
Length – Weight relationship males	$\log BM = 3.67 \log TL - 6.6.$	Boy <i>et al.</i> 2007
Length – Weight relationship females	$\log BM = 3.72 \log TL - 6.7.$	Boy <i>et al.</i> 2007
Growth curve	$L_t = L_{\infty}(1 - e^{-k(t-t_0)})$ $L_{\infty} = 123.8 \text{ mm}$, $k = 0.33 \text{ year}^{-1}$ and $t_0 = -1.01 \text{ years}.$	Rojo <i>et al.</i> 2018
Reproduction type	Gonochoric, repetitive spawning, 4-11 spawning pulses for 10-60 days.	Valdebenito and Vega 2003; Boy <i>et al.</i> 2009 ^a
Spawning season	October–February.	Boy <i>et al.</i> 2007
Maturation age males	1+.	Rojo <i>et al.</i> 2018
Maturation age females	1+, some at 0+.	Vega <i>et al.</i> 2013; Rojo <i>et al.</i> 2018
Maturation length males	38 mm.	Barbee <i>et al.</i> 2011; Vega <i>et al.</i> 2023
Maturation length females	70 – 96 mm.	Boy <i>et al.</i> 2007
Type of eggs	Adhesives.	Vega <i>et al.</i> 2013
Egg size	700 μm – 1200 μm .	Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 1995; Valdebenito <i>et al.</i> 1996; Allibone 2003; Valdebenito and Vega 2003; Boy <i>et al.</i> 2009 ^a
Fecundity	1,175 \pm 422 oocytes per ovary.	Boy <i>et al.</i> 2009a
Newly larvae weight	Data not available or not determined.	
Newly larvae length	4-6 mm.	Mitchell 1989; Barile 2003; Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 1995; Valdebenito 1996; Montoya 2012; Jellyman and Harding 2014
Juvenile feeding habits	Marine zooplankton (near the coast) or freshwater, especially cladocerans, cyclopoid copepods, larvae and pupae of chironomids and surface insects.	Vega <i>et al.</i> 2013a
Adults feeding habits	Bentophagus, feeding mainly on arthropods (insects, crustaceans), fish eggs and larvae.	Vega <i>et al.</i> 2013a

Table 15: Main water quality conditions need for whitebait farm.

Characteristic	Description	References
Salinity	0 - 48 mg/L.	Chessman and Williams 1975; Velásquez 1993; Bórquez and Dantagnan 1999; Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2006; Urbina 2013; Delgado <i>et al.</i> 2023
Temperature	10 - 24.5°C.	Eldon 1969; Mitchell 1989; Richardson <i>et al.</i> 1994; Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 1995; Bórquez and Dantagnan 1999; Ferriz <i>et al.</i> 2001; Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2006; Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2010; Delgado <i>et al.</i> 2023; Jellyman and Harding 2014; O'Malley 2023
Photoperiod	12L:12D – 14L:10D.	Richardson <i>et al.</i> 1994; West <i>et al.</i> 1997; Encina <i>et al.</i> 2010; Urbina 2013; Jellyman and Harding 2014; Urbina and Glover 2015; Delgado <i>et al.</i> 2023
pH	6.8 - 9.3 juveniles. 8.5 - 10 adults.	West <i>et al.</i> 1997; Ferriz <i>et al.</i> 2001; Urbina 2013; Urbina and Glover 2015; Barile <i>et al.</i> 2016; Delgado <i>et al.</i> 2023;
Ammonium	0.01 mg/L.	Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2006
Nitrite	0.1 mg/L.	Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2006
O ₂	>5 mg/L.	Encina Montoya <i>et al.</i> 1999; 2011; Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2006

Table 16: Main parameters related to the performance of the whitebait in captivity.

Characteristic	Description	References
Fertilization rate	90%.	Valdebenito and Vega 2003
Hatching rate	91 - 88 %.	Barile <i>et al.</i> 2013a
Larvae survival	10 dph: 86 - 88%. 30 dph: 60-70%.	Valdebenito and Vega 2003; Barile <i>et al.</i> 2013 ^a
Juvenile survival	95-98 % monthly.	Valdebenito and Vega 2003
Adult survival	< 2 years: 99-97% monthly.	Valdebenito and Vega 2003
Post spawn survival	2 years: 90% monthly. 3 years: 30% monthly.	Valdebenito and Vega 2003
SGR	0.1 - 3.7 %/day, depending on protein levels.	Vega 2013
FCR	0.5-4 depending on protein levels.	Vega 2013
Volumetric eggs	12.500 eggs = 10 ml.	Valdebenito and Vega 2003
Spermatic density	32.4 - 67.4 sp/ml.	Valdebenito and Vega 2003
Motility	10 - 15 seconds at 5 - 10 °C.	Valdebenito and Vega 2003
Incubation temperature	9 - 19.7°C.	Barile 2003; Bórquez <i>et al.</i> 2007; Barile <i>et al.</i> 2013; Montoya <i>et al.</i> 2012; O'Malley 2023
Incubation salinity	0 - 20.	Velásquez 1993; Hicks <i>et al.</i> 2010; Barile 2003; Barile <i>et al.</i> 2013b
Thermal Units	280 - 320 (10°C).	Barile <i>et al.</i> 2013b
Hatching	31 days at 4.4°C - 10 days at 17°C.	Benzie 1968; Barile 2003

Table 17: Summary of whitebait feeding tests in aquaculture.

Characteristic	Description	References
Time until first exogenous feeding	1-5 days.	Mitchell 1989; Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2002
Larvae	0-20 days: 100 % Rotifers. 21-30 days: 90% Rotifers + 10% artemia nauplii. 31-40 days: 75% Rotifers + 25% artemia nauplii. 40 - 70 days: Artemia nauplii + Formulated feed.	Mitchell 1989; Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2002; Mardones and de Los Ríos 2012; Vega <i>et al.</i> 2013
Juveniles	1 st week: Beef liver. 2 nd week: 75% liver and 25% oil-free salmonid starter 3 rd week: 50% liver and 50% starter. 4 th week: 25% liver and 75% starter. 5 th week 100% of starter.	Mardones <i>et al.</i> 2008
Ongrowing	0.3 - 0.5 g: Starter 00. 0.5 - 1 g: Starter. 1 - 1.5 g: Alevins crumble 1. 1.5 - 2 g: Alevins crumble 2.	Mardones <i>et al.</i> 2008
Ongrowing feeding ratio	Salmon starter, Drosophila larvae or pupae. 45-47% protein, 15-16% lipids, <2.5% fibre, 15% humidity, + Vita A, C, D, E. 2% body weight daily in 10 daily rations by automatic feeders. 2 daily rations.	Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2002; Valdebenito and Vega 2003; Mardones <i>et al.</i> 2008; Vega <i>et al.</i> 2013
Cannibalism	Yes.	Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2002; Allibone 2003
Size separation	60 dph.	Dantagnan <i>et al.</i> 2002

Gaps and Recommendations

Biological studies

There is sufficient literature that describes the life history of wild whitebait populations in detail. In particular, the life cycle has been described for several populations of Tierra del Fuego. However, no work has yet been carried out to understand the relationships between environmental factors, such as photoperiod and temperature, which allow planning a manipulation of reproductive quality in captivity.

To achieve the complete cycle in captivity, it is necessary to have biotechnological tools to manage reproduction. In this sense, conducting research programs to understand the endocrine mechanisms that regulate whitebait reproduction to manipulate and maximize seed production in captivity is crucial.

Aquaculture

The production scale of whitebait should be producing low biomass but a product of high commercial value. To achieve the first steps developing the production, it is recommended to supply restaurants near aquaculture facilities that work with international tourism.

Since one of the main bottlenecks of whitebait aquaculture is obtaining seeds, the best strategy could be collecting wild individuals, either as broodstock whose eggs will hatch and develop in culture or as early stages for growth under controlled conditions. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations has recognised this production strategy as capture-based aquaculture (FAO 2008). Capture-based aquaculture has certain advantages and disadvantages compared to aquaculture, which controls the complete cycle of the cultured species. One of the main advantages is that the need to develop hatcheries or breeding programs is avoided, lowering costs. However, the need for domestication potential for captured species is a significant disadvantage as it is impossible to carry out genetic selection and improvement programs.

To use this production strategy, it is essential to know the state of conservation of the natural populations to avoid any alteration. On the other hand, it is recommended that this type of approach be used only during the initial stage of production development which allows all the necessary advances to be made to achieve a stable breeding stock.

Although data about the quality of water used to maintain whitebait in captivity has been reported, few experimental works have evaluated the optimal parameters. It is recommended especially to develop studies that determine levels of ammonium and nitrites that this species can tolerate.

Market opportunities

Whitebait is not a well-known product in Argentina's gastronomic field. However, the fact that it is a product like the European eel (*Anguilla anguilla*) consumed in Europe and Asia (see Figure 45) means that whitebait has great gastronomic potential and could be focused on the consumption of international tourists.

Figure 45: Photographs showing the similarities between European eel (Left, taken from www.casas.co.uk/blog/) and whitebait (right). Taken from www.countrygourmettraveler.blogspot.com/.

Traceability and consumer confidence

One of its current limitations in being able to popularise it is that it is not included in the Argentine food code, which makes its traceability difficult and could have little confidence on the part of consumers.

The whitebait is a native species whose populations are threatened by the impact of the invasion of salmonids in Argentina and Chile. For this reason, it is recommended that this species be commercialised only through a seal that certifies that the products come from aquaculture and not from wild populations.

8.3.2 Glasswort (*Sarcocornia magellanica*)

Distribution

Sarcocornia is a genus of halophytic edible succulent plants that belongs to the Amaranthaceae family (Steffen *et al.* 2015). This genus includes 28 species commonly named glasswort, samphire, or just sarcocornia. *Sarcocornia* is distributed worldwide in saline environments, usually salt marshes habitats with low precipitations. *S. magellanica* is an endemic species to southern Argentina and Chile, growing in salt marshes associated with the Atlantic tides (Alonso and Crespo 2008). In Tierra del Fuego, *S. magellanica* occupies the northeastern area (see Figure 46), where marshes form a vegetation gradient between the marine coast and the steppe and in coastal lagoons located in old tidal flats (Bianciotto 2004).

Figure 46: Distribution of marshes and coastal lagoons (dark green areas) with natural populations of glasswort in Tierra del Fuego. Data source: Bianciotto 2014. © CADIC_CONICET

Biology

There are three native species of *Sarcocornia* in Argentina: *S. ambigua*, *S. neei* and *S. Magellanica* (Cantero *et al.* 2016). The *Sarcocornia* genus is often confused with *Salicornia*, but they are two different genera with high morphological similarity (Scott 1977). One of the most important differences to be considered from a productive point of view is that while the *Salicornia* genus includes only annual species, *Sarcocornia* is composed of perennials, allowing partial harvests for several years (Bianciotto 2016). It has a tolerance to concentrations of up to 40 g/L of salinity, pH values between 7 to 8 and soil temperature ranges ranging from 11 to 18°C (Arce *et al.* 2016; Bianciotto *et al.* 2016; Bianciotto *et al.* 2020).

S. magellanica presents mat-forming growth and decumbent sub-shrubs with a clonal habit that involves above-ground (5 – 10 cm high) creeping stems rooting at nodes (Alonso and Crespo 2008). The natural cycle of *S. magellanica* begins with the appearance of buds at the end of October (Austral spring), growing until the flowering stage in January and reaching fruiting in March and the senescence at the end of April. It goes dormant in mid-June, and after the winter, the halophytes resprout in spring (Bianciotto 2020; Figure 47). It takes four years to generate seeds and depending on climatic conditions it can generate seeds continuously every 5-7 years. (Bianciotto *et al.* 2004).

Figure 47: Typical life cycle of *S. magellanica* in natural marshes of Tierra del Fuego. © CADIC-CONICET.

Exploitation and Natural Stock

In Patagonia (Chile and Argentina), *Sarcocornia neei* and *S. magellanica* have been historically harvested from natural banks near the seashore. The harvest of wild *Sarcocornia* is carried out in summer when the shoots are tender and are more palatable to consume fresh. Some reports have reported that locals let their cattle, mainly sheep, graze on the *sarcocornia* natural pastures (Bianciotto *et al.* 2016). These informal practices are evidence of both the potential of these halophytes as emerging harvests and the need to develop productive practices for their use while avoiding the ecological depletion of the marshes. No official or published information on current natural status was found.

Aquaculture and Production State

The salt tolerance and the high nutritional value for humans make the *Sarcocornia spp.* a halophyte with the potential to be integrated into aquaculture systems with brackish or marine species. This species is also promising to develop aquaculture in the context of climate change and soil and water salinisation, added to the fact that this crop does not require the use of freshwater (Ventura *et al.* 2011; Ventura and Sagi 2013; Bianciotto *et al.* 2021).

Sarcocornia ambigua and *S. neei* have been used in aquaculture for bioremediation of marine fisheries wastewaters (Beyer *et al.* 2021), in aquaponic systems (Spradlin and Saha 2022), and for production diversification in integrated biofloc systems (Pinheiro *et al.* 2020).

In Tierra del Fuego, sarcocornia cultivation experiences have been carried out in three different systems: Soil crops without wind protection, soil crops in tunnels and greenhouse crops.

Soil crops without wind protection: *S. magellanica* have been cultivated in estuarine environments of the Fuegian steppe, and the form of culture implanted in coastal depressions of the Beagle Channel and irrigated with seawater (Figure 48; Bianciotto 2004).

Soil crops in tunnels: Bianciotto *et al.* (2015) have developed several trials evaluating the productive performance of sarcocornia cultivated in wind protection tunnels in Tierra del Fuego (Figure 49). Through the implementation of cultivation tunnels for protection against the wind and seawater pumping from the Beagle Channel, yields of 4.2 – 4.5 kg/m² were obtained (Table 18). These yields are like those obtained in natural environments with daily tidal irrigation, allowing cultivation in any area with seawater source. Furthermore, using tunnels promotes the regrowth of the sarcocornia, allowing the production of cuttings and stolons.

Crops in greenhouse: One of the most significant advances in achieving profitable cultivation of sarcocornia is the ability to carry out partial harvests since it has been verified that the halophytes can resprout when it grows in a greenhouse (Bianciotto *et al.* 2004). It is estimated that in greenhouse crops, staggered cuts could be made every 20 days, obtaining between 4 and 6 harvest cycles during the growing season, and obtaining 1,250 g/m² of green shoots (Bianciotto *et al.* 2004).

Figure 48: Panoramic view of a historical test of *Sarcocornia* growth in the intertidal zone of the Beagle Channel. Taken from Bianciotto (2004).

Figure 49: *Sarcocornia* culture assays. Left: cultivation implanted with the protection of tunnels and windbreaks on the coasts of the Beagle Channel. Right: cultivation with tunnel protection in the Río Chico Marsh on *Sarcocornia* mats. Taken from Bianciotto et al. (2015).

Table 18: *Sarcocornia* biomass production obtained with different systems during two consecutive years. (Sources: Vater et al. 2014).

Plant density	Treatment	Production 1 st year	Production 2 nd year
12 pl/m ²	Plastic Tunnel	1,115 g/m ²	4,374 g/m ²
	Without protection	513 g/m ²	1,832 g/m ²
18 pl/m ²	Plastic Tunnel	1,976 g/m ²	3,800 g/m ²
	Without protection	978 g/m ²	1,439 g/m ²

The productive cycle begins mid-December when the plant matures (Figure 50). At this time, shoots (5 cm in length) are collected using cuttings or stolons, transplanted, and watered with seawater (11

to 20 g/L) in a greenhouse at 20°C (Bianciotto *et al.* 2016; Bianciotto *et al.* 2021). It is harvested after four months of growth until reaching lengths of 13 cm (Ventura 2011). This type of harvest with staggered cuts makes it possible to lengthen the phenological cycle of the species and obtain sprouts through agamic reproduction for the second year of production, resulting in a cycle of 120 days from the capture of shoots to harvest (Bianciotto *et al.* 2004).

Figure 50: Productive cycle of *S. magellanica* developed in greenhouse. © CADIC-CONICET.

Market

Due to their nutritional (fiber, and antioxidant vitamins), organoleptic and medicinal properties, *sarcocornia* have a high economic potential in various biotechnology sectors and are considered promising gourmet vegetables to be explored in the context of climate change, soil, and water salinisation (Custódio *et al.* 2021). *S. magellanica* has a high Ca^{++} and Mg^{++} content, good digestibility, high protein content (34%), and abundant unsaturated essential fatty acids, giving it the aptitude for prolonged cholesterol treatments (Bianciotto *et al.* 2004). It has been tested and developed commercially for fresh or dry human consumption, and cultivation possibilities for sheep foraging have been tested in Argentina (Arce *et al.* 2016; Bianciotto *et al.* 2016; 2021). The retail value of glasswort in Europe can be estimated by the current values for *Salicornia* at around 12 €/Kg (Custódio *et al.* 2021).

Regarding the production cost of growing this species, Bianciotto *et al.* (2020) reported a value that varies between 5 and 10 US\$/kg of green shoot for human consumption and with possibilities of placement in the local market of Ushuaia City and the national one, with successful shipping tests for gastronomy in Buenos Aires (Figure 51). Also, some souvenir shops are selling grinders with sarcocornia on them.

Figure 51: Gourmet dish with salicornia grown in the Granja Biosalina of Rawson Ambiental inc., Argentina, offered in sea food restaurants. Taken from <https://rawsonambiental.com/>.

In ASTRAL, 27 seafood restaurants in Ushuaia City were surveyed to learn about the potential market for sarcocornia. The survey consisted of the following questions:

1. Do you know what sarcocornia is?
2. Do you use sarcocornia in your recipes?
3. Who are your suppliers, and where do they get sarcocornia from?
4. If you don't use sarcocornia, why don't you include it in your recipes?
5. Would you be interested in including sarcocornia in your recipes?

At the end of the surveys, a general description of the sarcocornia was transmitted, and it was explained how it is used in gastronomy, the harvest season, and when it can be found in Tierra del Fuego.

The main result of the survey showed that almost 50% of the restaurants know what sarcocornia is, but only 22.2% mentioned that they use it as an ingredient in their recipes. Besides, among the restaurants that know what sarcocornia is, 46.2 % use it in their gastronomic dishes (Figure 52).

Figure 52: State of knowledge and uses of sarcocornia by seafood restaurants in Ushuaia City, Argentina.

Among the restaurants that know about the species and use it in their recipes, they show interest in getting it fresh throughout the year. Some of the most exciting comments mentioned by the interviewees are the following:

- *“We use it in seafood recipes and as a dessert topping.”*
- *“We use it fresh in summer; the rest of the year, we keep it preparing vacuum pickle.”*
- *“We use it fresh in summer and dehydrated the rest of the year as salt.”*

Among the restaurants that do know sarcocornia but do not use it, the reasons were investigated, obtaining the following answers:

- *“We do not use sarcocornia because the species is available for very little time each year.”*
- *“We cannot include it because we do not know its qualities and suitability for human consumption.”*
- *“There are no cooks who know how to use it.”*
- *“We avoid incorporating it due to the lack of traceability.”*

Nevertheless, 22.0% of the restaurant that doesn't use sarcocornia in their recipe mentioned that they are interested in knowing how to incorporate it and the potential suppliers.

Summary of main characteristics

Table 19 shows main biological parameters relevant to aquaculture of glasswort.

Table 19: Main biological parameters of glasswort relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristic	Description	References
Environment type	Coastal, salt marshes, on soft and mud substrate.	Alonso and Crespo 2008
Soil salinity	17 – 19 g/L.	Bianciotto <i>et al.</i> 2016
Optimum soil temperature	10-25°C.	Bianciotto <i>et al.</i> 2004
Reproduction type	Hermaphroditic flowers.	Castroviejo and Coello 1980
Cycle type	Perennial.	Bianciotto <i>et al.</i> 2020
Natural cycle	Seeds (January); young halophytes (60 days); mature halophytes (60 days); bloom and harvest (30 days); fruiting and regrowth (60 days); senescence (30 days).	Vater <i>et al.</i> 2014; Arce <i>et al.</i> 2016; Bianciotto <i>et al.</i> 2016; 2020;
Seed size	0.9-1.3 mm.	Alonso and Crespo 2008
Flower size	0.7-2.0 mm.	Vater <i>et al.</i> 2014
Productivity (maximum)	4-4.5 kg/m ² and 0.70 kg/m ² (dry weight).	Bianciotto <i>et al.</i> 2016
Crop density (in greenhouse)	7-18 halophytes/m ² .	Bianciotto <i>et al.</i> 2020
Crop density (Plastic Tunnel)	4.1 kg/m ² (green shoots); 0.7 kg/m ² (dry weight).	Bianciotto <i>et al.</i> 2016
Crop density (Unprotected)	3.7 kg/m ² (green shoots); 0.5 kg/m ² (dry weight).	Bianciotto <i>et al.</i> 2016
Productive cycle (in greenhouse)	Young halophytes (30 days); mature halophytes and agamic reproduction (60 days); seedling regrowth (30 days).	Bianciotto <i>et al.</i> 2004, 2016; 2021; Vater <i>et al.</i> 2014; Ventura 2011

Gaps and recommendations

Biological studies

The most important aspect of its biology that was detected as a priority for future studies is to understand the complete cycle until the appearance of seeds to develop tools to obtain seedlings. Furthermore, how many years a halophyte can be kept producing shoots remains unknown. This is essential to evaluate a crop's profitability since it would allow quantifying the number of total harvests that could be obtained.

On the other hand, no data was found regarding pathogens that can attack these halophytes, for which specific investigations should also be planned.

Production

The cultivation of halophytes at the national level has been developed to produce forage for fattening sheep; however, it has yet to reach stable commercial levels (Bianciotto *et al.* 2020; Arce *et al.* 2016). One of the main limitations encountered has been reaching the scale of production needed

to supply livestock producers. In this sense, an important step would be to understand and quantify the demand of livestock producers to dimension the scale of production that should be achieved.

Another opportunity around the production of *sarcocornia* is the use of this halophyte for bioremediation projects of wastewater from fisheries, taking advantage of the capacity of this species to accumulate and degrade organic and inorganic substances (See section 6.1 for more details). Besides, the high nitrogen needs of *S. magellanica* are highly attractive for implementation to the retention of this nutrient integrated with fed aquaculture.

There are several works on the cultivation of halophytes in aquaponic systems (Maciel *et al.* 2020; Marques *et al.* 2021). This type of system could be a good way to take the first steps in developing their cultivation since these systems can be deployed in small spaces on an experimental scale, ideal for manipulating controlled conditions with little investment.

Traceability and consumer confidence

Regarding the distrust about the traceability and safety of glasswort, it should be made known that *S. magellanica* was registered in [Article 822](#) of the Argentine Food Code in April 2023 through the [Joint Resolution 11/23](#) by the Secretariat of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries together with the Secretariat of Quality in Health.

Sarcocornia, in addition to being a halophyte, is characterised by being a metallophyte, which means that it can grow in environments with high concentrations of metals (Ginocchio and Baker 2004). In particular, it is known that *S. neei* can live in soils with high contents of heavy metals, such as Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, As, Hg, and Cd, without suffering phytotoxicity (Sepúlveda *et al.* 2020). This ability to bioaccumulate heavy metals makes it necessary to pay special attention to ensuring that *sarcocornia* production is carried out with a water source free of heavy metals to avoid health problems.

Market opportunities

To develop the local market, chefs must promote the use of glasswort through gastronomic courses. In this sense, it is important to highlight the activities carried out by the National Institute of Agricultural Technology (INTA) of Tierra del Fuego, promoting the consumption of *salicornia* through field trips to recognize this species in the marshes, workshops on methods of harvest and gastronomic courses.

Another area for improvement related to the value chain of *sarcocornia* is that fresh products are only available for a short period of the year, representing an unfavourable scenario for installing the product in restaurants. To resolve this limitation, researchers and students from the National Technological University of Tierra del Fuego have formed a working group in 2022 under the motto

Chemistry Applied to the Environment, Food and Sustainable Development (QA3DS)⁸ to explore new frontiers in food from Tierra del Fuego through freeze-drying processes not only of *sarcocornia* but also of red sea urchin uni. This process would preserve food but keep its flavours, textures and, most importantly, its nutritional values intact.

8.3.3 Blue Mussel (*Mytilus chilensis*)

Distribution

The blue mussel *Mytilus chilensis* is a filter-feeder bivalve that distributed along the Pacific coast of Chile and up to Brazil in the Atlantic (Osorio 2002; Figure 53).

Figure 53: Computer generated distribution maps for *Mytilus chilensis* (Blue mussel), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Biology

Recent evidence suggests that *Mytilus chilensis* and *Mytilus platensis* (mainly registered on the South Atlantic coast) represent conspecific variants rather than distinct species (Gaitán-Espitia *et al.* 2016 and references therein). They occur mainly in the intertidal and subtidal zone at depths of ~10m and exceptionally to 25 m (Osorio 2002). It can form dense banks of up to 5000 individuals/m² when not exposed to the breaking waves (Duarte *et al.* 2006). *M. chilensis* has separate sexes and a complex life cycle alternating between a planktonic larval phase and a benthic juvenile-adult phase (Molinet Flores *et al.* 2015 and references therein; Figure 54). *M. chilensis* attains sexual maturity during its first year of life, usually in spring-summer time (if environmental conditions are favourable). Sperm

⁸ More information about this company can be found in <https://qa3ds-frtdf.tech/>.

and oocytes are released into the water, where fertilisation occurs. On the Atlantic coast of Argentina, total spawning, partial spawning, and seed catchment events vary throughout the year and with latitude (Isola 2019). In the Beagle Channel, total spawning events occur in May-June and October-November, with short rest periods during February-March (Isola 2019). The new individual (trochophore larvae) does not have a valve and feeds actively. Development continues through a valved larva (veliger larvae) and finally through a pediveliger one. The pediveliger larvae eventually attach to hard substrates such as rocks and then reach the adult form. The larvae take between 24-48 hours to go from the trochophore to the veliger stage, and it takes them around 30-45 days to the postlarva stage, depending on the environmental conditions (Pacheco and Olave 2000).

Figure 54: Typical life cycle of blue mussel in the Beagle Channel. © CADIC-CONICET.

Fisheries and Wild Stocks

Historically, mussel landings from wild stocks in Chile never exceeded 10 tons annually. Since the 1990s, wild stock harvests have gradually and then rapidly been replaced by culture production, which increased exponentially after a few years (Gonzalez-Poblete *et al.* 2018). During the last decade (2010-2020), mussel landings in Chile averaged 306.000 tons per year, over 98% from cultures (SERNAPESCA 2020). In Argentina, mussel production combines wild stock harvests and cultures, reaching 248 tons in 2011 (Trivellini 2019), to only 2 tons in 2020 (FAO 2022; Figure 55).

Regarding the state of its wild populations and distribution of banks, there is no published data along the Beagle Channel, much less along the Southwest Atlantic coast. Although it is known that there is empirical data about the location of some mussel banks. Therefore, knowledge about the ability to capture seeds is limited.

Figure 55: Historical harvest from aquaculture of *Mitilus chilensis* in Argentina. Data Source: FAO 2022.

Aquaculture State

China is the world's leading producer of mussels, while Chile is currently the second, reaching landings of 400,604 tons in 2020, becoming one of the leading world exporters (SERNAPESCA 2020). Nowadays, particularly in South America, blue mussel aquaculture is performed mainly through suspension cultures, including rafts in quiet waters and longlines in rough waters (Pacheco and Olave 2000).

In Argentina, mussel aquaculture (including *M. chilensis*) is slowly developing. Remarkably, several small-scale attempts were addressed in the Beagle Channel during the past decades in the coastal area of Puerto Almanza, Beagle Channel (Zampatti 2002; Bertolotti *et al.* 2011; 2014). These initiatives were active for 12 years and peaked in 2004, reaching 45 tons (Figure 56). For a few years, production reached between 22 and 32 tons and diminished drastically during the last years of activity (2010-2012), fluctuating between 1 and 6 tons per year (Fosati 2011). In 2021, a private company, technically supported by the Secretariat of Fisheries and Aquaculture of TdF, has already begun to invest part of the over 1.5-million-dollar budget in a new blue mussel farming project in the area. This company has yet to harvest and market the product, so it is impossible to analyze its results.

Figure 56: Harvest from natural bank and aquaculture production of *M. chilensis* in the Beagle Channel between 2000 and 2010. Modified from Bertolotti *et al.* 2011.

The blue mussel production cycle lasts from 12 to 18 months from seed catchment to achieve a commercial size of 57 mm (Silva 1998; Zampatti *et al.* 2012). It typically involves five steps: 1) seed catchment (2-3 cm seeds); 2) seed string when seeds are included in a cotton sleeve surrounded by a fishing net; 3) growth when cords are placed in rafts or longlines until reaching the commercial size (6-8 cm); 4) thinning when mussel density is controlled to ensure homogenous growth and avoid detachments; and 5) harvest when the mussels are detachment, cleaning, and size grading for commercialisation.

The seed collectors are installed one month after the spawning season to ensure the settlement of the post-larvae in December-February (Isola 2019).

A complete production cycle lasts two years, from the natural collection of seeds to the harvest, with one unfolding annually in autumn (Figure 57). Also, it is possible to perform a cycle of only 14-18 months if bank seed is used.

Figure 57: Productive cycle of blue mussel in the Beagle Channel. © CADIC-CONICET.

Market

Mussel culture is well-established and occurs in many countries worldwide, and the global production of *Mytilus chilensis* is up to 365.6 thousand tonnes (FAO 2020). In 2020, the leading buyer markets for Chile’s products were Spain, Russia, the United States of America, France and Italy, accounting for 67% of the total mussel exports. Chile’s production is mainly commercialised frozen (92.6%), preserved (5.4%) or fresh (2%) (SERNAPESCA 2020). Argentina’s mussel production comes primarily from Tierra del Fuego and Chubut provinces and is commercialised locally, regionally, or nationally. However, due to low local production, Argentina imports blue mussels from Chile (<https://mejillondechile.cl/industria/>). The production is commercialised internally, with Buenos Aires City as the primary recipient market (Huidobro 2019). In Argentina, mussels are sold frozen (with or without valves), fresh (in coastal markets) and preserved. Market prices for mussels range from US\$ 7.5/kg in Buenos Aires (frozen, valved; <https://www.buenosmares.com.ar/mariscos/>) up to US\$ 10.25/kg in Ushuaia (frozen, without valve; <https://pescaderia-seafood-patagonia.com.ar>).

Summary of Main Characteristics

Table 20 and Table 21 show biological parameters relevant to aquaculture, and parameters related to the performance of the blue mussel in farms at the Beagle Channel.

Table 20: Main biological parameters of blue mussel relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristic	Description	References
Environment type	Intertidal, subtidal, on hard substrata.	Zelaya and Güller 2014
Depth	Up to 25 m.	Pacheco and Olave 2000; Osorio 2002
Max. length	92 mm in the longest axis.	Cremonte <i>et al.</i> 2011
Max. weight	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. age	Data not available or not determined.	
Length – Weight relationship	Data not available or not determined.	
Reproductive type	External fertilisation. Gonochoric. Dioic.	Oyarzún <i>et al.</i> 2011
Spawning season	October - November (main season). May - June (minor season).	Tortorelli 1987
Maturation age	First year.	Isola 2019
Maturation size	Data not available or not determined.	
Type of eggs	Free pelagic.	
Egg size	60-90 µm.	Tortorelli 1987; Diaz <i>et al.</i> 2018
Fecundity	2.38×10^5 to 6.55×10^6	Lagos <i>et al.</i> 2012
Newly larvae weight	11 days \sim 120 µm	Diaz <i>et al.</i> 2018
Larvae feeding habits	Filter POM	Zelaya and Güller 2014
Juvenile feeding habits	Filter POM	Zelaya and Güller 2014
Adults feeding habits	Filter POM	Zelaya and Güller 2014

Table 21: Main performance for blue mussel farm in the Beagle Channel.

Characteristic	Description	References
Initial seed density	2.4 Kg / meter of line	Silva 1998
Final rearing density	7 - 9 kg/meter of line	Silva 1998
Fertilization rate	44.6 - 94%	Tortorelli 1987; Lagos <i>et al.</i> 2012
Hatching rate	Larvae D: 67.6 - 99 %	Lagos <i>et al.</i> 2012
Larvae survival	Data not available or not determined.	
Juvenile survival	Data not available or not determined.	
Adult survival	Data not available or not determined.	
Post spawn survival	Data not available or not determined.	
SGR	Data not available or not determined.	
FCR	Data not available or not determined.	
Obtaining gametes	Capture of natural seeds with artificial collectors	Silva 1998
Fertilization	50 oocytes/ml + 10^4 spermatozoa/ml	Tortorelli 1987
Incubation temperature	7-9°C	Tortorelli 1987
Incubation salinity	26 ppm	Tortorelli 1987

Gaps and recommendations

Biological studies

Few studies have described the life cycle of *M. chilensis* in detail in the Beagle Channel, and no analyses relate environmental variables such as temperature and photoperiod in the modulation of this cycle. In this way, it is essential to develop research aimed at understanding the life history of this species, mainly in those phases that allow designing strategies for seed collection to supply

cultivation systems. Furthermore, since the mussel production cycle begins with the collection of natural seeds, conducting studies on the state and distribution of natural banks would be advisable.

There is also no available data on growth rates except the study done by Silva (1998) 30 years ago (Figure 58). This marks a significant gap in vital information to manage production and to relate growth rates with environmental factors such as temperature, depth, and productivity, among others, as well as productive factors such as reared density. Thus, to plan more efficient farms, estimating the growth curves for several years is essential to determine the best conditions to use. This takes on greater importance if the integration of cultivation with other species is proposed since the environmental needs of the species must be similar for multitrophic aquaculture to work.

Figure 58: Growth curve of blue mussel reared in longlines in the Beagle Channel. Data source: Silva 1998.

Another essential aspect to achieve is understanding the distribution of *M. chilensis* in the Argentine Sea and confirming or rejecting the presence of areas where it forms natural hybrids with *M. edulis* as has been suggested by previous works (Oyarzún *et al.* 2016).

Aquaculture

The frequent blooms of toxic dinoflagellates occurring in the Beagle Channel force bans on the collection and marketing of bivalve molluscs to be imposed. This situation could represent a limitation for aquaculture's regional development and growth. However, in recent years, significant progress in understanding the harmful algal bloom events in the Beagle Channel and protocols for monitoring them have been achieved (Almandoz *et al.* 2019; Cadaillon *et al.* 2022; Schloss *et al.* 2023). In addition, it is important to highlight that the province of Tierra del Fuego acquired a

spectrometer for determining toxins in 2023 thanks to funds from the National Fund for the Development of Aquaculture Activities (FONAC). These acquired capacities allow management strategies to be carried out to adapt production to temporal variations in the presence of toxins.

One of the drawbacks of longline cultivation is the overloading of lines due to biofouling (Cahill *et al.* 2022). In this sense, it would be important to determine when there are seeds from other species, such as scallops, ribbed mussels, ascidians, and cirripedians, to design strategies to avoid or reduce the overweight of the lines. Of all the species that can make up the biofouling community, ascidians are one of the organisms that can represent the greatest load on mussel longlines (Papadopoulos *et al.* 2023).

Market opportunity

Global mussel aquaculture production has increased steadily since the 1950s, reaching 2 million tonnes in 2019 (FAO 2020). Nevertheless, European production has decreased while the market has increased, which is a good opportunity to boost production in other countries like Argentina to supply this market (Avdelas *et al.* 2021).

Furthermore, it has been seen that farmed mussels from Beagle Channel have a higher mussel/shell ratio than mussels obtained from natural banks (Silva 1998). This fact makes the marketing cost lower when it comes to farmed mussels due to a decrease in transportation costs.

Traceability and consumer confidence

M. edulis is the only species of the genus *Mytilus* included in the Argentine Food Code (see Article 270⁹). Nevertheless, *Mytilus spp.* are included as Fishing Products in the Chapter 23 of the Decree 4238/68¹⁰. In this sense, including *Mytilus chilensis* in the Argentine food code would be important to increase consumer confidence.

Seafood traceability, sustainability, and consumers' right to an informed purchase represent challenges that specific regulations and controls should be addressed. A fundamental aspect is that the products have a correct identification of the species that are marketed. In this sense, considering situations that have already occurred regarding the incorrect identification of bivalve molluscs in several international markets (see Giusti *et al.* 2020), it is advisable to carry out molecular identification monitors of *Mytilus spp.* present in the Beagle Channel, which could add value to the

⁹ The Article 270 of the Argentine Food Code can be queried in:

https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/anmat_caa_capitulo_vi_carneos_act_2023_5.pdf

¹⁰ The Chapter 23 of the Decree 4238/68 can be queried in:

<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/recurso/24788/dn4238-1968cap23/htm>

product through greater traceability. For instance, a significant advance in this direction was made by Chile in 2020 when the Integrated Taxonomic Information System (<https://www.itis.gov/>) incorporated *Mytilus chilensis* in its database as a valid scientific name for the mussel native to the Chilean coast. This decision was supported by the results published by Larraín *et al.* (2018) about the phylogeny of the genus *Mytilus*. Although the scientific name *Mytilus chilensis* had already been recognized as valid by other taxonomic databases (e.g. WoRMS, EOL, FAO, and GAA), the inclusion in ITIS is essential, as it is one of the most consulted databases to obtain authorized taxonomic information worldwide.

8.3.4 Red Sea Urchin (*Loxechinus albus*)

Distribution

L. albus has a wide geographic distribution in the southeastern Pacific Ocean (Figure 59). It is found uninterruptedly from the north of Peru (6°53'50" S) to the Isla de los Estados at the southern tip of the American continent (57°58'00" S). It is also found in the Beagle Channel and the Strait of Magellan.

Figure 59: Computer generated distribution maps for *Loxechinus albus* (red sea urchin), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Biology

The red sea urchin is a member of the phylum Echinodermata, which contains about six thousand species, including starfish and sea cucumbers (Broger *et al.* 2013). This species inhabits mainly on

rocky bottoms and *Macrocystis* forests, feeding algae of the genera *Lessonia*, *Macrocystis*, *Ulva*, *Polysiphonia*, and *Porphyra* (Yamashiro Guinoza *et al.* 1996). Its translation capacity is low, mainly using its spikes and ambulacral feet. Its maximum size can reach 150 mm in diameter without considering the spikes (Yamashiro Guinoza *et al.* 1996).

The natural cycle of *L. albus* in the Beagle Channel is described in Figure 60. It begins with the spawning season during spring-summer (Pérez 2008; Schuhbauer 2010; Brogger 2013; Vásquez 2020; Lovrich *et al.* 2021). The red sea urchin hatches as a planktonic prism larva after 48 hours of incubation, and after 18 days, they reach the pre-metamorphic larva stage to fixate and become a benthic juvenile finally (Vidal 2000; Bustos 2001; Sosa 2016; Lovrich 2021). The pre-metamorphic stage can be recognized by the larvae changing from a pelagic behaviour to a benthic behaviour, after the absorption of the arms, acquiring a spherical shape (Espinoza and Arraigada 2017). The red sea urchin is characterized by slow growth, taking 4 to 5 years to reach the adult stage with an approximate size of 40 mm test diameter (Frayse 2017; Urrutia *et al.* 1999; Bustos 2001; Arana 2005; Carcamo 2015; Sosa 2016; Pierola 2017; Lovrich 2021).

Figure 60: Typical life cycle of red sea urchin in the Beagle Channel. © CADIC-CONICET.

Fisheries and Wild Stock Status

L. albus is one of the most economically important species for the artisanal fishery in the Pacific littoral benthic of South America, and Chile has one of the most important sea urchin fisheries worldwide (Andrew *et al.* 2002; Arana 2005). Chilean landings of *L. albus* averaged 18,077 t between 2010 and 2016, causing a dramatic decrease in population density and alterations in size structure. (Contreras *et al.* 2019). There is practically no data on the past and status of the sea urchin stock in the Beagle Channel. Nevertheless, the government of the province of Tierra del Fuego has shown interest to exploit this live resource (see the report by Orler 1997). Dayton (1985) mentions that the abundance of this species in the Beagle Channel is low compared to other parts of its distribution due to the West wind Drift that carries most of the larvae away. This edible sea urchin has been exploited sporadically in the Beagle Channel, mainly in Ushuaia Bay and its vicinity. Principally, it has been destined for the local market, for tourism from the eastern countries, and occasionally exported to Chile (Pérez 2009). Resolution 292/2022 authorised the “Sustainable Program for the use of the Sea urchin Resource in the Beagle Channel”, in waters under the provincial jurisdiction of the Beagle Channel, framed in the “Red Sea Urchin Research Campaign (*Loxechinus albus*) in the Beagle Channel”, for one year. This program aims to determine the closed areas, reproductive seasons, and period of commercial use and establish, in turn, the scale of the fishery: artisanal, intermediate, or commercial/industrial, among other objectives that the Enforcement Authority deems appropriate to establish, to ensure exploitation sustainable.

In Chile, its minimum extraction size is between 6.5 and 7.0 cm in test diameter (excluding the spikes), depending on the fishery zone (www.sernapesca.cl/medidas/erizo; Ayerbe Ochoa *et al.* 2018).

Aquaculture State

Due to the high demand for sea urchins as human food, and because landings have fallen by more than half in the last 20 years, aquaculture is in full expansion (Stefánsson *et al.* 2017; FAO 2020). Some knowledge has been accumulated to enable the cultivation of larvae and juveniles of *L. albus* in a controlled environment (Pérez *et al.* 1995; Bustos and Olave 2001; Ayerbe Ochoa *et al.* 2018). From a list of 17 echinoderm species from Latin America with commercial value, the sea cucumber *Isostichopus fuscus*, and the sea urchins, *L. albus* and *Arbacia dufresnii* stand out for their potential for aquaculture. This list is supported by growth, feed conversion, nutritional and nutraceutical values, domestication grade, and relevance for re-stocking wild populations (Sonnenholzner-Varas 2021). Although aquaculture research on red sea urchins has focused mainly

on the reproductive cycle and larval production for repopulation (Cárcamo *et al.* 2004b; Espinoza and Arraigada 2017) and gonadal improvement through the implementation of artificial diets (Olave *et al.* 2001; Fraysse *et al.* 2017). High gonadal production by feeding with artificial diets has been reported for *L. albus* (Lawrence *et al.* 1997; Vidal Santana 2000). The main bottleneck for sea urchin culture is the long period required to achieve market size (Lawrence *et al.* 2001).

The larvae are maintained in 20-L polycarbonate carboys under constant aeration (Cárcamo *et al.* 2005). Corrugated and smooth polycarbonate sheets have been used to induce metamorphosis (Zamora and Stotz 1994). Post-larvae are reared in fibreglass tanks with sets of transparent fibreglass plates assembled with plastic pipes (Bustos and Olave 2001).

The systems experimented with for the growth of red sea urchins have been land-based open systems using rectangular or conical fibreglass tanks (Espinoza and Arraigada 2017; Ayerbe Ochoa *et al.* 2018) and open systems in cages suspended or supported on the marine bed (Vidal Santana 2000; Cárcamo 2004a; Ayerbe Ochoa *et al.* 2018).

The productive cycle of *L. albus* can begin with the capture of adult individuals by diving before the spawning season (Figure 61). Once in the laboratory, they are induced to spawn by injecting in the coelomic cavity with 3 ml of 0.5 M KCl through the peristomial membrane (Zamora and Stotz 1994; Bustos and Olave 2001). Fertilization takes place in 50-l plastic containers 4.5 X10⁶ eggs/container, stirred gently, add 10 ml of sperm suspension, prepared by diluting 1 ml of concentrated sperm from five adult male urchins in 200 ml seawater (Cárcamo *et al.* 2005). From there, they are attached to suspended culture systems or through cages on rocky bottoms, to which maintenance must be carried out and food renewed by diving (Bustos 2001; Olave 2001). To carry out the fattening stage in a natural environment, starting with individuals of 10 mm is recommended, which can be achieved in 12 to 18 months in the laboratory (Perez 1995; Sonnenholzner 2021). The estimated fattening time at sea is three years using balanced feed (Bustos 2001; Pierola 2017), which makes it possible to reduce the harvest by more than one year compared with natural captures.

Figure 61: Productive cycle of red sea urchin. © CADIC-CONICET.

Market

The sea urchin roe is considered a delicatessen worldwide and is a traditional food in Japan, a country that accounts for over 80 % of the global consumption the seafood (Brown and Eddy 2015). Consumer demand for sea urchins is driven by several key market factors, including innovation, experimentation, and health (Stefánsonn *et al.* 2017).

The gonads or roe, informally called urchin “tongues”, constitute the product the market requests. The organoleptic characteristics of sea urchins’ gonads (size and colour, among others) determine the final market value (Frayse *et al.* 2017).

A business model has been created along the sea urchin value chain for open-water and land-based IMTA in Ireland and South Africa ASTRAL IMTA labs. High-value products for niche and luxury markets around sea urchins have been detected as an internal strength, with great economic opportunities due to sea urchins’ consumption booms in Asian markets. As a social external factor, a misreading of the sea urchin in many countries has been detected, requiring a valorisation of the product to achieve new markets.

Summary of Main Characteristics

Table 22-Table 25 show biological parameters relevant to aquaculture, water quality needs, and parameters related to the performance of the red sea urchin in captivity and feeding tests in aquaculture.

Table 22: Main biological parameters of red sea urchin relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Environment type	Intertidal and shallow subtidal rocky environments. On boulders, less frequently found in rock crevasses or under boulders and never found inside the holdfasts of <i>M. Pyrifera</i> .	Vásquez <i>et al.</i> 1984; Dayton 1985; Vásquez and Buschmann 1997
Depth	Commonly 1-16 m, but also at >100m.	Vásquez <i>et al.</i> 1984; Molinet <i>et al.</i> 2012
Max. weight males	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. weight females	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. size	89.1 mm - 161.6 mm.	Urrutia <i>et al.</i> 1999
Max. age	13 years.	Schuhbauer <i>et al.</i> 2010
Test diameter – Weight relationship	$W (g) = 0.02713 * TD (mm)^{2.00708}$ $W (g) = 0.0023646 * TD (mm)^{2.54939}$	Urrutia <i>et al.</i> 1999; Arana 2005
Growth curve	$D_T = DT_{\infty}(1 - \exp^{-K(t-t_0)})$. ($DT_{\infty}=95.1$; $K=0.179$; $t_0=-0.1952$). $D_T = DT_{\infty}(1 - be^{-Kt})^{-n}$. ($DT_{\infty}=120$; $K=0.06$; $n=349$). $D_T = DT_0 e^{G(1 - e^{-Kt})}$. ($DT_0=8.5^b$; $G=2.31$; $K=0.35$)	Schuhbauer <i>et al.</i> 2010
Reproductive type	Dioicous, without sex dimorphism.	Ayerbe Ochoa <i>et al.</i> 2018
Spawning season	September – December.	Bay-Smith <i>et al.</i> 1981; Pérez <i>et al.</i> 2010
Maturation age	4 years.	Vásquez 2007
Maturation size males	TD 30-50 mm, all mature: 60 mm.	Bay-Smith <i>et al.</i> 1981
Maturation size females	First maturation: Test diameter 30-50 mm, all mature: 70 mm.	Bay-Smith <i>et al.</i> 1981
Type of eggs	Data not available or not determined.	
Egg size	Diameter: 120 μ m.	Cárcamo <i>et al.</i> 2005
Fecundity	Expressed as the difference between the Gonadosomatic Index of mature and spawned gonads: 7.28%.	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 2010
Newly larvae weight	Data not available or not determined.	
Newly larvae (metamorphosis) size	Diameter: 0.33 - 0.41 mm.	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 1995
Metamorphosis period	45 dpf.	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 1995
Larvae feeding habits	Microalgae.	Cárcamo <i>et al.</i> 2005
Juvenile feeding habits	Benthic grazers, Macroalgae, mainly macrocystis.	Dayton 1985; Vásquez 2007
Adults feeding habits	Benthic grazers, Macroalgae, mainly macrocystis.	Dayton 1985; Vásquez 2007

Table 23: Main water quality conditions need for red sea urchin.

Characteristics	Description	References
Salinity	32.2 psu	Cárcamo <i>et al.</i> 2005
Temperature	16 - 18°C	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 1995; Bustos and Olave 2001; Cárcamo <i>et al.</i> 2005; Espinoza and Arraigada 2017
Photoperiod	12L:12D	Cárcamo <i>et al.</i> 2005; Espinoza and Arraigada 2017
pH	6-7.8	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 1995; Bustos and Olave 2001
Ammonium	200 - 300 mg/ml	Bustos and Olave 2001
Nitrite	Data not available or not determined.	
O ₂	Data not available or not determined.	

Table 24: Main characteristic related to performance of red sea urchin in aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Initial larval density	0.7 – 1.5 larvae/ml.	Espinoza and Arraigada 2017
Rearing density	0.25 juvenile / cm ² .	Espinoza and Arraigada 2017
Fertilization rate	95-100 %.	Zamora and Stotz 1994; Cárcamo <i>et al.</i> 2005
Hatching rate	Data not available or not determined.	
Larvae survival	Survival at 27 dpf eggs < 100 µm: 18%; 100 µm: 25%. 63-82 % depending on diet composition.	Pérez 1995; Cárcamo <i>et al.</i> 2005
Competent survival	49-58%.	Cárcamo <i>et al.</i> 2005
Juvenile survival	Data not available or not determined.	
Adult survival	Data not available or not determined.	
Post spawn survival	Data not available or not determined.	
SGR	Data not available or not determined.	
FCR	Data not available or not determined.	
Obtaining gametes	Spawning induced with KCl.	Zamora and Stotz 1994; Bustos and Olave 2001
Incubator system	Circular tanks 40L.	Espinoza and Arraigada 2017
Volumetric eggs	Data not available or not determined.	
Spermatic density	Data not available or not determined.	
Motility	Data not available or not determined.	
Incubation temperature	Data not available or not determined.	
Incubation salinity	Data not available or not determined.	
Thermal Units	24-26 h, there is no data about T°C.	Zamora and Stotz 1994
Hatching	Data not available or not determined.	

Table 25: Summary of red sea urchin feeding tests in aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Time until first exogenous feeding	Data not available or not determined.	
Larvae	Post-metamorphic. Microalgae: <i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i> , <i>t-Isochrysis</i> , <i>Pseudoisochrysis</i> and <i>Chaetoceros gracilis</i>	Zamora and Stotz 1994; Pérez <i>et al.</i> 1995
Juveniles and ongrowing	Macroalgae: 2/3 <i>Macrocystis pyrifera</i> , 1/3 <i>Ulva</i> sp., <i>ad libitum</i> Extruded (% of dry weight): Diet 1: Corn 36.56, Ground wheat 36.40, Soya meal 11.10, Fish Meal 10.00, Calcium Carbonate 1.66, Sodium Biphosphate 1.17, Phospholipid 1.00, Fish oil 0.71, Sodium chloride 0.61, Cholesterol 0.30, Minerals and Vitamins 0.20, Vitamin C 0.08, Carotenoids 0.01. Diet 2: Kelp 14.00, Corn 32.00, Ground wheat 27.53, Soya meal 11.10, Fish Meal 12.00, Potassium Biphosphate 1.33, Fish oil 0.24, Cholesterol 0.30, Minerals and Vitamins 0.08, Vitamin C 0.08.	Vidal Santana 2000; Cárcamo 2004a
Enhance gonad quality	<i>Macrocystis pyrifera</i> meal 100 %. <i>Macrocystis pyrifera</i> meal 14 %; Soybean meal 13 %; Corn starch 24.53 %; Wheat 23 %; Fish meal 12 %; B-carotene 0.02 %; Lecithin 2%; Corn oil 4%; Dicalcium phosphate 1.8 %; Ethoxyquin 0.2 %; Vit C 0.1 %; Vit/Min 0.1 %; Magnesium oxide 0.25 %; Gelatin 5%.	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 2015
Cannibalism	No reported	
Size separation	Data not available or not determined.	

Gaps and Recommendations

Biological studies

Although there is reliable information on the biology of *L. albus*, it would be recommended to validate the biological aspects at the southern end of its distribution where the potential IMTA system would be placed. Secondly, coupled with the previously mentioned information, it is essential to assess the actual state of red sea urchin wild banks in the Beagle Channel for estimating the availability of seed. In this sense, the government of the Province of Tierra del Fuego is working together with CADIC-CONICET researchers to update the basic knowledge from wild populations, focused on several estimations such as the number of banks in the area, density, and growth parameters of *L. albus*.

Furthermore, the species' slow growth would imply a rapid decline in the performance of wild populations if they were collected frequently, as has occurred in other regions.

Thus, the use of *L. albus* as a link in a multitrophic system would be justified by its benefits to the system as a sediment POM feeder and the market that demands its production.

Aquaculture

Unlike in other areas of species' distribution, the abundance of the *L. albus* in the Beagle Channel appears low. This added to the growing demand in the market for the species, would indicate that, in time, a decrease in population numbers is highly probable. Thus, developing appropriate aquaculture techniques for *L. albus* is needed.

Regarding aquaculture, knowledge is limited and restricted to the larval phase for stock enhancement. Therefore, further research is required on the aquaculture of juvenile and adult phases to understand how to articulate its culture in a potential multitrophic system. It is considered essential to estimate both growth and survival rates for juvenile and adult stages. Particular focus on the nutritional aspects of the species would be useful to enhance the growth and survival of the different stages and to understand how to articulate its culture in the multitrophic system.

Market opportunity

One option to take the first commercial steps in developing sea urchin farming is to supply the local market around international tourism that grows in the province of Tierra del Fuego. In this sense, promotional initiatives such as the creation of the "*Ruta de la Centolla*" (Southern king crab route), which promotes the gastronomy of local species along a tourist corridor through 15 km in the coastal route between Puerto Almanza and Punta Paraná are of great help. Furthermore, it is interesting to mention that this corridor runs along the coast of the Beagle Channel where marine aquaculture has

historically been developed, which would allow the market to be near of the production area, reducing marketing costs.

Traceability and consumer confidence

L. albus is not included in the Argentine Food Code. Nevertheless, *A. Dufresnii* was included in Article 270¹¹, being the first and only echinoderm included, which would facilitate the incorporation of new species.

As was mentioned for whitebait, it is suggested that when marketing the product, it should be highlighted that it comes from local aquaculture, which could increase consumer confidence and add value.

¹¹ The Article 270 of the Argentine Food Code can be queried in:
https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/anmat_caa_capitulo_vi_carneos_act_2023_5.pdf

9 Proposed IMTA Configurations

From the species previously selected and described, two IMTA configurations were proposed and briefly described. The first configuration is integrated with whitebait (fed aquaculture) and sarcocornia (extractive aquaculture) maintained on land-based semi-closed system. The other proposed IMTA is integrated by the production of mussels in longlines (extractive aquaculture) together with the production of sea urchins in suspended cages (fed aquaculture).

In this report, no work was done on the design of the IMTA facilities since this depends on innumerable variables such as the level of available investment, availability of inputs and equipment, the specific site where the production would be located and the market targeted. In this way, only the compatibility between the species selected to integrate the same multitrophic system is mentioned in the following sections.

9.1 Glasswort (*Sarcocornia magellanica*) + Whitebait (*Galaxias maculatus*)

There are many examples of using halophytes as biofilters to treat final effluents from marine aquaculture (Brown *et al.* 1999). However, in recent years, these have begun to be used as components of integrated multitrophic systems (see Custódio *et al.* 2017 and cites therein).

The large volumes of wastewater discharged from open land-based systems can affect seriously the surrounding coast by increasing nutrients, mainly inorganic N and P. An option successfully applied for disposing of marine aquaculture effluent is using salt-tolerant plants commonly named halophytes (Brown *et al.* 1999; Buhmann and Papenbrock 2013; Liang *et al.* 2017). The potential of these species for reducing and recycling waste, optimizing resource utilization, and developing alternative production in the frame of a sustainable model for a circular economy has been mentioned by Chaturvedi *et al.* (2021). Constructed wetlands could be a good option for treating and/or exploiting wastewater in a highly cost-efficient way, requiring low investment and the use of non-nature materials (Turcios *et al.* 2021). Besides, this system avoids or diminishes the necessity of using plastic. It is highly noted that in Argentina, the company Rawson Ambiental¹², located in Chubut Province, is leading a project evaluating on a pilot-commercial scale using settling (anaerobic) and oxygenation (aerobics) ponds provided with geomembrane mounted on geotextile to treat wastewater from fish processing. This company is also evaluating the growth of glasswort

¹² More information about this company can be found in <https://rawsonambiental.com/>.

Sarcocornia neei on a pilot-commercial scale, taking advantage of the dissolved nitrogen in the previously treated wastewater (Figure 62).

This system has the limitation that wastewater availability from seafood processing plants is not constant throughout the year since it is interrupted during closed seasons. A strategy to overcome this limitation could be incorporating water used for whitebait production into sarcocornia cultivation. Particularly, since salicornia cuttings in a greenhouse can be produced in aquaponic cultures, this system could be temporarily coupled with the production of puyen as a source of water rich in nitrogen and inorganic dissolved phosphorus. The latter would be beneficial in maintaining whitebait adults and larvae since both phases grow in euryhaline environments.

Figure 62: Rawson Ambiental SA facilities with ponds where aerobic denitrification and subsequent irrigation of *sarcocornia* are carried out.

It is widely known that aquaculture feed represents, mainly in fish, the principal cost along the production value chain, with protein sources being one of the supplies that most affect its value. This cost increases for aquaculture facilities isolated from balanced food production centres, as in Tierra del Fuego (Hualde 2005). For this reason, to achieve a profitable aquaculture initiative, it is essential to deploy strategies that reduce the costs of the food used.

The most used protein input is fish meal, which has acceptable costs, digestibility, and conversion values. However, the expansion of aquaculture and the withdrawal of some fisheries have considerably increased their value, making the search for alternative protein sources essential (Rana

et al. 2009). Various alternative protein sources have been tested for the formulations of diets for fish and other aquatic animals (Luthada-Raswiswi *et al.* 2021). Among them, the earthworm proteins present interesting characteristics not only from a nutritional point of view but also as facilitators of circular production (Parolini *et al.* 2020). In Argentina, the presence of 74 species of earthworms have been recorded (Mischis 2000; Christoffersen 2011), 11 of which are present in Tierra del Fuego (Mischis and Moreno 2003). Particularly, the epigeal worm *Lumbricus rubellus*, introduced to Tierra del Fuego from Europe (Mischis and Herrera 2006), has been successfully tested as a potential source of protein for animal feed (Kostecka and Pączka 2006; Isea *et al.* 2008; Istiqomah *et al.* 2009; Farah *et al.* 2019). Likewise, this species is recognised as valid for composting organic waste and producing vermicompost, facilitating the development of circular production systems (Domínguez and Gómez Brandón 2010; Vanella *et al.* 2019; 2021).

9.2 Blue Mussel (*Mytilus chilensis*) + Red Sea Urchin (*Loxechinus albus*)

As mentioned, one of the drawbacks of blue mussel cultivation in longlines is the overloading of lines due to biofouling, for which various preventive solutions and treatments have been sought (Bannister *et al.* 2019). A novel opportunity that arises from IMTA systems is the possibility of biologically controlling biofouling by integrating the production of species that take advantage of biofouling as food. In this framework, several studies have shown that cultivating urchins in cages suspended on mussel longlines reduces biofouling (Sterling *et al.* 2016). Furthermore, sea urchins grown on longlines deployed higher survival and growth rates than wild stocks (Cook and Kelly 2009; Kelly *et al.* 2015).

The main limitation to developing profitable urchin aquaculture is their low growth rate, requiring five years to reach adult size. A possible strategy to develop a more cost-effective activity is to cultivate adult sea urchins starting from wild individuals with the sole objective of improving their gonad index, avoiding the previous growth stage (Barker 2015).

Another alternative to reduce production costs is to take advantage of the juvenile urchins that grow naturally attached to the longlines, feeding on biofouling, without intervention from the producers, as it was already recorded in blue mussel farms in the Beagle Channel.

Therefore, mussels and urchins can be successfully co-cultured without external food inputs, but there is a balance between controlling biofouling and urchin growth (Sterling *et al.* 2016). To achieve the development of either of these two strategies, it is necessary to carry out studies that evaluate the composition of the biofouling and the biomass of urchins that it could support. Furthermore, it is

recommended to supplement the diet of these urchins with macroalgae from the area, which would increase the system's carrying capacity.

10 Conclusion

Argentina has opportunities to farm an increased number of marine species, many of which are low trophic species with the potential to be combined in IMTA systems. However, despite the long history of attempts to develop marine aquaculture, much work still needs to be done. In this sense, through the development of this report, five major challenges have been detected in promoting and developing IMTA in Argentina:

1. Access to knowledge

A lack of dissemination and even less exploitation of the results of much research and works related to aquaculture development has been detected. This could be reversed through the generation of specific repositories for aquaculture issues.

2. Integrate knowledge on different species.

Despite the available knowledge about new low trophic-level species, their behaviour in an integrated system still needs to be evaluated. The only way to assess the potential of these species to form an integrated system is to promote work among researchers who carry out activities aimed at the development of monospecific production. The human resource potential that Argentina has to develop the IMTA was detected during the ASTRAL Training course “Bases and Concepts for the Development of Aquaculture,” where participants showed knowledge about aquaculture in eight different groups of species (Figure 63). However, none of them have had experience working at IMTA.

Figure 63: Species with which the activities of different aquaculture actors in Argentina are related. Data source: ASTRAL Training course “Bases and Concepts for Aquaculture Development”, May 15-19, 2023. Ushuaia, Argentina.

3. Interdisciplinary and interinstitutional work

It must be highlighted the importance of considering all stakeholders involved in the development of aquaculture. At this initial development stage of IMTA, the intervention of government agencies that promote and facilitate aquaculture is essential, articulating activities with the private, scientific, and academic sectors. In this sense, Argentina has two initiatives whose objectives are precisely to intervene in the coordination of different sectors:

The Aquaculture Strengthening Network (REFACUA¹³ in Spanish): CONICET created the network in 2016. It is conceived from a sustainable and multidisciplinary approach that seeks to transfer available services, knowledge, and technologies to the public sector and the productive sphere, visualizing new alternatives for the development of the activity.

The Marine Fish Farming Project¹⁴, within the framework of of the National Institute for Fisheries Research and Development (INIDEP), created the Mariculture Laboratory in 1994 to develop the technology for the farming of commercially important native marine species such as sea bream (*Pagrus pagrus*), sole (*Paralichthys orbignyanus*), chernia (*Polyprion americanus*), Patagonian king crab (*Lithodes santolla*) and Tehuelche octopus (*Octopus tehuelche*), and lemon fish (*Seriola lalandei*). The latter is the most emblematic since it has reached advanced levels of development and is expected to advance to the pilot-commercial farming stage with the private sector.

4. Pilot-scale facilities

The above only makes sense if Argentina manages to create institutions explicitly designed to develop this activity, with aquaculture facilities designed to evaluate productive trials on a pilot scale. This is crucial to generate spaces for interaction between stakeholders and researchers from different specialities. Since the scientific sector does not have pilot-scale infrastructure installed in the marine environment, improving existing production methods and introducing new approaches like IMTA would be impossible.

¹³ More information about the activities of REFACUA can be found in <https://www.refacua.gob.ar/>.

¹⁴ More information about the activities of the Marine Fish Farming Project can be found in <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/inidep/investigacion-cientifica/direccion-de-informacion-operacion-y-tecnologia/maricultura>.

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13 Annexes

13.1 Annex I: Summary of References about Selected Species

The following tables (Table 26 to Table 29) summarise the bibliographic sources with data on different aspects of the four selected species.

Table 26: Compendium of literature relating to whitebait aquaculture.

Whitebait (<i>Galaxias maculatus</i>)	
Biology	
Growth	3; 10; 13; 12; 25; 26; 30; 52
Feeding	10; 25; 24; 26; 36; 37; 38; 43; 47; 48; 52; 55; 56; 57
Reproduction	3; 17; 18; 19; 20; 34; 43; 46; 51; 52; 53; 54; 56; 57; 59
Cannibalism	1
Life cycle	22; 27; 39; 56
Morphology	2; 21; 33; 41; 42; 44; 45
Migration	11; 21; 34
Production	
Prophylactic treatment	4; 9; 36; 37
Facilities	13; 14; 15; 25; 27; 31; 36; 37; 38; 52; 54; 55; 56
Water Quality	
Salinity	6; 7; 23; 27; 28; 29; 34; 49; 50
Temperature	5; 6; 16; 27; 42; 52
pH	8; 35; 58
Photoperiod	40
Oxygen	32; 49; 55

1: Allibone (2003); 2: Aló *et al.* (2019); 3: Barbee *et al.* (2011); 4: Barile (2003); 5: Barile *et al.* (2013a); 6: Barile *et al.* (2013b); 7: Barile *et al.* (2015); 8: Barile *et al.* (2016a); 9: Barile *et al.* (2016b); 10: Barriga (2006); 11: Barriga *et al.* (2007); 12: Benzie 1968; 13: Bórquez (1996); 14: Bórquez and Dantagnan (1999); 15: Bórquez *et al.* (2007); 16: Boubee *et al.* 1991; 17: Boy *et al.* (2007); 18: Boy *et al.* (2009a); 19: Boy *et al.* (2009b); 20: Boy *et al.* (2023); 21: Campos (1973); 22 : Chapman *et al.* 2006 ; 23: Chessman and Williams (1975); 24: Dantagnan *et al.* (1995); 25: Dantagnan *et al.* (2002); 26: Dantagnan and Lazo (2007); 27: Dantagnan *et al.* (2007); 28: Dantagnan *et al.* (2010); 29: Delgado *et al.* (2023); 30: Eldon (1969); 31: Encina Montoya *et al.* (1999); 32: Encina Montoya *et al.* (2011); 33: Ferriz *et al.* (2001); 34: Hicks *et al.* (2010); 35: Jellyman and Harding (2014); 36: Mardones *et al.* (2008); 37: Mardones and De los Ríos-Escalante (2012); 38: Mitchell (1989); 39: Montoya *et al.* (2012); 40: O'Malley (2023); 41: Pérez (2009); 42: Richardson *et al.* (1994); 43: Rojo *et al.* (2018); 44: Rojo *et al.* (2020); 45: Rojo *et al.* (2020b); 46: Vega-Aguayo (1999); 47: Vega-Aguayo *et al.* (2023); 48: Rodríguez Aguilera and Domke (2006); 49: Urbina (2013); 50: Urbina and Glover (2015); 51: Valdebenito *et al.* (1995); 52: Valdebenito *et al.* (1996); 53: Valdebenito and Vega 2003; 54: Vega *et al.* (1996); 55: Vega (2013^a); 56: Vega *et al.* (2013b); 57: Velásquez 1993; 58: West *et al.* (1997); 59: Wood (2016).

Table 27: Compendium of literature relating to glasswort culture.

Glasswort (<i>Sarcocornia magellanica</i>)	
Biology	
Growth	4; 5; 13; 15; 19; 20
Biomass	4; 12; 19; 21; 22
Physiology	15
Phenology	5; 16; 17
Taxonomy	2; 18
Production	
Farm	1; 3; 5; 7; 8; 11; 14; 15; 17; 19; 20; 21; 22
Bioremediation	4; 9; 10; 12
Integrated system	4
Nutritional composition	1; 5; 6; 7; 10; 11; 14; 19; 20; 21
Seeds selection	22
Ovine production	3; 5; 6; 7
Compost	13
Water Quality	
Salinity	3; 7; 9; 12; 15
Nitrogen removal	4; 9
Phosphorus removal	9
Temperature	5; 6; 13; 20
pH	3; 13
Water quality	4; 17
Soil	3; 6; 7; 9

1: Abdal (2009); 2: Alonso and Crespo (2008); 3: Arce *et al.* (2016); 4: Beyer *et al.* (2021); 5: Bianciotto (2004); 6: Bianciotto *et al.* (2016); 7: Bianciotto *et al.* (2020); 8: Bianciotto *et al.* (2021); 9: Brown *et al.* (1999); 10: Chaturvedi *et al.* (2021); 11: Custodio *et al.* (2021); 12: Ebadi *et al.* (2018); 13: Gibilisco *et al.* (2020); 14: Glenn *et al.* (2013); 15: Maboud (2023); 16: Muñoz *et al.* (2021); 17: Pinheiro *et al.* (2017); 18: Steffen *et al.* (2014); 19: Vater *et al.* (2014); 20: Ventura *et al.* (2011); 21: Ventura and Sagi (2013); 22: Zerai *et al.* (2010).

Table 28: Compendium of literature relating to blue mussel aquaculture.

Blue mussel (<i>Mytilus chilensis</i>)	
Biology	
Growth	10; 14; 19; 23; 29; 30; 33
Feeding	17; 23; 34
Reproduction	16; 17; 21; 32
Fixation	10; 16; 29; 33
Population	17; 20
Size frequency	10
Weight and size	17; 19
Morphology	20; 26; 32; 34
Gonad maturation	14; 21; 25; 29; 30
Taxonomy	15; 19; 21
Production	
Farm	3; 4; 7; 8; 19; 23; 24; 26; 30; 31; 32; 33
Recruitment	10; 12; 16; 23; 27; 30
Aquaculture	4; 14; 18; 22; 23; 31
Legislation	3; 24
Classification zones	3; 7; 4; 24
Performance	23; 29; 30
Environmental	
Distribution	10; 30; 32
Temperature	17; 19; 23; 25; 29; 32
Acidification	13
Red Tide	1; 2; ; 6; 5; 9; 28
Disease	
Reproductive	11

1: Almandoz *et al.* (2011); 2: Almandoz *et al.* (2019); 3: Álvarez *et al.* (2012); 4: Avdelas *et al.* (2021); 5: Benavides *et al.* (1995); 6: Benavides *et al.* (2019); 7: Bertolotti *et al.* (2011); 8: Bertolotti *et al.* (2014); 9: Cadaillon *et al.* (2022); 10: Calcagno *et al.* (2012); 11: Cremonte *et al.* (2011); 12: Curelovich *et al.* (2016); 13 : Diaz *et al.* (2018); 14: Diaz *et al.* (2019); 15: Gardner *et al.* (2021); 16: Isola (2019); 17: Lagos *et al.* (2012); 18: Larraín *et al.* (2018); 19: Marques *et al.* (2020); 20 : Osorio (2002); 21: Oyarzun *et al.* (2011); 22: Oyarzún *et al.* (2016); 23: Pacheco and Olave (2000); 24: Pagani *et al.* (2012); 25: Pino Catalán (2015); 26: Ríos *et al.* (2018); 27: Ruzzante and Guerrero (1982); 28: Schloss *et al.* (2023); 29: Silva and Calvo (1992); 30: Silva (1998); 31: Smaal *et al.* (2019); 32: Tortorelli (1987); 33: Zampatti (2002); 34: Zelaya and Güller (2014).

Table 29: Compendium of literature relating to red sea urchin aquaculture

Red sea urchin (<i>Loxechinus albus</i>)	
Biology	
Distribution	7; 8; 14; 27; 39; 42; 44; 47; 48; 49; 50
Depth	28
Growth	2; 3; 4; 11; 16; 17; 20; 21; 38; 40; 42; 49
Feeding	4; 9; 10; 11; 12; 16; 18; 19; 20; 22; 23; 29; 37; 38; 41; 44; 46; 47; 48; 49; 50
Reproduction	2; 5; 6; 8; 12; 17; 19; 23; 25; 27; 31; 34; 35; 36; 40; 46; 47; 50
Taxonomy	5; 7; 8; 42; 52
Density	14
Morphology	37; 47; 48; 49
Population	4; 7; 14; 44; 48
Size/age distribution	1; 4; 18; 22; 23; 32; 33; 40; 44
Structure	29
Gonad maturation	10; 19; 20; 23; 24; 26; 30; 31; 34; 35; 36; 38; 39; 40
Biodiversity	7; 37
Production	
Aquaculture	5; 7; 8; 9; 11; 12; 13; 17; 33; 39; 41; 42; 48; 49; 50; 51
Fishery	1; 2; 4; 7; 43; 48; 49
Legislation	1; 26; 32; 43; 48; 50
Restocking	1; 16; 17; 48; 49
Water Quality	
Salinity	12; 33
Temperature	12; 15; 24; 33; 35; 51
pH	9; 33
Habitat	1; 5; 8; 28; 39; 42; 45; 47; 48; 49; 50

1: Andrew *et al.* (2002); 2: Antiquero (2017); 3: Antiquero (2021); 4: Arana (2005); 5: Ayerbe *et al.* (2018); 6: Bay-Smith *et al.* (1981); 7: Brogger *et al.* (2013); 8: Bustos and Olave (2001); 9: Cameron and Hinegardner (1974); 10: Cárcamo (2004^a); 11: Cárcamo (2004^b); 12: Cárcamo *et al.* (2005); 13: Cárcamo (2015); 14: Dayton (1985); 15: Dettleff *et al.* (2020); 16: Espinoza and Arraigada (2012); 17: Espinoza and Arraigada (2017); 18: Flores *et al.* (2010); 19: Fraysse and Pérez (2015); 20: Fraysse *et al.* (2015^b); 21: Fraysse *et al.* (2017); 22: Gebauer and Moreno (1995); 23: Incio *et al.* (2020); 24: Lawrence *et al.* (1997); 25: Lovrich *et al.* (2021); 26: Malanga *et al.* (2009); 27: Molinet *et al.* (2012); 28: Moreno and Molinet (2013); 29: Newcombe *et al.* (2012); 30: Olave and Bustos (2001); 31: Oyarzun *et al.* (1999); 32: Palma and Arana (1996); 33: Pérez *et al.* (1995); 34: Pérez *et al.* (2008); 35: Pérez *et al.* (2010); 36: Pérez *et al.* (2011); 37: Pérez *et al.* (2014); 38: Pérez *et al.* (2015); 39: Piérola (2017); 40: Schuhbauer *et al.* (2010); 41: Sonnenholzner-Varas (2021); 42: Sosa (2016); 43: Stefánsson *et al.* (2017); 44: Urrutia *et al.* (1999); 45: Vásquez *et al.* (1984); 46: Vásquez and Buschmann (1997); 47: Vásquez (2007); 48: Vásquez and Donoso (2013); 49: Vásquez (2020); 50: Vidal Santana (2000); 51: Zamora and Stotz (1994).

13.2 Annex II: Summary of Other Species Analysed

13.2.1 Patagonian blenny (*Eleginops maclovinus*) - Fed Aquaculture

Distribution

The Patagonian blenny has a widespread extra-Antarctic distribution, reaching 35°S along the Atlantic coast and 37°S along the Pacific coast (Norman 1937; Andriashev 1965) (Figure 64).

Figure 64: AquaMaps (2019, October). Computer generated distribution maps for *Eleginops maclovinus* (Patagonian blenny), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Biology

Patagonian blenny is the only species belonging to the family Eleginopidae. It is the largest notothenid, with *C. gobio*, after *Dissostichus eleginoides* and *D. mawsoni* (Eastman 2019). It is essentially a coastal and benthic euryhaline species, being able to penetrate rivers and estuaries to reproduce and feed (Lloris and Rucabado 1991).

This species reaches a maximal size of 90 cm (Brickle *et al.* 2005a). *Eleginops maclovinus* presents as part of its reproductive strategy protandric hermaphroditism, when fish reach > 45 cm in length (Calvo *et al.* 1992; Brickle *et al.* 2005b). Nevertheless, the protandrous hermaphrodite condition is not corroborated for all populations, and it is proposed that this mechanism of sex change is more often at high latitudes.

Market

A small but stable market is supported by this species along with its distribution. The main product is frozen both for export and the domestic market, but it is mainly consumed like fresh filet. A small proportion goes to canning (<https://www.inidep.edu.ar>). Currently, artisanal fishers from Tierra del Fuego report an approximate market value of around 5 U\$D/kg (fresh wholesale price). There is no set of commercial sizes, but it is known that consumers prefer large fish above 1000 g in total weight (Fundación Chile 2005).

Fisheries and wild stock status

The fishing effort on this species is mainly found from the Valparaiso region (Chile) up to the south of the country, reaching 158 tons in the year 2020 (SERNAPESCA 2020). Currently, a small artisanal and recreational fishery is being developed with this species in Tierra del Fuego at a very low cost for the fishers since it does not require large investments in infrastructure for its capture. These factors highlight this species as economically important at the regional level. Nevertheless, there are no reports about the wild stock status.

Aquaculture

Significant progress has been made in rearing Patagonian blenny in captivity, but there are still many limitations to developing its commercial aquaculture. The main one is the lack of knowledge to manage reproduction in captivity and establish an efficient system for incubation. The common-reared system consists of land-based tanks with flow-through water (Sa *et al.* 2014; Oyarzún *et al.* 2020). On the other side, there are several advancements in sperm collection and manipulation (Contreras *et al.* 2017; Valdebenito *et al.* 2017; Ulloa-Rodríguez *et al.* 2018; 2019), food needs (Sa *et al.* 2014, Oyarzun *et al.* 2019), effects of temperature and salinity on growth and feeding (Vanella *et al.* 2012; Vargas-Chacoff *et al.* 2015). To obtain gametes, the urogenital pore is disinfected with alcohol and slight abdominal, pressure is applied. The semen is then collected with a 5 ml syringe. The semen extracted is only used if it presents maximum motility and when the volume obtained is greater than 1 ml (Valdebenito *et al.* 2018). The eggs are incubated in Zoug jar type.

Summary of Main Characteristics

Table 30 to Table 33 show biological parameters relevant to aquaculture, water quality needs, parameters related to the performance of the Patagonian blenny in captivity and feeding tests in aquaculture.

Table 30. Main biological parameters of Patagonian blenny relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Environment type	Coast, euryhaline. Males between 1-4 years are found in estuaries. Females between 5-8 years are found in the open sea.	Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006
Depth	0-250 m.	Eastman 2017
Max. length males	45 cm.	Calvo <i>et al.</i> 1992; Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006
Max. length females	80 cm.	Eastman 2019
Max. weight males	1,001 - 1,155 g.	Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006; Gastaldi <i>et al.</i> 2009
Max. weight females	5,722 - 7,239 g.	Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006; Gastaldi <i>et al.</i> 2009
Max. age males	5-6 years.	Brickle <i>et al.</i> 2005b; Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006
Max. age females	11 years.	Brickle <i>et al.</i> 2005b
Length – Weight relationship males	$W = 9.8E^{-03}TL^{3.03}$ $W = 9.8E^{-06}TL^{3.1889}$	Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006; Gastaldi <i>et al.</i> 2009
Length – Weight relationship females	$W = 9.8E^{-03}TL^{3.03}$ $W = 9.8E^{-06}TL^{3.1889}$	Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006; Gastaldi <i>et al.</i> 2009
Growth curve	$L_t = 124.41(1 - e^{-0.14/year(t-0.01years)})$ at 4-11°C.	Brickle <i>et al.</i> 2005b
Reproduction type	Protandrous hermaphrodite, intersex at 41-45 cm length. Batch spawner.	Calvo <i>et al.</i> 1992; Brickle <i>et al.</i> 2005b
Spawning season	September – December.	Brickle <i>et al.</i> 2005b
Maturation age males	30 cm.	Gosztonyi 1980; Brickle <i>et al.</i> 2005b
Maturation age females	A50 4.5 years (CI: 4.0–6.2 years).	Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006
Maturation length males	Data not available or not determined.	
Maturation length females	L_{50} 35.7 cm TL (CI: 29.3–39.0 cm).	Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006
Type of eggs	Pelagic.	Brickle <i>et al.</i> 2005b
Egg size	1.0 - 1.2 mm.	Brickle <i>et al.</i> 2005b; Valdebenito <i>et al.</i> 2018
Fecundity	331 – 1394 eggs/g.	Gosztonyi 1980; Brickle <i>et al.</i> 2005b
Newly larvae weight	Data not available or not determined.	
Newly larvae length	Post-larvae 20 mm.	Gosztonyi 1980
Larvae feeding habits	Data not available or not determined.	
Juvenile feeding habits	Data not available or not determined.	
Adults feeding habits	Omnivorous. Benthic organisms such as polychaetes and crustaceans.	Guzmán and Campodónico 1973; Pequeño 1979; Isla and San Román 1995; Pavés <i>et al.</i> 2005; Licandeo <i>et al.</i> 2006

Table 31: Main water quality conditions need for Patagonian blenny farm.

Characteristics	Description	References
Salinity	15-31 psu.	Vargas-Chacoff et al. 2015b; Oyarzún et al. 2020
Temperature	10-20°C.	Vanella et al. 2012; Oyarzún et al. 2020; 2021)
Photoperiod	12L:12D.	Oyarzún et al. 2020
pH	7.6-8.0.	Mardones et al. 2019
Ammonium	LC50-96h: 0.413mg NH ₃ /L.	Mardones et al. 2019
Nitrite	Data not available or not determined	
O ₂	9.2-10.4 ppm, > 80% saturation	Oyarzún et al. 2020

Table 32: Main parameters related to the performance of the Patagonian blenny in captivity.

Characteristics	Description	References
Initial larval density	Data not available or not determined.	
Rearing density	3 - 12 Kg/m ³ - 15 - 60 Kg/m ³ .	Martínez 2013; Oyarzún et al. 2019; 2020
Fertilization rate	Data not available or not determined	
Hatching rate	Data not available or not determined	
Larvae survival	Data not available or not determined	
Juveniles survival	100% at 10, 15 and 20°C. 36% at 25°C	Oyarzún et al. 2021
Adults survival	Data not available or not determined	
Post spawning survival	Data not available or not determined	
SGR	0.37 (feed ratio 1%); 0.42 (feed ratio 2%); 0.48 (feed ratio 4%); 0.13 (stock density 3kg/m ³); 0.12 (stock density 6kg/m ³); 0.09 (stock density 12kg/m ³); - 0.04 (stock density 24kg/m ³).	Llancabure 2011; Vargas-Chacoff et al. 2015; Oyarzún 2019; Oyarzún et al. 2020
FCR	3.93 (feed ratio 1%); 7.23 (feed ratio 2%); 13.18 (feed ratio 4%).	Llancabure 2011; Oyarzún et al. 2019
Prophylaxis during incubation	Data not available or not determined.	
Incubation light	Dark	Valdebenito et al. 2018
Incubation temperature	10.5 °C	Valdebenito et al. 2018
Incubation salinity	Data not available or not determined.	
Thermal Units	Data not available or not determined.	

Table 33: Summary of Patagonian blenny feeding tests in aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Time until first feeding	Data not available or not determined.	
Larvae	Data not available or not determined.	
Juveniles	30-35% Protein + 15% Lipids (Fish meal 27.5%, starch 21%, wheat meal 18%, fish oil 10.5%, vitamins and minerals 1.5%, NaH ₂ PO ₄ 1%, chromium oxide 0.5%). BioMar 522: 50.5% protein, 20% lipids, 1.2 % raw fibre, 10% moisture and 12 % ash. Skretting Nutrece Defense 100TM, 48 % protein, 22 % fat, 13 % carbohydrate, 8 % moisture and 8.5 % ash.	Llancabure 2011; Vargas-Chacoff et al. 2015; Oyarzún et al. 2019
On growing	BioMar, Golden Optima 522: 50.5% protein, 20% lipids, 1.2 % fibre, 10% moisture, 12 % ash.	Oyarzún et al. 2020
Protein requirement	About 30%.	Sa et al. 2014
Ongrowing feeding ratio	1-2-4 %.	Oyarzún et al. 2019
Cannibalism	Data not available or not determined.	

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13.2.2 Patagonian Red Octopus (*Enteroctopus megalocyathus*) - Fed Aquaculture

Distribution

Patagonian Red Octopus inhabits cold waters from the intertidal to ~240 m depth at the south of 42°S in both the Atlantic and Pacific oceans of South America (Figure 65) (Ré 1998a; Chong Lay-Son *et al.* 2001; Ortiz *et al.* 2006; Ortíz 2009; IFOP 2010; Uriarte and Farías 2014).

Figure 65: AquaMaps (2019, October). Computer generated distribution maps for *Enteroctopus megalocyathus* (Patagonian giant octopus), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Biology

The red octopus is a semelparous benthic species that can reach 1 meter in length and weigh up to 7 kg. Sexual maturity for both females and males has been estimated at 135.4-158.5 mm of dorsal mantle length (Chong Lay-Son *et al.* 2001; Ortiz *et al.* 2011). In Chilean waters, the breeding starts in winter reaches the maximum in spring and continues during the summer (Uriarte and Farías 2014), while in north Argentinean Patagonia, it is likely to encompass nearly all year round. Moreover, evidence suggests that the main reproductive process occurs at depth (Ortiz and Ré 2019), while in shallow waters (up to 25 m), mating takes place from mid-spring to mid-summer, and spawning occurs during summer-winter. Females attach egg strings (~1300 eggs per clutch) to the roofs of holes and crevices and care for them during ~6 months (embryogenesis period) until paralarvae hatching occurs (Ortiz *et al.* 2006; Ortiz *et al.* 2011).

Fisheries and wild stock status

The red octopus is harvested mainly by divers on shallow waters or hooks to capture animals from rocky intertidal shores along the Patagonian seacoast (Ré 1998a; Ortiz *et al.* 2006; Rocha and Vega 2003). In Argentina, the small-scale fishery of red octopus is unregulated and concentrated at the north Patagonian seacoast. The fishing activity is performed mainly from March to November when octopus abundance is highest (Ré 1998a; Ré 1998b), and captures are estimated at 9-15 tons per year (Cinti *et al.* 2003; Ré 1998a). In Chile, fisheries are regulated by a banned period during reproduction season from mid-November to mid-March, and it is only allowed to land animals >1 kg (Chong Lay-Son *et al.* 2001; Rocha and Vega 2003). Chilean captures varied between 200 and 500 tons annually, peaking at 1700 tons in 2008 (Rocha and Vega 2003; Uriarte and Farías 2014 and cities therein). In 2008, the *E. megalocyathus* fishery was banned for three years in Chile, making their aquaculture an important issue (Uriarte *et al.* 2011).

Market

In Argentina and Chile, ~90% of the red octopus captures are commercialized frozen. In Chile, most production is exported at values ranging between 4.5 and 7.3 U\$S/kg (Molinet Flores *et al.* 2018). In contrast, the rest of the production is commercialized as gourmet seafood, either fresh or canned, with values extremely variable between 2.6 U\$S/kg (ECOS, 2021) and 48.2 U\$S/kg (<https://geomar.cl>; <https://frescosur.cl>). In contrast, in the north Argentinean Patagonia, the red octopus is commercialized mainly at fish stores near the fishing areas, and its prices vary between 11 and 15 U\$S/kg (Bariffuzza and Fiedorowicz Kowal, 2020). Particularly in Tierra del Fuego, no developed market exists, and the sporadic red octopus captures are sold to specific local restaurants as a gourmet delicacy (F. Valdéz per.com.).

Aquaculture

During the last few years, studies have focused on developing red octopus' culture to explore the possibility of supporting its production and reducing the fishing pressure.

Experimental evidence indicates that the production of juveniles is possible in a period of 12 months. This process includes broodstock conditioning, egg-laying, embryo incubation and paralarval rearing until early juveniles, followed by a period of 9 months to grow juveniles of 100 g until they reach a commercial size of 2.5 - 3.0kg (Uriarte *et al.* 2019). However, it is still necessary to determine the growth rate of early juveniles (from 0.4 to 100 g) to establish the total time needed for cultivation

until reaching the legal size recommended of 1,200 g body weight (Uriarte and Fariás 2014 and cites therein).

This species has complex reproductive behavior (Gutiérrez *et al.* 2012), with courtship prior to mating and the eggs incubated with maternal care (Uriarte *et al.* 2014).

Summary of Main Characteristics

Table 34 to Table 37 show biological parameters relevant to aquaculture, water quality needs, parameters related to the performance of the Patagonian red octopus in captivity and feeding tests in aquaculture.

Table 34: Main biological parameters of Patagonian red octopus relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Environment type	Merobenthic.	Uriarte and Fariás 2014
Depth	Intertidal to ~240 m depth.	Ortiz 2006; Uriarte and Fariás 2014
Max. weight	4 - 7 kg.	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 2006; Ortiz <i>et al.</i> 2006; IFOP 2010; Ortiz 2013; Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2014
Max. age males	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. age females	Data not available or not determined.	
Length – Weight relationship males	BW = 0.01ML ^{2.28} , BW: body weight; ML: mantle length.	Ortiz and Re 2019
Length – Weight relationship females	BW = 0.008ML ^{2.40} , BW: body weight; ML: mantle length.	Ortiz and Re 2019
Growth curve	Data not available or not determined.	
Reproduction type	Semelparous.	Ortiz 2009; Uriarte and Fariás 2014
Spawning season	Mid-spring to mid-summer.	
Maturation age males	Data not available or not determined.	
Maturation age females	Data not available or not determined.	
Maturation length males	135.4-158.5 mm of mantle length.	Chong <i>et al.</i> 2001; Ortiz <i>et al.</i> 2011
Maturation length females	135.4-158.5 mm of mantle length.	Chong <i>et al.</i> 2001; Ortiz <i>et al.</i> 2011
Type of eggs	Benthic or pelagic depending on egg morphometry. Centrolecithal, consisting mainly of yolk with corion that forms the stalk in the vegetal pole.	Ortiz <i>et al.</i> 2006; Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2014
Egg size	Length: 9.5–12 mm. Width 3–4.7 mm.	Ortiz <i>et al.</i> 2006; Ortiz 2009
Fecundity	1469–1532 eggs/spawn; 2500–2900 oocytes/female. 774- 924 eggs/kg females.	Ré 1998b; Ortiz <i>et al.</i> 2006; Ortiz 2009; Fariás <i>et al.</i> 2011; Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2014
Newly paralarvae weight	90 - 150 mg.	Ortiz <i>et al.</i> 2006
Newly paralarvae length	7-9.5 mm TL.	Ortiz <i>et al.</i> 2006
Paralarvae feeding habits	Fed on zooplankton.	Fariás <i>et al.</i> 2016
Juvenile feeding habits	Crustacean, fish, bivalves, other octopuses, cannibalism.	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 2006; Ibáñez and Chong 2008
Adults feeding habits	Crustacean, fish, bivalves, other octopuses, cannibalism.	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 2006; Ibáñez and Chong 2008

Table 35: Main parameters related to the performance of the Patagonian red octopus in captivity.

Characteristics	Description	References
Fertilization rate	Data not available or not determined	
Hatching rate	15%	Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2014
Paralarvae survival	<20%; 27-80%	Farías <i>et al.</i> 2016; Espinoza <i>et al.</i> 2020
Juvenile survival	Data not available or not determined.	
Adult survival	Data not available or not determined.	
IGR	1.96%-0.49%	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 2006
SGR	1.5%/day fed with fresh fish; 0.3% fed with paste crabs	Farías <i>et al.</i> 2010
Prophylaxis during incubation	Data not available or not determined.	
Incubation light	Darkness	Ortiz <i>et al.</i> 2006
Incubation temperature	12 - 14°C	Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2014; Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2016
Incubation salinity	Data not available or not determined.	
Thermal units	150 days	Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2008

Table 36: Main water quality conditions need for Patagonian blenny farm.

Characteristics	Description	References
Initial larval density	10-15 paralarvae/L.	Espinoza <i>et al.</i> 2020; 2021
Rearing density	Data not available or not determined.	
Salinity	30 ppm.	Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2014
Temperature	10 - 12°C.	Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2014; 2018
Photoperiod	10L:14D; <50 lux. 12L:12D; Natural photoperiod, with reduced illumination.	Farías <i>et al.</i> 2010 Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2018; Espinoza <i>et al.</i> 2021
pH	Data not available or not determined	
Ammonium	Data not available or not determined	
Nitrite	Data not available or not determined	
O ₂	6-8 mg/L.	Uriarte and Farías 2014

Table 37: Summary of Patagonian red octopus feeding tests in aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Paralarvae	Artemia; artemia enrichments: <i>Nannochloropsis</i> sp; Ori-gold (Skretting); and LC60 (Phosphotek).	Espinoza <i>et al.</i> 2020; Farías <i>et al.</i> 2020
Juveniles	Formulated diets of crab paste and a mixture of freeze-dried meals of crab and squid.	(Martínez-Montaña <i>et al.</i> 2017
Ongrowing	Crustaceans <i>Petrolisthes</i> sp., <i>Acanthocyclus hassleri</i> and <i>Hemigrapsus crenulatus</i> . Fresh crabs, squids, and fish at a feed ratio of 5% body weight/day.	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 2006; Farías <i>et al.</i> 2010; Uriarte <i>et al.</i> 2014
Cannibalism	During early paralarvae rearing.	Espinoza <i>et al.</i> 2019

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13.2.3 Green Sea Urchin (*Arbacia dufresnii*) - Organic Extractive Aquaculture (Sedimented POM Feeders)

Distribution

The green sea urchin *Arbacia dufresnii* is an abundant species that inhabits the southern tip of South America (Figure 66). *A. dufresnii* can be found from Río de la Plata (35°S, Southwest Atlantic) to Puerto Montt (42°S, Southeast Pacific). Its distribution includes the Malvinas Islands, at a depth ranging from 0 to 315m (Bernasconi 1966; Brogger *et al.* 2013).

Figure 66: AquaMaps (2019, October). Computer generated distribution maps for *Arbacia dufresnii* (green sea urchin), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Biology

Depending on the environment and food availability, the green sea urchin can be considered omnivorous, herbivorous, or carnivorous (Zárate *et al.* 2016).

The reproductive cycle of this species was studied in populations from Nuevo Gulf and San Jorge Gulf, showing an annual cycle in both populations. Gonad development proceeds through pregametic (austral autumn, May), growth (austral winter, July, and August), premature and mature stages (austral spring, September to November), with an extended spawning season during the late spring and summer (two partial spawning stages, December to February) and a reabsorption stage at the end of the summer (March) (Epherra *et al.* 2015).

Market

Although this species doesn't have gastronomic potential, its aquaculture development in Argentina has advanced from the obtaining of pharmaceutical (including COVID-19 treatments), nutraceutical and cosmetic products developed by Erisea SA, a Technology Base Company of CONICET (Barbieri *et al.* 2020; Rubilar *et al.* 2021).

Fisheries and wild stock status

Data about fisheries and wild stock status are not available, and there are no specific regulations about fishing quotes.

Aquaculture

While it is possible to find several ongoing efforts to produce or increase the production of roe for human consumption to meet the global food demand, there are few aquaculture initiatives aimed to obtain nutraceutical products from sea urchin eggs active principles (spinochromes, astaxanthin, amino acids, fatty acids, choline, phospholipids, vitamins, and minerals) (Leal *et al.* 2016). In Argentina, the spin-off Erisea¹⁵, located in Puerto Madryn City (Chubut, Argentina), is cultivating *A. dufresnii* with the aim to produce active principle and biologically active additives based on sea urchin eggs to improve human health (Rubilar and Cardozo 2021). Under the interest of aquaculture, there is information on several population parameters that give an idea of the growth of the species (Epherra *et al.* 2017), the effect of light on gamete production and maturity (Sepúlveda *et al.* 2021), temperature effect on the development of embryos and larvae (Pía-Fernández *et al.* 2021). Balanced foods' ingestion, absorption and assimilation efficiency have also been studied (Rubilar *et al.* 2016).

Detailed protocols have been developed to obtain gametes and subsequent fertilization (Chaar *et al.* 2021). Briefly, to obtain gametes, the mature females and males are injected in the peristomal membrane with 0.3% of 0.55 M KCl and 50.000 eggs/ml are mixed with sperm diluted 1:100.000 v/v and incubated with gentle aeration (Ettensohn 2017; Fernández *et al.* 2019).

¹⁵ More information about this company can be found in <https://promarineantioxidants.com/>.

Summary of Main Characteristics

Table 38 to Table 41 show biological parameters relevant to aquaculture, water quality needs, parameters related to the performance of the green sea urchin in captivity and feeding tests in aquaculture.

Table 38: Main biological parameters of Patagonian red octopus relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Environment type	Benthonic, areas with coarse sediments (sand) and hard substrates.	Brogger <i>et al.</i> 2013; Epherra 2016
Depth	0 to 315m.	Vásquez <i>et al.</i> 1984; Zaixso and Lizarralde 2000; Brogger <i>et al.</i> 2013
Max. weight males	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. weight females	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. age males	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. age females	Data not available or not determined.	
Diameter – Weight relationship males	Data not available or not determined.	
Diameter – Weight relationship females	Data not available or not determined.	
Growth curve	Data not available or not determined.	
Reproduction type	Synchronic	Brogger <i>et al.</i> 2010
Spawning season	A first peak in October-November (spring) and a major one in January-February (summer).	Brogger <i>et al.</i> 2004; 2010
Maturation age males	Data not available or not determined.	
Maturation age females	Data not available or not determined.	
Maturation size males	Data not available or not determined.	
Maturation size females	Data not available or not determined.	
Type of eggs	Isolecithal.	Ettensohn 2017
Egg size	Diameter: 87.1 μm , with a jelly coat of 12.7 μm . Diameter: 62 μm .	Brogger <i>et al.</i> 2010; Fernández <i>et al.</i> 2019
Fecundity	Up to 3,500,000 eggs/female.	Sepúlveda <i>et al.</i> 2021
Larval stages	Planktotrophic.	Brogger <i>et al.</i> 2010
Newly larvae weight	Data not available or not determined.	
Newly larvae length	60 - 100 μm .	Fernández <i>et al.</i> 2021
Larvae feeding habits	Phytoplanktonic.	Strathmann 1971
Juvenile feeding habits	Primarily carnivorous, but also macroalgae.	Vásquez <i>et al.</i> 1984; Penchaszadeh and Lawrence 1999
Adults feeding habits	Mainly carnivorous, but also macroalgae.	Vásquez <i>et al.</i> 1984; Penchaszadeh and Lawrence 1999

Table 39: Main water quality conditions need for green sea urchin farm.

Characteristics	Description	References
System	Land-based, RAS.	Rubilar <i>et al.</i> 2016
Initial larval density	5 larvae/ml.	Chaar <i>et al.</i> 2021
Rearing density	Data not available or not determined.	
Salinity	33-34 ppm.	Ancin <i>et al.</i> 2021
Temperature	13-15°C.	Ancin <i>et al.</i> 2021
Photoperiod	12L:12D.	Ancin <i>et al.</i> 2021; Sepúlveda <i>et al.</i> 2021
pH	7.8 - 8.0.	Catarino <i>et al.</i> 2011
Ammonium	Data not available or not determined.	
Nitrite	Data not available or not determined.	
O ₂	Data not available or not determined.	

Table 40: Main parameters related to the performance of the Patagonian red octopus in captivity.

Characteristics	Description	References
Fertilization rate	99%; 92.4% (17°C) - 88.2% (12°C).	Fernández <i>et al.</i> 2019; 2021
Hatching rate	Data not available or not determined.	
Larvae survival	54% at 14 days post fertilization.	Chaar <i>et al.</i> 2021
Juvenile survival	Data not available or not determined.	
Adult survival	83.3% (13°C); 66.7% (15°C); 41.7% (17°C).	Ancin <i>et al.</i> 2021
SGR	Data not available or not determined.	
FCR	2.85 - 3.16.	Rubilar <i>et al.</i> 2016
Prophylaxis during incubation	Sea water filtered up to 1 um and sterilized with UV light.	Chaar <i>et al.</i> 2021
Incubation light	Data not available or not determined.	
Incubation temperature	12 - 17°C.	Fernández <i>et al.</i> 2021
Incubation salinity	34-35 ppm.	Chaar <i>et al.</i> 2021
Thermal Units	48hs at 17°C.	Fernández <i>et al.</i> 2021

Table 41: Summary of green sea urchin feeding tests in aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Larvae	Daily with mix of <i>Tetraselmis suecica</i> and <i>Isochrysis galbana</i> 10.000 - 40.000 cells/larvae.	Chaar <i>et al.</i> 2021
Juveniles	Data not available or not determined.	
On growing	Formulated by Texas A&M AgriLife Research. Ingredients: Wheatstarch 18.04%, Soy protein 7.70%, Casein 4.00%, Cellulose 3.00%, Beta carotene 1.00%, Vitamin premix 0.60%, Mineral premix 17.73%, Other marine ingredients 31.00%, Other nonmarine ingredients 16.90%. Composition: Lipids 7.38%, Soluble protein 17.02%, Insoluble protein 2.3%, Carbohydrates 37.75%, Ash 32.22%, UOM 3.33%. Formulated by the Group for Research and Technological Development in Aquaculture and Fisheries (GIDTAP) at the National Technological University (UTN-FRCH): Wheat Starch 4%, Cornstarch 19%, Soy protein 11%, Lecithin 0.6%, Marine Ingredients 36%, Non-Marine Ingredients 28.2%, Vitamin premix 0.6%, Minerals premix 0.6%.	Rubilar <i>et al.</i> 2016; Sepúlveda <i>et al.</i> 2021
Cannibalism	Data not available or not determined.	

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13.2.4 Southern King Crab (*Lithodes santolla*) and False King Crab (*Paralomis granulosa*)

Distribution

South of 40°S, the Southern king crab *Lithodes santolla* and the False king crab *Paralomis granulosa* inhabit the Atlantic and Pacific coasts of South America (Figure 67 and Figure 68), from the intertidal to deep waters (Lovrich and Tapella 2014 and cites therein).

Figure 67: AquaMaps (2019, October). Computer generated distribution maps for *Lithodes santolla* (Southern king crab), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Figure 68: AquaMaps (2019, October). Computer generated distribution maps for *Paralomis granulosa* (softshell red crab), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Biology

The maximum size of *L. santolla* is around 180 mm of carapace length (CL), and from 110 mm CL, it weighs more than 1kg (Boschi et al. 1984). In contrast, *P. granulosa* reaches 115 mm CL and a male of

100 mm CL weighs ~700 g (Lovrich 1991). The growth of both species is slow, and they attain sexual maturity at advanced ages. *L. santolla*'s females mate at ~six years old when they reach gonadal maturity (~70 mm CL), whereas males do it later (~6-7 years old) once they attain morphometric maturity at 75-92 mm CL (Lovrich et al. 2002; Lovrich and Tapella 2014). *P. granulosa*'s females and males reproduce at ~10 years old when they attain gonadal (61 mm CL) and morphometric (57 mm CL) maturity, respectively (Lovrich and Tapella 2014). The reproductive cycle of *L. santolla* and *P. granulosa* is annual and biennial, respectively. In the Beagle Channel, the mating occurs in November for *P. granulosa* (Lovrich and Vinuesa 1993) and in December for *L. santolla* (Lovrich et al. 2002). After mating, females carry the eggs under their abdomen during embryogenesis. In *L. santolla*, larval hatching occurs during September - October, 9-10 months after mating (Vinuesa 1984), whereas in *P. granulosa* occurs in June - August, 18-22 months after mating (Lovrich and Vinuesa 1993). Fecundity, as several eggs per brood, is almost three times higher in *L. santolla* ranging between 5,000 to 30,000 eggs/female (Lovrich 1997), than in *P. granulosa*, ranging from 800 to 10,000 eggs/female (Lovrich and Vinuesa 1993). Larval development in both species is endotrophic (Lovrich et al. 2003; Calcagno et al. 2003), and it comprises two and three Zoea stages for *P. granulosa* and *L. santolla*, respectively, and one Megalopa (Campodonico 1971; Campodonico and Guzmán 1981). All larval stages are benthic, particularly in *L. santolla*, and prefer complex habitats like broken shells or gravel, where they can avoid predators and cannibalistic interactions (Tapella et al. 2012; Sotelano et al. 2012; 2016). Early life stages of both species occur at depths <40m (Tapella and Lovrich 2006), and they have been found at low densities associated with the kelp forest *Macrocystis pyrifera* (Brusca et al. 2000; Alonso and Tapella 2017). Although no formal study on adult displacement exists, an apparent seasonal migration to shallow and deeper waters during summer and winter, respectively, has been reported (Lovrich and Vinuesa 2016).

Market

The southern king crab *L. santolla* has always been commercially preferred over the false king crab *P. granulosa* mainly because of its larger size and delicate flavour (Lorenzo et al. 2021). This has caused the commercial value of *L. santolla* to almost double the value of *P. granulosa*. Thus, the constant demand for *L. santolla* from international markets has promoted that most of the production from Argentina or Chile is exported as clusters of frozen legs. Particularly, during the last 10 years, Argentina has exported between 387 and 2529 tn/year of clutch frozen legs from the offshore fishery of the San Jorge Gulf at values of 6-17 U\$S/kg (<https://www.argentina.gob.ar/agricultura>). The rest of the production is commercialized in the regional -Buenos Aires and Santiago cities- and local

markets near the fisheries areas. In Argentina and Chile, the price of the frozen vacuum-packed muscle of legs of *P. granulosa* and *L. santolla* varied between 31 and 55-70 U\$S/kg, respectively (<https://emporioaustral.com/>; <https://www.mellinoacasa.com.ar/>). In Tierra del Fuego, Argentina, the local production of both species is mainly sold to the restaurants to supply the international tourism demand and processed as souvenirs for their relevance in local gastronomy and tourism. (<https://www.ahumaderoushuaia.com.ar/>).

Fisheries and wild stock status

During the last century, the southern king crab and the false king crab have supported profitable fisheries along both the Atlantic and Pacific coasts. Captures are performed by baited traps, which are usually anchored at depths of 10-100 m and recovered 2-3 days later. The fishery is regulated by the so-called three "S" rule; Size, Sex and Season (Guzmán *et al.* 2004; Lovrich 1997; Lovrich and Tapella 2014). Thus, only males (>112 and >74 mm CL for *L. santolla* and *P. granulosa*, respectively) are allowed to be landed in Argentina, all females have to be returned to the sea, and some seasonal bans are defined for each species (Lovrich and Tapella 2014). Particularly, the Argentinean king crab fishery began during the 1930s in the Beagle Channel waters (Vinuesa *et al.* 1996) and reached its maximum yields (~200-300 tons/year) during the 1970s and 1980s. Then, *L. santolla* captures declined and promoted the extraction of *P. granulosa* and the development of the *L. santolla* fishery off San Jorge Gulf (Lovrich and Tapella 2014). As landings of *L. santolla* were diminishing, the captures of *P. granulosa* increased to their maximum values (~300 tn/year) during the 1990s, and they remained constant for almost 15 years. Since then, landings of both species have fluctuated around 30-50 tn/year (Lovrich and Tapella 2014; Narvarte *et al.* 2022). Despite management restrictions, the relative abundance of *L. santolla* in the Beagle Channel is about nine times less than in the 1970s, and the potential offspring production is diminished since only ~30% of mature females are found carrying eggs (Di Salvatore *et al.* 2020; Lovrich and Tapella 2014; Lovrich *et al.* 2017). In contrast, *P. granulosa* seems not to be affected by the fishery (Lovrich and Tapella 2014).

The current (years 2021-2022) total allowable catch of southern king crab in Tierra del Fuego Province is 50 tn/year in both Atlantic and Beagle Channel Coast (Acta Consejo Federal Pesquero Nº 25/2021).

Aquaculture

Since the Southern king crab population in the Beagle Channel has not shown any sign of recovery during the last two decades, studies have been focused on the development of early life stages in order to promote the wild stock enhancement program with juveniles. Thus, a complementary methodology of larval and juvenile cultures at hatchery and sea has been successfully explored (Tapella *et al.* 2009; Sotelano *et al.* 2018). Nowadays, it is possible to produce juveniles of ~3-6 mm CL in seven months (Sotelano *et al.* 2018, Sotelano *et al.* 2022). In contrast, the culture of the False king crab has not been explored, probably due to its relatively stable fishery stocks (Lovrich and Tapella 2104 and cites therein).

Summary of Main Characteristics

Table 42 to Table 46 show biological parameters relevant to aquaculture, water quality needs, parameters related to the performance of the southern king crab and false southern king crab in captivity and feeding tests in aquaculture.

Table 42. Main biological parameters of the southern king crab relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Environment type	Adults: soft and hard bottoms, juveniles' complex substrates <40 m depth frequently associated with holdfasts of <i>Macrocystis</i> sp.	Tapella <i>et al.</i> 2006; 2012
Depth	0-700 m	Vinuesa 1991
Max. weight males	6 kg	Lovrich 1997
Max. weight females	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. age males	15 years	Lovrich and Tapella 2014
Max. age females	15 years	Lovrich and Tapella 2014
Length – Weight relationship males	$Y=0.0006 X^{3.0145}$	Iorio <i>et al.</i> 2008b
Length – Weight relationship females	$Y=0.0006 X^{3.0226}$	Iorio <i>et al.</i> 2008b
Reproduction type	Sexual / spermatophores	Vinuesa and Labal 1998
Spawning season	September –December	Vinuesa, 1984; Vinuesa and Balzi 2002; Lovrich <i>et al.</i> 2002; Balzi 2006
Maturation age males	5-6 years (morphometric maturity)	Lovrich 1997
Maturation age females	5 years	Vinuesa 1984; Lovrich <i>et al.</i> 2002
Maturation length males	92,6 mm (morphometric maturity)	Lovrich 1997
Maturation length females	65-75 mm (gonadal maturity)	Vinuesa 1984
Type of eggs	Data not available or not determined.	
Egg size	3.6 mm ³	Diaz 2013
Fecundity	$\log F = 2.79 \log CL - 1.42$; $\log F = 3.326 \log CL - 2.468$; 5000-32000 eggs/female	Vinuesa 1982; Lovrich 1997; Di Salvatore <i>et al.</i> 2020
Embryogenesis	9-10 months	Vinuesa 1984
Larval stages	3 Zoea stages, 1 megalopa stage	Campodónico 1971
Newly larvae weight	Data not available or not determined.	
Newly larvae length	3.75 mm length, 1.88 mm width	Campodonico 1971
Larvae feeding habits	Lecitotrophic	Lovrich <i>et al.</i> 2003
Juvenile feeding habits	Data not available or not determined.	
Adults feeding habits	Opportunistic/generalist.	Comoglio and Amin 1996

Table 43: Main biological parameters of the false southern king crab relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Environment type	Adults: soft and hard bottoms, juveniles' holdfasts of <i>Macrocystis</i> sp. (Marine benthic fauna).	Lovrich and Tapella 2014
Depth	10-100 m.	Lovrich and Tapella 2014
Max. length males	115 mm CL.	Lovrich 1991
Max. length females	90 mm.	Lovrich 1991
Max. weight males	700 g.	Lovrich 1991
Max. weight females	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. age males	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. age females	~26 years.	Lovrich 1991
Length – Weight relationship males	$Y = 0.0003 X^{3.2035}$.	Iorio <i>et al.</i> 2008a
Length – Weight relationship females	$Y = 0.0014 X^{2.8097}$.	Iorio <i>et al.</i> 2008a
Reproduction type	Sexual – spermatophores.	
Reproductive season	November.	Lovrich 2002
Hatching season	June-August, could extend until October.	Lovrich and Vinuesa 1993; Iorio <i>et al.</i> 2008b
Maturation age males	8-10 years.	Lovrich and Tapella 2014
Maturation age females	8-10 years.	Lovrich and Tapella 2014
Maturation length males	57 mm (morphometric maturity).	Lovrich and Vinuesa 1993
Maturation length females	61 mm (gonadal maturity).	Lovrich and Vinuesa 1993
Egg size	1.9 mm.	Lovrich and Tapella 2004
Embryogenesis	18-22 months.	Lovrich and Vinuesa 1993
Relative fecundity	$\log F = 2.61 \log CL - 1.21$; 800-10000 eggs/female.	Lovrich and Vinuesa 1993
Larval stages	2 Zoeas, 1 megalopa.	Vinuesa <i>et al.</i> 1989
Newly larvae weight	Data not available or not determined.	
Newly larvae length	Data not available or not determined.	
Time until first exogenous feeding	47 days at 6°C.	Anger <i>et al.</i> 2003
Larvae feeding habits	Lecithotrophic.	Calcagno <i>et al.</i> 2003
Juvenile feeding habits	Molluscs (lower frequencies), algae, crustaceans, foraminiferans, hydrozoans, bryozoans, echinoderms.	Comoglio and Amin 1999
Adults feeding habits	Molluscs (higher frequencies), algae, crustaceans, foraminiferans, hydrozoans, bryozoans, echinoderms.	Comoglio and Amin 1999

Table 44: Main water quality conditions need for the false southern king crab farm.

Characteristics	Description	References
System	Plankton-kraisel, pvc bottom-meshed	Tapella <i>et al.</i> 2019
Initial larval density	600 – 3600 larvae/plankton-kraisel.	Tapella <i>et al.</i> 2019
Rearing density	Data not available or not determined.	
Salinity	31 ± 1 psu.	Sotelano <i>et al.</i> 2018
Temperature	6 -15°C.	Sotelano <i>et al.</i> 2018
Photoperiod	12:12-h light/dark.	Anger <i>et al.</i> 2004
pH	8.1 ± 0.3.	Sotelano <i>et al.</i> 2018
Ammonium	<0.25 mg/L.	Sotelano <i>et al.</i> 2018
Nitrite	< 0.5 mg/L.	Sotelano <i>et al.</i> 2018
Prophylaxis during incubation	None.	Sotelano pers. comm.
O ₂	Data not available or not determined.	
Incubation light	Data not available or not determined.	
Incubation temperature	Data not available or not determined.	
Incubation salinity	Data not available or not determined.	
Thermal Units	Data not available or not determined.	
Prophylaxis during incubation	None.	Sotelano pers. comm.

Table 45: Main parameters related to the performance of the false southern king crab in captivity.

Characteristics	Description	References
SGR	Data not available or not determined.	
FCR	Data not available or not determined.	
Fertilization rate	Data not available or not determined.	
Hatching rate	Data not available or not determined.	
Larvae survival	5-70 % (depending on the hatching season)	Tapella <i>et al.</i> 2019
Juvenile survival	Not determined in hatchery. Up to 40% of survival in the field, mortality mainly due to cannibalism	Sotelano <i>et al.</i> 2018
Adult survival	Data not available or not determined.	
Hatching	Extended hatching, 30-days per female.	Thatje <i>et al.</i> 2003

Table 46: Summary of false southern king crab feeding tests in aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Time until first exogenous feeding	~66 days.	Lovrich <i>et al.</i> 2003
Larvae	Lecitotrophic.	Lovrich <i>et al.</i> 2003
Juveniles	Not specific or formulated diet. In the field early juveniles can survive and grow through consumption of fouling.	Sotelano <i>et al.</i> 2018
Ongrowing	Data not available or not determined.	
Cannibalism	High during early juvenile massive culture.	Sotelano <i>et al.</i> 2012; 2016

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13.2.5 Ribbed Mussel (*Aulacomya ater*)

Distribution

The ribbed Mussel is a mytilid distributed from southern Brazil (30°S) to Tierra del Fuego on the Atlantic coast (55°S) and to Peru (12°S) on the Pacific coast (Cancino and Becerra 1978) (Figure 69). Besides, it is present on the South African coast (Barkai and Branch 1989).

Figure 69: AquaMaps (2019, October). Computer generated distribution maps for *Aulacomya ater* (ribbed mussel), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Biology

In natural banks, *A. ater* is usually accompanied by other molluscs, mainly *M. chilensis* with which it competes for space in the rocky habitat, sometimes displacing it (Cancino and Becerra 1978).

It is a gonochoric species, with spawning activity in the Beagle Channel over an extensive period, beginning in late winter-early spring (August-September), continuing until late summer, and a maximum peak in October-November (Tortorelli 1987; Avendaño and Cantillán 2014). However, few studies focus on understanding the dynamics of natural banks as a source of larvae, and the temporal distribution of banks used as capture sites is poorly understood (Avendaño and Cantillán 2014).

This species inhabits rocky or mixed bottoms from shallow to 40-50m in coastal waters. Usually, the banks of ribbed mussels are found between 5 to 20 m deep (Gutierrez *et al.* 2015). Adult individuals reach a maximum length of approximately 17 cm (Gutierrez *et al.* 2015).

The growth rate of this species seems to be quite variable. Growth rates between 0.28 mm/day and 0.96 mm/day have been recorded (Barkay and Branch 1989). In animals of a total height between 60 and 70 mm, the total body mass and soft tissue relationship vary from 38 % to 53 %, showing a mean of 43.62 % (de Vido de Mattio 1983).

Market

The ribbed mussel is less appreciated than the blue mussel and has a lower market value (Lasta *et al.* 1998). Mainly destined for the internal market, it is sold whole animal, fresh or frozen pulp and, to a lesser extent, canned (Gutierrez *et al.* 2015). In Chile, the minimum commercial size of *A. ater* is between 5.5 and 7 cm (SERNAPESCA 2020).

The current local market in Ushuaia city is low, where only 4 out of 22 seafood restaurants offer this species and is classified as not important in the menu (ASTRAL unpublished data).

Fisheries and wild stock status

The natural bank of *A. ater* in Brown Bay (Beagle Channel) in 2001 showed a density of 8.6 - 11.8 individuals/m² (Zampatti 2002). The maximum extraction from the natural bank of the Beagle Channel was 33 tn in 2008 (Pagani *et al.* 2012). Nowadays, there is no data on the fishery for this species and on the current status of the wild stock. Nevertheless, the comments from the artisanal fishers are that it is more challenging to achieve the fishery every time. In Chile, the fishery is stable, fluctuating between 4.500 and 9.000 tn/year from 2010 to 2020 (SERNAPESCA 2020).

Aquaculture

The aquaculture production of ribbed mussel in the Beagle Channel was approved in 2007 by Provincial Resolution N° 203/07, enabling this species to be cultivated as a by-product of blue mussel production. Nevertheless, the activity has not been fully developed, achieving a maximum production of only five tn in 2008 (Valdes *et al.* 2012). The farming of *Aulacomya ater* in Chile reached between 1000 and 4000 tn between 2010 and 2020 (SENARPECA 2020). The culture

methods are the same for blue mussels, and the market size of 70 mm could be obtained in a 2-year culture period (Cancino and Becerra 1978; Winter *et al.* 1984).

In Chile, the collection of seeds for ribbed mussels' cultivation is carried out from natural populations using artificial hard substrates (Lovatelli and Holthus 2008). The spatfall of *M. chilensis* and *A. atra* first showed almost homogeneous vertical distribution. It has been observed that free larvae of Mytilidae species are collectable in the same procedure (Ruzante *et al.* 1982). However, a stratified distributional spat pattern emerged after six months, with *M. chilensis* dominating between 0 and 7 m depth and *A. atra* dominating between 7 and 13 m depth. These authors observed a good catchment by collection devices made in polyethene monofilament, making possible the discrimination of the larvae from 500 µm of shell high.

Summary of Main Characteristics

Table 47 and Table 48 show biological parameters relevant to aquaculture, water quality needs, parameters related to the performance of the ribbed mussel in nature.

Table 47: Main biological parameters of the ribbed mussel relevant to aquaculture.

Characteristics	Description	References
Environment type	Benthic, predominantly hard bottoms in monospecific banks. Mainly sandy bottoms in mixed banks with <i>Mytilus chilensis</i> and <i>Aequipecten tehuelchus</i> .	Cancino and Becerra 1978
Depth	From the intertidal zone to 30 m depth.	Zaixso 2004
Max. length	17 cm.	Molina <i>et al.</i> 2015
Max. weight	Data not available or not determined.	
Max. age	Data not available or not determined.	
Length – Weight relationship	$\log L = -3.622 + 2.460 \log \text{Wet Weight}$.	Cancino and Becerra 1978
Growth curve	$L_t = 107.0 (1 - e^{-0.0549(t)})$.	Avendaño <i>et al.</i> 2016
Reproduction type	Gonochoric.	Pérez <i>et al.</i> 2013
Spawning season	May–July, August–November, and December–February.	Tortorelli 1987; Avendaño and Cantillán 2014
Maturation age	Data not available or not determined.	
Maturation length	Data not available or not determined.	
Type of eggs	Data not available or not determined.	
Newly larvae length	Data not available or not determined.	
Larvae feeding habits	Data not available or not determined.	
Juvenile feeding habits	Suspended filter feeding.	Montero <i>et al.</i> 2021
Adults feeding habits	Suspended filter feeding.	Montero <i>et al.</i> 2021

Table 48: Main parameters related to the performance of the ribbed mussel in nature.

Characteristics	Description	References
Initial seed density	Data not available or not determined.	
Final rearing density	Data not available or not determined.	
Fertilization rate	Data not available or not determined.	
Hatching rate	Data not available or not determined.	
Survival	Data not available or not determined.	
Obtaining gametes	Capture of natural seeds with artificial collectors	Winter <i>et al.</i> 1984
Fertilization	Data not available or not determined.	
Incubation salinity	Data not available or not determined.	

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13.2.6 Sea Lettuce (*Ulva spp.*) - Dissolved Inorganic Nutrients

Only a general description of each species of this group has been made.

Distribution

Ulva is a genus of green algae that can be found growing on rocky shores of seas and oceans worldwide, including the Antarctic Ocean, in intertidal and subtidal zones. It can also be found in brackish waters (Mantri *et al.* 2020) (Figure 70).

Figure 70: AquaMaps (2019, October). Computer generated distribution maps for *Ulva lactuca* (sea lettuce), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Biology

Ulva is known to occupy several ecological niches, which is attributed to its tolerance to key determinants such as light, temperature, and salinity (Mantri *et al.* 2020). The highest number of species recorded is in Asia (56), followed by Australia (40), Europe (38), North America (34), Africa (31), South America (20), and Antarctica (12). Several species of *Ulva* have been reported in Argentina: *U. lactuca*, *U. rigida* (C. Agardh) with a typical laminar thallus and with a tubular or filamentous thallus: *Enteromorpha lingulata* J. Agardh, *E. prolifera* (O.F. Müller) J. Agardh, *E. linza* J. Agardh, *E. bulbosa* (Suhr) Montagne and *E. torta* (Mertens) Reinbold (Boraso 1975, 1978, Rico *et al.* 1995). More recently, in the Beagle Channel, a tubular and a laminar type were observed (Macaya *et al.* 2020). Nevertheless, molecular taxonomy has not been carried out so far and some species should be revised.

The type species within the genus is *Ulva lactuca*, the thallus is a sheet of cells up to 30 cm long and two cells thick and is embedded in a tough gelatinous sheath, nevertheless there is high phenotypic plasticity among the species, so taxonomic identification can be quite challenging (Lobban and Harrison 1995; Bolton *et al.* 2016).

The holdfast, which anchors the alga to its substrate, is disk-like. In some calm waters with muddy or clay sediments, organisms may grow free of attachment, floating.

The life cycle consists of alternation of similar spore-producing (diploid) and gamete-producing (haploid) generations (Ghaderiardakani 2021). Asexual reproduction is typically by fragmentation.

Extraction and standing stock status

In many cases *Ulva* spp. arrive at the shore after storms or strong winds. These natural depositions have been collected and used in experiments in agriculture as a natural fertilizer, for its low nitrogen-rate emission, and in diet supplement for caged-egg production, for its high carotenoid content. Although there are many experiments on evaluating marine algae pharmaceutical properties, in Argentina there are still no local-made pharmacological products. Natural *Ulva* populations have not been extracted in Argentinean waters, therefore standing stocks are naturally regulated (Boraso *et al.* 2014).

Market

Ulva is considered a novel food with many nutritional values, and for its diverse uses in industry and medicine for different aims (Kraan 2013; Buschmann *et al.* 2017). *Ulva* spp. are also used as a feed source in aquaculture and for environmental bioremediation (Mantri *et al.* 2020).

Aquaculture

The culture of *Ulva* can be achieved by photo-bioreactor, land-based, or open-sea farming, each with variable potential production. For example, productions can reach 90 dw/ha/y in photo-bioreactors (Mhatre *et al.* 2018), or 40 dw ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ in land-based tanks grown at latitudes similar to those of Tierra del Fuego (55°) (Bruhn *et al.* 2011).

Ulva can be used as a co-culture species in integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) systems (Bolton *et al.* 2016). The main reasons behind the extensive use of *Ulva* are that (i) they are economically valuable, (ii) many members of this genus naturally adopt unattached morphotypes,

which fit more suitably to the commercial aquaculture units and (iii) *Ulva* species represent special affinities for growing in waters with high levels of nitrogen such as wastewater from fish farms (Bolton *et al.* 2009).

For enhancing growth and development, *Ulva* requires the presence of a combination of regulatory morphogenetic compounds released by associated epiphytic bacteria in addition to nutritional parameters (Ghaderiardakani 2021).

Ulva's sustainable growth and development can benefit from multi-trophic aquaculture systems and shallow water systems, due to the naturally enriched algal growth and morphogenesis promoting factors (AGPFs) and their *in-situ* production by bacteria in intensive algal aquacultures.

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13.2.7 Giant Kelp (*Macrocystis pyrifera*)

Distribution

M. pyrifera is distributed in cool coastal waters of the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans (Figure 71), limited because its reproduction is heavily influenced by water temperature (< 18-20°C, Dean and Deysher 1983) and nutrient availability (Zimmerman and Kremer 1984).

Figure 71: AquaMaps (2019, October). Computer generated distribution maps for *Macrocystis pyrifera* (giant kelp), with modelled year 2050 native range map based on IPCC RCP8.5 emissions scenario. Source <https://www.aquamaps.org>.

Biology

Macrocystis pyrifera, commonly known as giant kelp is a brown alga and one of the four species of the genus *Macrocystis*. *Macrocystis pyrifera* is the largest algal species, measuring up to 65 m long, and forms massive kelp forests, providing habitat for numerous fish, marine invertebrates, and other algae (Adami and Gordillo 1999). The typical *Macrocystis* adult sporophyte consists of numerous blade-bearing fronds that arise from a basal branching system of stipes. Lower portions of the basal stipe system also produce root-like haptera (holdfast) that grow downwards, wrapping around and forming an attachment to irregularities in solid substrata. These large algae are the diploid sporophyte generation, which produces spores in specialized blades near the holdfast. The spores develop into haploid male or female gametophytes, which eventually produce sexual gametes. The oogonia (eggs) are released with a pheromone that triggers nearby male gametophytes to release the biflagellate antherozoids (sperm) for fertilization (Cole 1968; North 1987).

Fisheries and wild stock status

In many countries, several species of *Macrocystis* are commercially harvested for direct human consumption and as a source of alginate, for industrial and biomedical applications. Wild resources are being harvested all along its distribution and in some countries even collapsing natural stands (e.g., Buschmann *et al.* 2014). In Argentina, the only consumption of *Macrocystis pyrifera* comes from wild harvesting, in Chubut, Santa Cruz and Tierra del Fuego provinces. This activity is mostly informal and artisanal, therefore, proper data on extracted annual biomass are not available.

Market

Eight genera provide most of the world's seaweed mariculture production; *Macrocystis pyrifera* is not included in that list and has been predominately only wild-harvested. Nevertheless, its properties associated with polysaccharides and proteins have resulted in increased interest in them (Purcell-Meyerink *et al.* 2021). In 2016, *M. pyrifera* global wild harvest yield reached 31.835 tonnes; however, only one tonne of *M. pyrifera* was produced through aquaculture (Purcell-Meyerink *et al.* 2021).

Aquaculture

Seaweeds now represent more than half of the marine and coastal aquaculture production (around 51%), worldwide production of seaweed reaches 32.4 million tonnes, valued at US\$13.3 billion (Chopin and Tacon 2021). Seaweed's mariculture has taken place mainly within nine East and Southeast Asian countries (99.5%), followed by Zanzibar and Chile (0.3 and 0.1%, respectively). *Macrocystis pyrifera* aquaculture started in 1972 in California and since then has gone through many stages and advances in culturing techniques have been done in different countries. The aquaculture process has been thoroughly described and performed in several countries. In Chile, exploitation of natural kelp forests to supply food to the abalone industry has led the resource to a critical level and aquaculture cultivation research has led to a potential productivity of 200 tonnes /ha/year and developing culture protocols for this and other species of macroalgae (see Avila *et al.* 2010). More recent work found that a 10-ha cultivation system with *M. pyrifera* priced at EUR 72/wet tonne would be profitable (Camus *et al.* 2019). *Macrocystis pyrifera* was only cultured in Perú, with Chile the predominant country for wild harvest collection followed by the USA (Purcell-Meyerink *et al.* 2021).

There is no aquaculture cultivation of *M. pyrifera* in Argentina to this date.

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